

**Abstract Proceeding of International Conference on
Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development (ICMASD-26)
January 29-31, 2026**

Organized by

Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune

Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli

&

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow, UP, India

Edited by

**Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
Dr. Pratap Raghunath Desai
Prof. R.K. Shukla**

**Abstract Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary
Approaches for Sustainable Development(ICMASD-26)**

Editors

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary
MKSES Educational Society,
Lucknow, UP, India

Dr. Pratap Raghunath Desai
Associate Professor
Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University,
(IMRDA) Maharashtra, India

Prof. R.K. Shukla
Professor
University of Lucknow, Lucknow, U.P., India

Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University

Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University is one of the top-ranking universities in India committed to providing the best academic experience. It was established by Dr. Patangrao Kadam in 1964 in Pune with the aim to provide enhanced learning opportunities and bring about intellectual awakening of people through the spread of education that would have a positive impact on the world. Today it has 8 campuses spread over different locations in India.

Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration

Established in 1994, the Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli aims to impart high-class management and computer education to the students of the region. In the academic year 2005-06, the institute has been brought under the ambit of Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune.

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow, U.P., India

The Science-Tech is one of the premier institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like conferences, seminars, workshops and training programmes in collaboration with many national & international organizations and Institute have own Publication house and Journals' to be published Edited books, Course books and research papers. The institute is run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education.

International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development(ICMASD-26)

Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune, Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli & Science-Tech Institute Lucknow, U.P. India has chosen an e-platform for to share their ideas and research by organizing a three day International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development(ICMASD-26). The Conference will include Keynote lectures, Invited lectures , Paper presentations and Poster presentations.

Bharati Vidyapeeth

(Deemed to be University)

Pune, India.

Founder Chancellor : Dr. Patangrao Kadam

★ Accredited with CGPA 3.60 at 'A++' Grade (2024) by NAAC ★

**Institute of Management and
Rural Development Administration, Sangli.**

IMRDA

Prof. Dr. Shivajirao Kadam
Chancellor
M.Sc. Ph.D.

Dr. Pallavi Jamsandekar
Director

Prof. Dr. Vivek A. Saoji
MBBS, M.S. (Surg.)
Vice Chancellor

Dr. Vishwajeet Kadam
B.Tech., M.B.A., Ph.D.
Pro Vice Chancellor

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli, Maharashtra and Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kunwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organise **International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development (ICMASD-26) from January 29-31, 2026**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to National and International students, Academicians, Researchers and Industrialists to interact and involve in sustainable development. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge in multidisciplinary approaches for sustainability. I sincerely appreciate the humble efforts of the Institute in providing a platform for students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to share their ideas and research outcome through the forum of this Conference.

I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Date: 31/01/2026

Prof. (Dr). Pallavi Jamsandekar.
Director,
BVDU, IMRDA,
Sangli, Maharashtra

Prof. Dr. Shivajirao Kadam
M.Sc., Ph.D.
Chancellor
Dr. Pallavi Jamsandekar
Director

Bharati Vidyapeeth

(Deemed to be University)

Pune, India.

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**Institute of Management and
Rural Development Administration, Sangli.**

IMRDA

Prof. Dr. Vivek A. Saoji
M.B.B.S., M.S. (Surg.)
Vice Chancellor
Dr. Vishwajeet Kadam
B.Tech., M.B.A., Ph.D.
Pro Vice Chancellor

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli, Maharashtra** and **Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kunwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, U.P.** are going to organise **International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development (ICMASD-26) from January 29-31, 2026**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to National and International students, Academicians, Researchers and Industrialists to interact and involve in sustainable development. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers, and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge in research in multidisciplinary approaches in research and innovation.

I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Date: 31/01/2026

Dr. Pratap Raghunath Desai
Convenor
Associate Professor

Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University,
(IMRDA) Maharashtra, India

MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860)

Reg. Office : Hydell Nahar Chauraha, Housing Society Sarojini Nagar, Lucknow - 226008, UP India

Head Office : 1ST Floor Building No.85 A (Nanak Arcade) Near Shani Mandir,

Parag Road, LDA Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226012, UP India

Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : manrajkuwarsec@gmail.com

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to share that Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli. Maharashtra and Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kunwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, U.P. are going to organise International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development (ICMASD-26) from January 29-31,2026. The conference will offer a great opportunity to discuss important issues, researches and topics from varied fields and will allow exchange of knowledge, ideas.

This conference is also an opportunity to meet virtually many eminent faculty, scholars and public health specialists of national and international repute on a common platform.

I & my team ensure that the audience will experience the exchange of scientific knowledge and return with a satisfactory take home message.

Date: 25/01/2026

Mrs. Shweta Singh
Chairman
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP, India

SCIENCE TECH INSTITUTE

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. Higher Education Department & Ordinance No. 8 of 2002)

Run by : **MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY**

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Parag Road, LDA Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226012, UP India

Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : sciencetech487@gmail.com

Message

On behalf of the whole organizing team, share Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Institute of Management and Rural Development Administration, Sangli. Maharashtra and Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kunwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, U.P. are going to organise International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development (ICMASD-26) from January 29-31,2026. I am sure that this online gathering will provide a common platform for academicians of different branches (Medical Sciences, Humanities etc.), public health experts & researchers to put forth their research studies and works.

I take this opportunity to acknowledge all the concerned authorities or persons for their permission, continuous support and guidance in arranging this conference. I am sure that this conference will succeed in the walk on Commerce this path for improving the various soft skills of faculties and students in varied fields.

Date: 23/01/2026

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Singh'.

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP

**International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable
Development(ICMASD-26) from Jan 29-31, 2026
Mode: Virtual**

**Organized by
Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune, Institute of Management and
Rural Development Administration, Sangli
In Collaboration with
Science Tech Institute, Lucknow,
Details of Programe Schedule DAY-1 (29th Jan, 2026)**

**For Technical Support Contact Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh (8299547952)
WhatsApp group Chat link: <https://chat.whatsapp.com/JKoWl6dD7EuF8pgt9QjuCf>**

Inaugural Session Hosted by: Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/87380572004?pwd=EfCQisakeqUdayzVamg25OoA3LmfTF.1 Meeting id- 873 8057 2004 Password- 471429	
11:20 AM	INAUGURATION AND WELCOME ADDRESS BY Conference Chair/Conveners/ Organizing Secretaries
11:45 AM-12:00 PM Key Note Speaker	Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Nodal Officer (MRU), Professor, Department of Pathology, PGIMS, Rohtak
12:00-12.25 PM IT01	Dr. N.K. Sharma: - “ Recent Advances in optical fiber communication system”
12:25-12:50 PM IT02	Dr. Poornima Singh: - “Enhancing the Prevention of Chronic Kidney Disease by Predictive Profiling”
12:50-1:15 PM IT03	Dr. Garima Awasthi: - “Sustainable Dye Bioremediation Using Genetically Engineered Microbes: Insights from In Silico Prediction and In Vitro Validation”
1.15-1.35 PM IT04	Dr.Usha Mallick“ Sustainable Development Goals: Role of Nurses”
1.35-2.00 PM IT05	Dr. Neha Singh “One Health Approach in Control of Vector-Borne Viral Infections”

2 PM to 5 PM Day 1 (29th Jan, 2026)

Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Neha Singh

Dr. Roop Kumar

Dr.Rajeev Kumar

Dr.Kavita Sahu

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/87380572004?pwd=EfCQisakeqUdayzVamg25OoA3LmfTF.1>

Meeting id- 873 8057 2004 Password- 471429

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A1	Dr.Virender Kumar	Clinical features, diagnosis, treatment strategies and management of disease of COVID-19:An update
A2	Dr.Sarika Deepak Patil	New Species of Black Mildew fungi from Western Ghats
A3	Mrs.Vaishali Sambhaji Mulik	The Role and Relevance of the Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS) in LIS research
A4	Dr.YUSRA JAMAL	" COMPARATIVE STUDY OF HYPERTENSIVE DISORDERS OF PREGNANCY WITH NORMOTENSIVE PREGNANCIES THROUGH EVALUATION OF COAGULATION PROFILE AND PLATELET COUNT "
A5	Dr.Shruti Bhonsle	Role of Community Organization in Achieving Sustainable Rural Development
A6	Prof.Mukesh Kumar	Quantum Computing Materials: Unlocking the Potential of Quantum Information Processing
A7	Dr.Dr.Amit Ashok Gajarmal	From Tradition to Technology: A Bibliometric Exploration of Digital Tools in Traditional Medicine (1995â€“2025)
A8	Dr.Sita Ram Pal	Mental Health and sustainable Development in India
A9	Dr.Sandeep Salunke	Reconfiguring India Financial Landscape: The Transformative Impact of Green Bonds within Sustainable Finance.
A10	Mr.MAHAVEER KHAWATAKOPPA	Exploring the Dynamics of Workplace Flexibility and Workâ€“Life Integration among Gen Z Professionals in Bengaluruâ€™s IT Sector
A11	Dr.Anjali Gupta	To Find out the most preferred and popular social media platform for consumers
A12	Dr.HARI MOHAN SAXENA	Shaping Customer Connections: AI's Role in Indian E-commerce Engagement
A13	Dr.Subia Ambreen	Nanostructured Transition Metal Oxides for Efficient Removal of Dyes from Wastewater
A14	Dr.UshaRani Moravineni	Impact of Flipped classrooms as a Teaching-Learning tool among the phase1 MBBS students.
A15	Mrs.Sangeetha	Antibacterial effect of Lactobacillus acidophilus against Enterococcus and streptococcus biofilm
A16	Dr. RAJENDRA YONZONE	Orchid Species from Darjeeling and Sikkim Himalayas: Flora of British India (Vol. V and Vol. VI) â€“ A Review
A17	Prof.Bhise Shailesh Shivajirao & Mrs.Aswale Vrushali Abhishek	IoT-Enabled Bioelectronics: Towards Intelligent Healthcare
A19	Dr ANUPAMA	Arcade of struthers - An anatomical variation with clinical significance

A20 & A59	Dr.ASTHA PATHAK Pallavi Singh	Renewable Energy Adoption and Carbon Emissions in the QUAD Countries: A Comparative Study of Divergent National Trajectories (2000-2021)"
A21	Dr.Jomon Lonappan	Interdisciplinary approaches to Entrepreneurship Education
A22	Dr.Meera Jacob	Patient Centered Governance practices in Hospitals
A23	Mr.Deepak Rajan DS	Inflammation Integrated Triglyceride Glucose Index: A Novel Index to identify Insulin Resistance among Metabolic Syndrome patients " A Case Control Study
A24	Dr.Rita Rani	Carbon Pricing, Economic Efficiency, and Behavioral Responses: A Multidisciplinary Perspective on Climate Policy Effectiveness in India
A25	Dr.Nirmala Subramanian	Insilico Molecular docking and Simulation Studies of Thymoquinone (TQ) against Nfa1 protein for treatment of Primary Amoebic Meningoencephalitis (PAM)
A26	Ms.Mohini gupta	Role of AI in growth of online business
A27	Dr.Priyanka Singh	Efficacy of Herbal Extract against Growth of Isolated Lactobacilli Bacterial Strain from Saliva of Patients with Dental Caries
A28	Dr.Sachin Ayarekar	Micro Mastery Iterative Learning Model (MMILM) for Effective Online Education
A29	Dr. Ganraj S. Mane and . Ms. Karuna Devar	An analytical study on effectiveness of training programme conducted at Kirloskar Ferrous Industries Limited, Solapur

6 PM to 12 PM Day 1 (29th Jan,2026)

Session Chair: Dr. Pratyasha Tripathi

Dr. Neelam Bansal

Dr. Hardeep Kour

Dr. Anuradha Mishra

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83979498869?pwd=W1vk7aGYla2Ag7kpb43QtEDs7zpR6G.1>

Meeting id- 839 7949 8869 Password- 33868

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	Name	Title
IT06	Dr.Prajna Jha	Adaptive Intelligence for HealthCare: A Meta-Learning Perspective
IT07	Dr.Mukti Sharma	Acid Base balance: Organ Cross talk in maintaining pH Homeostasis and rendition of Human Health Score
A30	Dr.Sunila	Substance use pattern among women in rural North India: A chart review'
A31	Dr.Nisha Kapoor	Genetic characterization of metabolically healthy and unhealthy obesity
A32	Dr.Ajit Kumar Vishwakarma	Robotics in Oral and Maxillofacial surgery: A Review
A33	Dr.Hariom Mishra	The Correlation between urban energy efficiency technology, global warming, focusing on sustainable power system and electrical supply through Conventional and Non-conventional energy uses in various places on the basis of Renewable Energy System of the role in Sustainable Urban Development in India.
A34	Dr.Kaneez Fatima	The Right to Food as a Human Right in India: A Gender Justice Perspective under the National Food Security Act, 2013
A35	Dr.Bandana Dwivedi	Development of the biodegradable polymers for sustainable packaging

A36	Dr.Rajani Singh	Development of the biodegradable polymers for sustainable packaging
A37	Dr.Sumita Chatterjee	The Socio- Economic Position of Women in the Lodha Tribe of West Bengal
A38	Dr.Anand B Sidramgoal	A Comparative Study of Poisson and Negative Binomial Regression Models for Analyzing HIV/AIDS Transmission Risk Factors
A39	Dr.Suvarna Gulabrao Bhokare	TAPINAROF LOADED CHITOSAN NANOPARTICLES: PREPARATION EVALUATION AND IN VITRO RELEASE STUDIES
A40	Dr. Ritu Mahajan	Effect of growth regulators on callus induction and somatic embryogenesis in <i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.
A41	Dr.Sujoy Kumar Majumdar	Patterns and Determinants of Out-of-Pocket Health Care Payments and Financing Strategies among Urban Households in West Bengal
A42	Dr.Amit Prakash Sharma	Investigating the Impact of Perception on Job Satisfaction Among Dental Care Providers in Delhi NCR
A43	Mr.Mohd Faheem	Synthesis Of [68Ga]Triazine Linked With Glu-Ureido Targeting PSMA as Theranostics
A44	Ms.BEKI SUNIL	Implementing Outcome-Based Education (OBE) in Management Curricula: A Strategic Framework for Competency-Based
A45	Miss.Laxmi	Preparation of compost from Lignocellulosic waste and its effect on soil properties compared with urea and compost prepared from domestic waste
A46	Dr.Ashvini Vitthal Kamble	A Study to review an interdisciplinary research of Ayurvedic Rasayana therapy and genomic insights for health care interventions
A47	Ms.Deepmala Kumari	Drug Repurposing and co-adjuvant therapy for cancer care
A48	Mr.BHAGWAT SUKHADEO KALE	EVALUATION OF DIAGNOSTIC PERFORMANCE OF AMYLASE AND LIPASE IN PRE-OPERATIVE PANCREATIC DUCTAL ADENOCARCINOMA
A49	Ms.Janhavi Hemant Pednekar	Comparative Study of Performance of Plagiarism Detection Tools
A50	Mr.Amrut Mohan Jadhav	Bibliometric Mapping of Machine Learning for Cybersecurity
A51	Dr.Vandana	Type 2 Diabetes Healthcare Use Patterns: Gurugram, Haryana
A52	Miss.Shivam Sakshi	Work- Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs), Associated Factors, Preventive Practices, and Barriers Among Information Technology (IT) Professionals in Gurugram: A Cross - Sectional Study
A53	Mr.Digvijaysinh Anil Pawar	Citation Analysis of Ph.D. Theses: A Comprehensive Overview
A54	Dr.Shilpi Bhat	Comparative analysis of Vitamin D and Heart Rate Variability in Hypertensive subjects and Normotensive individuals with a Family History of Hypertension.
A55	Ms.Ritasana Bhattacharya	Animating Sustainability: Narrative Strategies of Sustainability in Hayao Miyazaki's Animated Cinema
A56	Mrs.USHA TANAJI PAWAR	The Role of Citation Analysis in Measuring Research Impact and Scholarly Influence
A57	Miss.Mansi Singh	Revisiting Organizational Socialization and Onboarding Through Bibliometric Analysis
A58	Miss.Areeba Khan	Instant Delivery Services: A Bibliometric Analysis
A60	Mrs.Chhavi	Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using Citrus Orange peels and evaluation of their anticancer Property
A61	Ms.Kavita	The AI impacts on Critical Thinking
A62	Mrs.LAVANYA R	Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) of Artificial Intelligence in Nutrition among Physiotherapy (BPT) Students in Bangalore using Bayesian Regression

		Modelling.
A63	Mr.SHUBHAM PUSHKAR	"A Systematic Review On Magnetic Properties Of Mn-Ni Based Full-Heusler Alloys"
A64	Mrs.Shivi Agarwal	Stress to strength: role of psychological hardiness in advancing sustainable future
A65	Mr.Karan Singh	Isolation, identification & optimization of new microbial strain from soil sample for the production of cellulase.
A66	Miss.MEENU ELIZABATH BENNY	Efficient Removal of Safranine Dye from Aqueous Solutions using Thuidium cymbifolium (Dozy & Molk.) Dozy & Molk. : A Green Approach
A67	Mr.Soumen Sarkar	Performance Management Systems in Manufacturing Industries: Foundations for Productivity, Engagement, Strategic Alignment and Resilience: A Literature Review".
A68	Mr.Bharat Suryawanshi	Micro Mastery Iterative Learning Model (MMILM) for Effective Online Education
A69	Mr.KANAGARAJ K	Computational Investigation of Self-Healing Concrete Structures: Finite Element Analysis and Artificial Neural Networks Study.

12.00 PM to 10 PM Day 2 (30th Jan,2026)

Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Roop Kumar

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84422613231?pwd=PlbPYpFt7fpg0SAInw6QyVIq4ejvOO.1>

Meeting id- 844 2261 3231 Password- 164130

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A71	Ms.KANEEZ FATIMA	Hexanediamine-assisted surface modification of ZnO nanoparticles for dielectric property tailoring and enhanced asymmetric supercapacitor device performance
A72	Ms.Nazia Zameer	MESOPOROUS IONIC LIQUID-FUNCTIONALIZED TRIAZINE-BASED COVALENT ORGANIC POLYMER; A HETEROGENEOUS CATALYST FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF PYRANOPYRAZOLES AND PYRANOCOUMARINS UNDER SUSTAINABLE CONDITIONS
A73	Mrs.Chhaya Vikram jawlikar	Biochemical Evidence of Systemic Inflammation in Lean Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Role of C-Reactive Protein
A74	Ms.Anita Verma	Immediate Effects of a Structured 4-Week Yoga Program on Heart Rate Variability and Autonomic Regulation in Healthcare Workers: A Randomized Controlled Trial
A75	Mrs.SUDAIVI PRABHAKAR KADAM	Effect of Self-Care Management Intervention package on Self-Care Efficacy among Women with Breast Cancer : Pre Interventional Report
A76	Ms.R.Midhuna	Invisible Administration: How Backend Digital Systems Shape Public Service Delivery in India
A77	Miss.Priyanka Singh	Computational Design and Optimization of an Ideal FrGeCl ₃ Lead-Free Perovskite Solar Cell for Theoretical Benchmark Analysis
A78	Ms.shatakshi kumari	Impact of climate change and environmental stressors on skin health: scope for plant based therapeutic approaches
A79	Mrs.Archana Adhikari	In-silico Design and Validation of PCR Primers for AT1R Gene Polymorphism in Hypertensive Patients
A80	Miss.Diksha Maurya	Mg ₂ Ni ₂ Nd ₂ Metallic Glass as a Mechanically Robust and Optically Active Material: First-Principles Evidence for Future Optical Coatings
A81	Ms.MONA KRITI	"Air pollution associated gut microbiome alterations in Type 2 Diabetes: Evidence from central Indian population"
A82	Dr.Nimty Raina Ambardar	Comparative analysis of serum cortisol variations induced by dental and periodontal pathologies vs psychological stress
A83	Mr.KUMAR S	LABORATORY MARKERS FOR EARLY DETECTION OF SEVERE DENGUE BY THE IMPLICATIONS FOR LENGTH OF HOSPITAL STAY
A84	Mr.K Ravinder Reddy	AI Regulation in India: A Global Comparative Perspective
A85	Mrs.C.Chandraleka	Clinical and laboratory profile of scrub typhus cases detected by RT PCR among adult febrile patients in a tertiary care hospital, Vellore, South India.
A86	Miss.Arockya Stafi A	Pomiferin as a Dual Action Bioactive for Therapeutic Use In Vitro Antioxidant and Anti Inflammatory Insights
A87	Miss. Durga Lakshmanan	Investigating The Molecular Mechanisms Underlying The Therapeutic Effects Of The Natural Alkaloid Cephalotaxine In Human Osteosarcoma Cells (MG-63 Cells)
A88	Mr.Abhijit Reang	Decoding Xylanolytic Potential in Rumen Bacteria through Genome Annotation and CAZyme Analysis
A89	Ms.PRIYA KUSHWAHA	Phytosynthesized Iron Nanoparticles Enhance Seed Germination in Pea (Pisum sativum L. var. GS-10): Concentration-Dependent Effects

A90	Mrs.ASWATHY .M	Variations in the branching pattern of Axillary artery - A cadaveric study
A91	Miss.RAINA V JOSEPH	Multiple variation in the tendon of abductor policis longus - A cadaveric study
A92	Mr.sajad ahmad sofi	phytochemistry and pharmacological properties of saussurea costus
A93	Mrs.Sona Ghosh	Exploring the anticancer potential of selected plant extracts: cytotoxic evaluation and partial purification

10:00 AM to 6 PM Day 3 (31st Jan, 2026) **Session Chair: Dr.Alka Singh Bhatt**
Dr. Garima Awasthi
Dr.Yasashavi Singh
Mobile No.- 8299547952
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/87863703667?pwd=FyFM48FveLZsbvTcJvLHFxtlaCWPtV.1>
Meeting id- 878 6370 3667 Password- 584365
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
IT08	Dr.Neelam Bansal	Inclusive Education: Fostering Inclusive Learning Environment
IT09	Dr. Priti Goyal	Nanotechnology for Energy Storage and Conversion Applications
IT10	Dr Pratyasha Tripathi	A Sustainable Development Perspective for Equitable Health Assessment
IT11	Dr. Rajeev Kumar	AI-Driven Durability Evaluation of Software Systems
IT12	Dr. Kavita Sahu	PyReliability: An AI-Driven Framework for Enhancing Software Reliability using Python
A94	Miss.Monika Mukund Adsule	Development of cooling bag using garment industrial waste.
A95	Ms.Suaad Aziz	Reconstructing misconceptions of parents about Intellectual Disability in community
A96	Dr.Sai Sravani B	Serum Interleukin 26 as a biomarker for disease activity assessment and association of single nucleotide polymorphism in interleukin 26 gene in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus
A97	Dr.Yash Bhardwaj	A CASE STUDY ON AUTOIMMUNE HEPATITIS IN MIDDLE AGED FEMALE A RARE CAUSE OF CHRONIC LIVER DISEASE IN INDIA
A98	Dr.Diksha Aghi	OSMOTIC DEMYELINATION SYNDROME A RARE CASE REPORT
A99	Miss.Kuhu	Solid Lipid Nanoparticles and Nanostructured Lipid Carriers as Advanced Nanoplatforms for Breast Cancer Treatment
A100	Dr.Aditya Seth	AI-Integrated Waste Management as a Preventive Health Strategy: A Multidisciplinary Analysis of Environmental Sanitation and Disease Burden in Urban Settlements
A101	Dr.Sriyansh jain	Association of Smoking, ABO Blood Group, and Lifestyle Determinants with Breast Cancer in a Tertiary Care Centre in Sagar District, Madhya Pradesh
A102	Miss.Manasi Sameer Sawant	Statistical Analysis of Spending on Food Delivery Apps
A103	Miss.Vaishnavi Pramod	A Statistical Analysis of Consumer Behaviour towards Discounts and Coupons

	Nalawade	
A104	Miss.SHAILYA PREETI	Blood sugar-controlled insulin delivery: Mechanisms, Technologies, and Future Direction
A105	Dr.Tenin Josewin	EFFECTS OF TRADITIONAL SOUTH INDIAN SNACKS ON REGULATING AUTISM SYMPTOMS IN CHILDREN COMPARED TO OTHER DIETARY GROUPS
A106	Miss.Ramsha Syed	CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing in fruit crops: Steps towards improving fruit traits and ensuring food security
A107	Miss.GARGI SHARMA	Traditional medicinal plant resources of North East India: a sustainable development and utility for healthcare needs
A108	Ms.Loveness John Kimaro	Lessons from Multi-OMICS Approaches for Investigating Plant- Endophyte Interactions: Is it time for revolution in Sustainable Agriculture?
A109	Miss.ANSHIKA TIWARI	A study of available family support for persons with intellectual disability in the community
A110	Dr.A.DEEPIKA	INVITRO ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY OF CS/PVA HYDROGEL INCORPORATING ZALEYA PENTENDRA EXTRACT AGAINST LUNG CANCER CELL LINE
A111	Dr.Kalaiarasi.S	Biogenic silver nanoparticles synthesized from sprouted Trigonella seeds exhibit Dual Antioxidant and Anti Diabetic activities
A112	Miss.Saumya Mishra	Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act
A113	Mr.Ishu Pandey	VISION MEETS LANGUAGE: AN IMAGE CAPTIONING FRAMEWORK USING DEEP LEARNING
A114	Dr.Anu Aksharaa JP	Body Fat Distribution Index(BFDI): A Novel Adiposity Marker for Identifying Metabolic Syndrome in Adults at a Tertiary Care Hospital
A115	Dr.Sanjay Redhu	Poster - To study upper limb nerve conduction velocity among professional computer operators and healthy volunteers from karnal.
A116	Mr.Sayed Baqar Abbas	Serverless document verification. system for colleges and universities
A117	Mr.Ajeet Singh Yadav	Need assessment of Parents having children with intellectual disability
A118	Dr. Sonia Saini	Importance of Taxonomy in Management of Invasive Plant Species
A119	Ms.Kiran Rao	Adolescents preference and perception towards Ayurvedic medicines: A mixed methods study from Pimpri Chinchwad Pune India
A120	Dr.Kumar Satyendra Yadav	Time Series Analysis of Chronic Kidney Disease Prevalence and Dialysis Demand for Sustainable Healthcare Planning
A121	Mr.Nitin Jaswal	2D Animated Storytelling as a Medium for Enhanced Emotional and Cognitive Engagement
A122	Ms.MARIA SAMREEN	Time Series Analysis of Chronic Kidney Disease Prevalence and Dialysis Demand for Sustainable Healthcare Planning
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Participation in Conference	
P1	Dr.Sai Shanmukh Vemparala
P2	Ms.balvinder kaur
P3	Dr.DAVE BHARGAV NILESHBHAI
P4	Dr.Aditi Snehi
P5	Dr.Shahirajpreet Kaur Gill
P6	Dr.Ambika Sharma
P7	Miss.Snehal Sanjay Sonawane
P8	Prof.Ranjit Guha
P9	Dr.Dipti G Pardeshi
P10	Ms.Divya Sarang
P11	Dr.Sudha Sharma
P12	Dr.Shikha Jaiswal
P13	Mr.c saravanan
P14	Dr.Pranjal

Valedictory Session at 6pm PM on 31st Jan 2026

Zoom link: Join Zoom Meeting

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Meeting ID: 878 6370 3667

Passcode: 584365

Note: Join all Participants

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Recent Advances in Optical Communication System

ABSTRACT

Optical communication is one type of communication where optical fibre is mainly used as transmission media for carrying the light signals to the remote end in place of electrical current. The basic building blocks of this system mainly include a modulator or demodulator a transmitter or a receiver a light signal and the transport channel. Optical communication system transmits data optically using optical fibers. This process can be achieved by changing the electronic signals to light pulse using laser or LED light sources. As concern to electrical transmission optical fibers have mostly replaced copper wire communication within core networks due to many benefits like high bandwidth, transmission range is huge, very low loss and no electromagnetic interference. With the increasing use of Internet or mobile phones, the capacity of backbone optical communication link has been continuously growing across the world and especially in India. The total optical fiber cable deployed for BharatNet initiative of Government of India increases from 3.4 million km to 5 million km in 2024-25.

Considering this deep proliferation this Paper attempts to capture the diverse research carried out in India in the domain of optical communication.

Keywords: Optical fibre, Total Internal Refraction (TIR), Modulator, Demodulator.

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IT-02

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Enhancing the Prevention of Chronic Kidney Disease by Predictive Profiling

Abstract:

The frequency of chronic kidney disease (CKD), a major non-communicable illness with significant clinical and financial costs worldwide, is steadily increasing. This study examines a wider range of clinical, metabolic, and symptomatic predictors, despite the fact that diabetes and hypertension are known causes of chronic kidney disease. The multifaceted nature of disease prediction was highlighted by the multivariable logistic regression model, which found 11 independent variables that accounted for 23.5% of the variability in CKD risk as measured by Nagelkerke R^2 . These results highlight the multifaceted character of CKD progression and support the necessity of multifactorial screening procedures.

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**Sustainable Dye Bioremediation Using Genetically Engineered Microbes:
Insights from In Silico Prediction and In Vitro Validation**

Abstract

The large-scale discharge of synthetic dyes from textile and allied industries represents a major environmental challenge due to their toxicity, persistence, and resistance to conventional treatment processes. Recent advances in genetic engineering and computational biology provide new opportunities to design efficient microbial systems for dye biodegradation. An integrated *in-silico* and *in-vitro* framework enhances microbial dye degradation using genetically engineered microorganisms. Computational pathway analysis and metabolic flux modeling was first applied to identify key enzymatic bottlenecks and regulatory nodes involved in dye degradation pathways. Based on these predictions, microbial strains were genetically engineered to overexpress dye-degrading enzymes, including azoreductases, laccases, and peroxidases, while minimizing the formation of toxic aromatic amine intermediates. *In-vitro* biodegradation experiments were conducted under controlled fermentation conditions to validate computational predictions. The engineered strains demonstrated significantly improved decolorization efficiency, faster degradation kinetics, and reduced half-life values compared to native strains across multiple dye classes. The *in-silico* predictions and experimental outcomes confirmed the reliability of the computational models for guiding strain optimization. The integrated approach also enabled rapid screening of dye and microbe interactions and prediction of degradation performance under untested conditions, thereby reducing experimental time and cost. Overall, this study highlights the effectiveness of combining *in-silico* metabolic engineering with *in-vitro* validation to develop robust, eco-

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friendly microbial platforms for the sustainable treatment of dye-contaminated wastewater.

Keywords: GEM; pathway analysis; metabolic flux; dye; bioremediation; wastewater treatment

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Sustainable Development Goals: Role of Nurses

Introduction -Nurses are foundational to achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by bridging clinical care with education, advocacy, and community engagement to address health, poverty, and environmental sustainability. Acting on the front lines, they are crucial for achieving SDG 3 (health and well-being), while also advancing gender equality, reducing inequality, and ensuring sustainable, resilient communities.

Sustainable development Goals –

In September 2015, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The goals build on the vital principle of “leaving no one behind”, and emphasizes a holistic approach to achieving sustainable development for all.

GOAL 1: No Poverty

End poverty in all its forms everywhere (eradicate extreme poverty currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day.)

GOAL 2: Zero Hunger

End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture

GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being

Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages

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GOAL 4: Quality Education

Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all

GOAL 5: Gender Equality

Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls

GOAL 6: Clean Water and Sanitation

Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all

GOAL 7: Affordable and Clean Energy

Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all

GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all

GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure

Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation

GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality

Reduce inequality within and among countries

GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities

Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable

GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production

Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns

GOAL 13: Climate Action

Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

GOAL 14: Life Below Water

Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development

GOAL 15: Life on Land

Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss

GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions

Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide

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access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels

GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goal

Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.

Role of Nurses-

A nurse is a vital healthcare professional who provides direct patient care, promotes health, prevents illness, and advocates for individuals, families, and communities, working across diverse settings like hospitals, clinics, and homes, with various specializations such as, requiring education, licensing, and compassionate skills to manage care, administer treatments, and offer support during health challenges.

Core Responsibilities

- **Patient Care:**

Administering medication, monitoring vital signs, providing physical care, and performing medical procedures.

- **Advocacy & Education:**

Educating patients and families about health conditions, treatments, and promoting healthy lifestyles.

- **Collaboration:**

Working closely with doctors, therapists, and other healthcare staff as part of a team.

- **Assessment:**

Observing, recording, and reporting symptoms, reactions, and patient progress.

- **Emotional Support:**

Offering comfort and support to patients and their families during vulnerable times.

Core Roles of Nurses in Achieving the SDGs:

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- **SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being:** Nurses provide essential preventive, curative, and rehabilitative services, managing chronic conditions and improving maternal/child health to reduce mortality.
- **Universal Health Coverage (UHC):** As primary care providers, nurses are central to ensuring access to quality, affordable healthcare for all.
- **Addressing Social Determinants of Health:** Nurses work to reduce inequalities by treating vulnerable, rural, and underserved populations.
- **Environmental Health and Advocacy:** They educate on environmental impacts on health, promote sustainable practices in healthcare, and contribute to designing resilient, sustainable communities.
- **Education and Empowerment (SDG 4, 5):** Nurses promote education, gender equality, and women's empowerment.

Actionable Approaches:

- **Integrating SDGs into Education:** Incorporating the 17 SDGs into nursing curricula is recommended to prepare future nurses for these challenges.
- **Policy and Leadership:** Nurses use their voices to lead, with organizations like the International Council of Nurses (ICN) highlighting their role in shaping health policies.
- **Local and Global Action:** Nurses contribute by implementing sustainable practices, participating in research, and advocating for policy changes at local and international levels.

Conclusion- The full realization of the 2030 Agenda relies heavily on the active contribution of nurses, as they are essential to building healthier, more equitable, and sustainable societies.

Key Words- Sustainable development goals, Nurse

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One Health Approach in Control of Vector-Borne Viral Infections

Abstract

Vector-borne viral infections such as dengue, chikungunya, Zika, yellow fever, West Nile virus, and others remain a major public health burden, causing over 700,000 deaths each year globally and accounting for about 17% of all infectious diseases (WHO, 2024). In India, particularly in regions like Chhattisgarh with dense forests, tribal areas, and close human-animal contact, these diseases thrive due to expanding vector habitats, climate change, urbanization, poor sanitation, and zoonotic spillovers. Recent reports highlight ongoing challenges, including malaria and filariasis in remote districts, and emerging threats like Chandipura virus outbreaks affecting other neighboring states. The One Health approach provides a vital, integrated strategy by linking human, animal, and environmental health. It promotes cross-sectoral collaboration among physicians, veterinarians, entomologists, ecologists, and policymakers to tackle diseases at their shared interface. Key elements include integrated surveillance that combines human case reporting, animal reservoir monitoring (e.g., birds, monkeys, pigs), vector tracking, and environmental data for early warning and predictive modeling. In practice, this means strengthening diagnostics, community education, source reduction for breeding sites, judicious vector control, and vaccination programs (e.g., for Japanese encephalitis). India's National One Health Mission and integration with the Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) aim to improve data sharing and rapid outbreak response. Despite barriers like fragmented systems, resource gaps, and workforce shortages, One Health offers clear benefits: earlier detection, reduced transmission, innovation in controls, and better preparedness against re-emerging threats. Adopting it more fully is crucial for sustainable control of vector-borne viral diseases in diverse settings like India.

Key Words: One Health, Vector-borne viral infections, Integrated surveillance, Climate change, Mosquito vectors, Early warning systems, National One Health Mission

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Adaptive Intelligence for HealthCare: A Meta-Learning Perspective

Abstract

Encouraged by the rapid increase of applications of Artificial Intelligence technologies in the healthcare field, has motivated the development Machine Learning (ML) models to enhance the predictability and diagnosis of the disease. The data in the healthcare field includes multiple inter-related domains with varying formats. The traditional ML models have performed efficiently in healthcare, but they are limited to single specific-domain problem statements. The meta-learner based algorithm tries to overcome the challenges usually associated with related cross-domain data, and strives towards generalization of the model. The meta-learner inherent capability to adapt parameters rapidly to any new data, any new example makes it an interesting field of research, especially, in healthcare domain which constantly faces issues with ever-evolving data patterns and data scarcity in a particular domain. The meta-learning model enables the algorithm to apply the prior knowledge and past experiences to adjust efficiently to new tasks and concepts. As a result, meta-learner can effectively manage domain-shifts, and facilitate cross-domain knowledge transfer. This capability allows the integration of data and insights from diversified medical conditions to develop models for a specific target condition, while considering individual differences in health biomarkers at the same time. The meta-learner-as a part of Machine Learning Algorithms enable the study of sparse data collected in different formats, thereby continuously improving the prior knowledge and experience of the algorithm. These unique features position meta-learner as a promising framework for developing impactful solutions in diverse healthcare contexts. In this session, we discuss the fundamental concepts of Meta-learner, and the essential techniques of the meta-learner. The session also highlights the current problem statements in the

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healthcare research, discusses possible solutions, and future direction of MetaLearner-based healthcare solutions

Keywords: Healthcare necessities, Clinical Intelligence, Cross-domain adaptive learner, Meta-learner

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Acid Base Balance: Organ Cross talk in maintaining pH Homeostasis and rendition of Human Health Score

ABSTRACT

Human Physiology relies on a delicate balance of acidity and alkalinity, reflected by blood pH. Disruptions in this equilibrium can contribute to chronic conditions like metabolic disorders, inflammation, and cancer. Causative factors may be the diets, environments or disease. Acidity and Alkalinity is defined as concentrations of HYDROGEN ions (pH) in BODY FLUIDS.

For the smooth functioning of cells, our body chose a distinct yet specific range of pH for ionic equilibrium, retaining homeostasis milieu. Skin is mildly acidic (4.5-5.5), Stomach enteroceles very acidic (1.5-3.5), blood is slightly alkaline (7.35-7.45). pH is crucial as it deviates enzyme functions impairing Basal Metabolism, denature protein structure/function, disrupts cell signalling, alter shifts in electrolytes balance affecting heart, nerves muscles etc. Human bodies maintain pH homeostasis via interplay of Lungs Kidneys, skins and biochemical buffers.

Cross talks and Homeostasis: Lung, kidneys, skin orchestrate pH balance. Be it Respiratory or Metabolic mediated acidosis /alkalosis both organs synergistically toil via respiratory or renal compensation. Understanding organ crosstalk's may inform diagnosis, managements of severe acid base disorders. Mechanisms of regulation is complex by respiration hyper/hypo ventilation or/and reabsorption /excretion of metabolite ions. Disruptions lead to acidosis (pH<7.35), alkalosis (pH>7.35) impacting cellular health.

PRAL implies **Potential Renal Acid Load** assessing Food impact on Body's Acid Base balance. All foods have specific PRAL score of positive and negative which impacts kidney thence. Negative PRAL is Good whereas positive PRAL including Acidifying Foods/ Drugs have adverse load on kidney. Acid base balance is critical because even small pH deviations can impair cardiovascular functions, enzyme activity and

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neurological status potentially leading to life threatening complications, critical factor in ICU patient management. **Acidity-Alkaline Index (AAI)** is must and reflects an individual's pH balance. AAI could offer a holistic and clinical threshold for assessing and optimizing health, guiding Dietary and Lifestyle interventions. In conclusion, emphasis should be placed on consumption of **Organically produced foods** & optimize blood by limiting animal protein, sodium, potassium, regulating PRAL /**AAI** to curtail organs strain.

Keywords: Acidity-Alkaline Index, organ crosstalk's, Homeostasis, PRAL, Metabolic Health Score.

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Building Inclusive Academic Environments: Strategies for Leaders

Abstract

Education is the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and habits through learning, teaching, training, or research. It helps individuals develop intellectually, socially, emotionally, and professionally. Education is a fundamental right, essential for the development of individuals and societies. Yet, for many years, students with diverse needs — including those with disabilities, from marginalized communities, or with different cultural or linguistic backgrounds — have been excluded from mainstream educational opportunities. Inclusive education is a transformative approach that aims to eliminate these barriers, ensuring that all students, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds, learn together in the same environment. It explores the concept of inclusive education, its objectives, benefits, challenges, and effective strategies for implementation. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines inclusive education as "a process of strengthening the capacity of the education system to reach out to all learners." It involves restructuring the school culture, policies, and practices to accommodate every student's unique needs.

Keywords: Inclusive education, inclusive environment, policies, equal access, social justice.

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Nanotechnology for Energy Storage and Conversion Applications

High-performance, sustainable, and effective energy storage technologies must be developed in response to the world's growing energy needs. Because nanotechnology has special qualities like enhanced conductivity and surface area, it has the potential to significantly improve the performance of energy storage devices through the manipulation of materials at the nanoscale. With an emphasis on capacitors and batteries, this article explores the critical role that nanotechnology plays in developing energy storage technologies, including lithium-ion, sodium-sulfur, and redox flow. We examine the many uses of nanomaterials in batteries, including separators, electrolytes, and electrode materials (such as metal oxides and carbon nanotubes). The development of improved nanostructured materials is being undertaken to tackle issues such as interfacial side reactions. We also explore other methodologies to manufacture nanomaterials, focusing on their scalability, such as top-down (like ball milling), bottom-up (like chemical vapor deposition), and hybrid methods. Although there are still issues with cost-effectiveness and environmental impact, solid-state batteries and the combination of nanomaterials with artificial intelligence for better energy storage are two new developments that bode well for nanotechnology in energy storage.

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Robust Outlier Accommodation in Maternal Mortality Rate Distributions: A Sustainable Development Perspective for Equitable Health Assessment

Abstract Sustainable development places strong emphasis on ensuring equitable access to quality healthcare and reducing preventable maternal deaths, as reflected in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG-3 (Good Health and Well-Being). Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) is a core indicator used globally to monitor progress toward maternal health targets and health system sustainability. However, from a statistical standpoint, MMR data are inherently complex, frequently exhibiting right skewness, heavytailed behavior, and extreme observations arising from socio-economic disparities, fragile health systems, geographic isolation, and crisis situations. These extreme values, often labeled as outliers, represent populations most at risk and therefore hold crucial relevance for sustainable development planning. Conventional statistical practices commonly address such outliers through trimming, winsorization, or deletion, which may inadvertently suppress critical information about vulnerable regions and marginalized communities. This study argues that such exclusionbased approaches are inconsistent with the principles of sustainable development, which prioritize inclusivity, equity, and evidence-based policymaking. Accordingly, the present work proposes a robust outlier accommodation framework for analyzing MMR distributions that preserves the informational content of extreme observations while ensuring reliable statistical inference. The proposed methodology adopts flexible, skewed, and heavy-tailed distributional models capable of naturally accommodating extreme maternal mortality values without distorting parameter estimates. Robust estimation techniques are employed to limit the undue influence of extreme observations while recognizing their structural

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importance. A simulation-based evaluation is conducted under realistic contamination scenarios that reflect genuine public health stressors rather than random measurement errors. Comparative results demonstrate that classical mean-based approaches tend to underestimate maternal risk and variability when extreme observations are excluded. In contrast, the robust framework yields stable parameter estimates, improved uncertainty quantification, and clearer identification of high-risk regions. From a sustainable development perspective, the findings highlight that extreme maternal mortality values are indicators of systemic inequality and health system fragility rather than statistical anomalies. In conclusion, robust outlier accommodation in MMR distributions provides a statistically sound and sustainability-oriented approach to maternal health assessment. Integrating such methods into public health monitoring frameworks can strengthen progress evaluation toward the Sustainable Development Goals and support the design of equitable, resilient, and inclusive healthcare systems.

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AI-Driven Durability Evaluation of Software Systems

Abstract: This paper presents an AI-driven approach to evaluating the durability of software systems, focusing on predicting and enhancing their lifespan. The proposed framework leverages machine learning algorithms to assess software durability based on factors like code quality, testing coverage, and maintenance history. By identifying potential vulnerabilities and areas of improvement, this AI-driven evaluation enables developers to optimize software systems for improved reliability, scalability, and overall durability. The AI-driven durability evaluation framework utilizes real-time data and advanced analytics to predict potential software failures and suggest proactive maintenance strategies. This approach helps reduce downtime, improve user experience, and increase the overall lifespan of software systems. Key aspects of this framework include data collection, feature engineering, model training, and continuous monitoring.

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**PyReliability: An AI-Driven Framework for Enhancing Software Reliability
using Python**

Abstract: PyReliability is an AI-driven framework that leverages Python to evaluate and enhance software reliability by analyzing code quality, testing coverage, and maintenance history. It utilizes machine learning algorithms to provide actionable insights, enabling developers to identify vulnerabilities, optimize testing strategies, and predict software failures, ultimately reducing downtime and improving user experience. By integrating with popular Python libraries, PyReliability helps developers improve code quality, enhance testing efficiency, and reduce maintenance costs, leading to more reliable software systems.

OP 1

Formulation and evaluation of microemulsion of minoxidil for alopecia areata**Virender Kumar^{1*}, Aditya Yadav¹ and Jyoti Mundlia¹****¹College of Pharmacy, Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences
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Abstract: Alopecia areata is a common hair loss disorder that requires effective and patient-friendly topical treatment. Although minoxidil (MXD) is widely used, its limited solubility and skin penetration reduce therapeutic efficiency. This study aimed to develop and evaluate a microemulsion-based delivery system to improve the stability, penetration, and sustained release of minoxidil. Minoxidil was confirmed as pharmaceutical grade through organoleptic evaluation, melting point (190 °C), FTIR analysis, moisture content (0.62%), and solubility studies, all of which complied with Pharmacopeial standards. Compatibility studies showed no interaction between MXD and selected excipients. UV analysis established 231 nm as the λ_{max} with excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.9998$). Oleic acid, Span 20, and PEG 600 were selected as formulation components, and an optimized microemulsion (50:37:13) was identified using ternary phase diagrams. Minoxidil was incorporated at 5% w/v. The optimized formulation showed good stability, appropriate viscosity (8.04 Pa·s), nanosized droplets (124 nm), narrow PDI (0.289), and a zeta potential of -23.9 mV. SEM confirmed spherical droplet morphology, while DSC indicated enhanced drug solubilization. In vitro release studies demonstrated sustained drug release (68.5% over 24 hours), following Higuchi diffusion kinetics ($R^2 = 0.8619$).

Keywords: Minoxidil, alopecia areata, microemulsion-based delivery system, ternary phase diagrams.

OP 2

The Role and Relevance of the Annals of Library and Information Studies in ALIS Research**Mrs. Vaishali Sambhaji Mulik¹ and Dr. Mohan Jamdade²**¹PhD scholar ²Ph. D. Guide

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Abstract: The Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS) is one of the oldest and most respected journals in the field of Library and Information Science (LIS) in India. Established to promote research and scholarly communication, it has served as a platform for disseminating innovative ideas, empirical studies, and theoretical advancements within the LIS community. The journal's evolution mirrors the growth of LIS as a discipline in the digital age. A descriptive and bibliometric approach was used, involving the analysis of articles published in ALIS over the past two decades. The study considered publication patterns, citation impact, authorship trends, and the thematic focus of research contributions. Data were obtained from the journal's online archives and bibliographic databases such as Scopus and Google Scholar. Findings reveal that ALIS has consistently published high-quality research on topics such as information literacy, library management, digital repositories, and bibliometrics. The journal demonstrates a growing international presence, with increased citations and contributions from global authors. Collaboration patterns show a steady rise in co-authored works, indicating stronger research networking within the LIS domain. The journal's sustained focus on both traditional and emerging LIS themes highlights its adaptability to changing scholarly needs. Its open-access policy and alignment with contemporary information science methodologies enhance its accessibility and global reach. The analysis confirms ALIS as a significant contributor to LIS education, research, and professional practice. Annals of Library and Information Studies remain a cornerstone of LIS scholarship, fostering intellectual growth and promoting evidence-based research. Its enduring relevance underscores the journal's pivotal role in bridging theory and practice within the field of library and information science.

Keywords: Annals of Library and Information Studies (ALIS), Library and Information Science (LIS), Bibliometrics analysis, Scholarly Communication, Research Trends, Academic Journals.

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OP 3**Reconfiguring India's Financial Landscape: The Transformative Impact of Green Bonds within Sustainable Finance****Dr. Sandeep Salunke****Assistant Professor****Department of Commerce, Government First Grade College, Hukkeri****Taluka – Hukkeri, Dist – Belagavi, Karnataka, Pin Code - 591309**

Abstract: India's economic transition to sustainability necessitates innovative financial systems that may bridge the gap between environmental objectives and economic prosperity. Green bonds have evolved as a significant tool in sustainable finance for funding renewable energy, low-carbon transportation, and environmentally friendly infrastructure projects. This study looks at the changing landscape of green bonds in India, specifically their role in enabling the country's transition to a low-carbon economy. The research assesses market knowledge, investor perception, and institutional readiness for green finance instruments using secondary data from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), SEBI, and the Climate Bonds Initiative (CBI), as well as a structured poll of 120 financial professionals.

Cronbach's alpha of 0.87 indicated the dataset's internal reliability. SPSS hypothesis testing demonstrated a significant positive correlation between green bond issuance and India's renewable energy capacity increase ($p < 0.05$). The findings reveal substantial investor interest, but also regulatory, reporting, and standardisation hurdles that prevent widespread use.

The study concludes that green bonds can become a key component of India's sustainable finance strategy if legislative incentives, transparency, and investor education are increased. Policy considerations include fiscal incentives for issuers, tax breaks for investors, and the integration of Indian green bond frameworks with global norms. Finally, this study emphasises that green bonds are more than just an environmental requirement; they are a strategic tool for India's inclusive and resilient economic change.

Key Words - Sustainable Finance, Green Bonds, Economic Transformation, Renewable Energy Investment, Institutional Readiness.

OP 4

Exploring the Dynamics of Workplace Flexibility and Work–Life Integration among Gen Z Professionals in Bengaluru’s IT Sector''**Shri Mahaveer Khawatakoppa****Assistant Professor****Department of Commerce, Government First Grade College Rabakavi-Banahatti-587315****Tq: Rabakavi-Banahatti, Dist: Bagalkot, State: Karnatka**

Abstract: The influence of flexible work arrangements on young employees’ ability to balance their work and personal lives in Bengaluru’s IT industry is the focus of this study. Additionally, it discusses the influence of workplace flexibility on job satisfaction and how trusts between employees and managers influence this relationship. Three hundred fifty IT professionals from various types of organizations, including startups, mid-range companies, and multinational corporations, participated in the research. The study's data collection was accomplished through a structured Google form, and the findings were analysed using advanced statistical methods. The study provides a strong predictive model of workplace flexibility, work-life integration, and job satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.71$). The findings support the theory that employees who manage their own schedules and work locations have greater success in achieving a healthy work/life balance, leading to increased job satisfaction and overall wellness. This increased balance in an employee’s life creates an enhancement of the positive effect flexible working has on job satisfaction when managers display trust towards their staff. Although trust increases job satisfaction from a flexible working arrangement, it does not significantly impact the ability of employees, primarily younger professionals, to achieve an effective work/life balance through self-control and adaptability. In conclusion, the findings support the use of flexible work arrangements in organizations that promote engagement and satisfaction of employees, as well as higher levels of productivity and engagement among employees within the organization. Flexible working arrangements should not only be viewed as a means of providing accommodation for an employee, but also as one of the main ways to enhance an employee's control, motivation, and sense of purpose in their job.

Keywords: Flexible work, work–life balance, job satisfaction, Gen Z, IT employees, Bengaluru.

OP 5

Shaping Customer Connections: AI's Role in Indian E-commerce Engagement

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Abstract: The Indian e-commerce scene is getting a major AI makeover, and it's changing how businesses connect with customers. This research dives into AI's role in shaping customer relationships in Indian e-commerce, focusing on personalization, chatbots, and predictive analytics. By talking to customers and industry experts, Researcher has uncovered AI's potential to boost satisfaction, retention, and overall experience. Our findings show AI can take customer connections to the next level, driving personalization and business growth. Study also reveals the challenges and opportunities for Indian e-commerce players to tap into AI-driven customer engagement strategies.

Keywords: Customer Engagement, AI in E-commerce, challenges and opportunities in adopting AI-driven customer engagement strategies.

OP 6

Impact of Flipped classrooms as a Teaching-Learning tool among the phase1 MBBS students

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Abstract: Flipped class is one such a kind that the goal is to shift the learning from being instructor-centered to student-centered. The flipped classroom may accommodate more interaction between teachers and students. Indeed, if such interaction leads to closer relationships between teachers and students, it may improve students' academic achievement and persistence. So flipped classrooms can replace some of the traditional didactic lectures to overcome the disadvantages of the traditional didactic lecture.

OP 7

IoT-Enabled Bioelectronics: Towards Intelligent Healthcare**Mr. Bhise Shailesh Shivajirao¹ and Mrs. Aswale Vrushali Abhishek²****¹Head of Department Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering
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Education Society's Polytechnic, Sangli)**

Abstract: The combination of bioelectronics and IoT technologies is catalysing a paradigm shift in modern health care as they allow for ongoing, remote, and customized physiological patient monitoring. IoT-enabled bioelectronic platforms provide an avenue for health care to transition from reactive treatment to proactive and preventive care. Herein, we present a new bioelectronic sensing platform that consumes minimal power and incorporates low-latency IoT connectivity for health monitoring in real-time or over the long term. We propose a multimodal physiological monitoring solution that enables the capture of multiple types of physiological data such as biopotentials and vital signs. The proposed architecture utilizes state-of-the-art, low-power analog circuitry for precise data acquisition and signal condition regardless of equipment configuration. Additionally, the use of algorithms for extracting clinically relevant data at the point of observation minimizes both redundancy and the amount of data transmitted to the cloud or share with clinicians. The system architecture is designed to conserve energy through the use of low-power circuits, adaptive duty cycling, and optimized wireless communication protocols. The system architecture has been specially designed to support applications such as wearable and implantable healthcare devices. The system architecture also uses encryption, authentication, and cloud access control to secure the data transferred from the device to the recipient. The data transferred to the provider and/or caretaker will be securely stored in the cloud, and may be accessed anytime from anywhere by the appropriate authorized party. Additionally, experimental evaluations demonstrated improved signal fidelity, reduced energy consumption, and an increased level of reliability for the operation of the platform compared to traditional wearable monitoring platforms. The evaluation also showed that the platform could be used for extended device lifetime and sustains continuous monitoring of the patient in prolonged monitoring scenarios. In summary, the proposed Internet of Things (IoT) enabled bioelectronic platform has an excellent potential to be scaled to support smart healthcare ecosystems. By allowing for the

ability to perform real-time data collection, remote monitoring, and predictive analytics, this platform will provide patient-centred care, early detection of anomalies, and improved clinical decision-making. The results of this study indicate that by integrating cloud computation, artificial intelligence, and bioelectronics will allow us to develop next-generation, smart healthcare solutions for chronic disease management, elder care, and remote health updates. As an added benefit, the integration of IoT and bioelectronics will also provide support for interoperability, regulatory compliance, and future applications with artificial intelligence capabilities to gain population-level data, create and sustain a digital healthcare transformation within the clinical settings and resourceconstrained environments around the world.

Keywords: Bioelectronics, Internet of Things, Smart Healthcare, Wearable Sensors, LowPower Systems, Remote Health Monitoring, Predictive Healthcare

OP 8

Inflammation Integrated Triglyceride Glucose Index: A Novel Index to identify Insulin Resistance among Metabolic Syndrome patients – A Case Control Study**Deepak Rajan DS^{1*}, Sabarinathan M² and Ananthi N³**¹Tutor, Biochemistry, Saveetha Medical College, SIMATS Chennai – 602105²Assistant professor, Department of Biochemistry, St. Peter's Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Hosur – 635109³Professor & Head, Biochemistry, Saveetha Medical College, SIMATS, Chennai – 602105

Abstract: Metabolic Syndrome (MetS) is a cluster of cardiometabolic risk factors including central obesity, increased fasting glucose, high blood pressure, and dyslipidemia. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome has risen sharply in recent decades. The development of MetS involves a combination of genetic and acquired factors, all linked to insulin resistance and persistent low-level inflammation. Inflammation Integrated Triglyceride Glucose Index (IITG) is novel index developed by combining hsCRP and TyG index. It is a case control study comprised of 150 cases and 150 controls. Cases include patients diagnosed with Mets as per NCEP ATP III guidelines. Controls include apparently healthy individuals. IITG was calculated by the formula $IITG = 0.391 * \ln(\text{hsCRP}) + \text{TyG}$. Pearson correlation and Receiving Operating Curve (ROC) analyses were performed. IITG is higher in metabolic syndrome patients (10.02 ± 0.75) when compared with controls (8.51 ± 0.35) with a p value of < 0.0001 . IITG showed a significant positive correlation with other insulin resistance indices and components of metabolic syndrome. ROC shows the highest area under the curve for IITG (0.954) with an optimal cut-off point of 9.04 at 89% sensitivity, 94% specificity with the Youden index of 0.8333. Inflammation Integrated Triglyceride Glucose Index (IITG) is a novel composite index by integrating lipid and glycemic markers, systemic inflammation emerges as a key pathophysiological factor in the development of insulin resistance. So, IITG can be used as a novel, effective and valuable marker in identifying metabolic syndrome patients.

Keywords: IITG, Insulin Resistance, Metabolic Syndrome.

OP 9

Carbon Pricing, Economic Efficiency and Behavioural Responses: A Multidisciplinary Perspective on Climate Policy Effectiveness in India**Dr. Rita Rani**

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Abstract: Climate change presents a critical challenge for developing economies striving to achieve sustainable growth while meeting rising energy demands. India, as one of the world's largest emerging carbon dioxide emitters, faces the dual imperatives of economic development and climate mitigation. Market-based instruments such as carbon pricing are widely recognized for their potential to internalize environmental externalities and improve economic efficiency; however, their effectiveness in developing countries, particularly through behavioural channels, remains unexplored.

This study examines the role of carbon pricing in enhancing economic efficiency and influencing behavioural responses in India from a multidisciplinary perspective, integrating economic analysis with insights from behavioural science and environmental policy. In the absence of an explicit carbon tax or emissions trading system, India relies on implicit carbon pricing mechanisms, including fuel excise duties and the coal cess. Using panel data econometric techniques and behavioural demand modelling, the paper assesses the impact of energy price signals on carbon emissions, energy consumption patterns, and welfare outcomes across income groups and economic sectors.

The study is closely aligned with **Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 13 (Climate Action)** by evaluating the effectiveness of fiscal instruments in reducing emissions, **SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy)** through its focus on energy consumption behaviour, and **SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production)** by analysing demand-side responses to price incentives. Additionally, distributional implications are examined in relation to **SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities)**.

The findings indicate that higher energy prices can improve economic efficiency by discouraging carbon-intensive consumption; however, behavioural responses are heterogeneous, with low-

income households exhibiting greater price sensitivity but facing higher welfare burdens. The paper highlights the importance of revenue recycling and complementary policy measures to enhance equity, public acceptance, and overall policy effectiveness. By providing empirical evidence from India, this study contributes to the global discourse on designing efficient, equitable, and behaviourally informed carbon pricing frameworks for sustainable development in emerging economies.

Keywords: Carbon pricing; Economic efficiency; Behavioural responses; Sustainable Development Goals; Climate policy

OP 10

Insilico Molecular docking and Simulation Studies of Thymoquinone (TQ) against Nfa1 protein for treatment of Primary Amoebic Meningoencephalitis (PAM)**Nirmala Subramanian¹****¹Department of Biochemistry, St. Ann's College for Women
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Abstract: Insilico molecular docking has revolutionized the world for various drug discovery process. The recent threat to world, the Primary Amoebic Meningoencephalitis (PAM), caused by *Naegleria fowleri*, a 'brain-eating amoeba', though being rare, has proved to be more fatal especially to the Indian Population since 2024. It has made a sudden alarming and an emergency threat with 153 confirmed infections and 20 deaths towards the end of 2025, especially to an Indian state like Kerala alone. Though various multi-level drugs are prescribed for PAM treatment, there is no reliable, effective and standardised protocol for treatment of PAM. Thus, we have utilized the various pharmacoinformatic techniques to analyse the phytochemical properties of Thymoquinone (TQ), a component of black cumin seeds to be treated against Nfa1 protein, causing PAM. Success stories of TQ being a potential barrier against various inflammations and damage of neural cells has paved way for our research of TQ against Nfa1 protein. Molecular Docking was performed with our prescribed TQ against Nfa1 protein, while parallelly, running docking using the drugs, like Amphotericin B, Miltefosine, Azithromycin, Fluconazole, and Rifampin, which are used to treat PAM as control samples, for a comparative study. The Nfa1 protein sequence was retrieved from Uniport database, followed by structure prediction by Swiss model. Other primary and secondary analysis was carried out using Protparam and PSIPred tools. The chemical structure of all drugs and TQ were obtained from PubChem. Molecular docking analysis were carried out using Autodock followed by the molecular simulations analysis. We were able to find that TQ from black seeds seems to score better results than the prescribed drugs, from our study. Henceforth, our findings suggest that TQ has the potential to be served as an alternative and effective medicine for treating PAM. However, we propose experimental validation is essential to confirm our findings.

Keywords: Thymoquinone, Nfa1 protein, Primary Amoebic Meningoencephalitis, Molecular Docking, Molecular Dynamics.

OP 11**Role of AI in Growth of Online Business****Ms. Mohini Gupta****Assistant Professor****Lucknow Public College of Professional Studies, Lucknow**

Abstract: The rapid evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed the online business landscape enabling companies to optimize operations enhance customer experiences and drive growth. This paper explores the multifaceted role of AI in the growth of online businesses highlighting its applications benefits and challenges.

AI-powered technologies such as machine learning natural language processing and computer vision are being increasingly adopted by online businesses to improve decision-making automate processes and personalize customer interactions. AI-driven analytics enable businesses to gain valuable insights into consumer behaviour preferences and trends facilitating data-driven decision-making and targeted marketing strategies.

The integration of AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants has revolutionized customer service providing 24/7 support and enhancing user experiences. Additionally AI-driven recommendation systems and predictive analytics are helping online businesses optimize product offerings pricing and supply chain management.

Despite the benefits AI adoption in online business also raises concerns around data privacy security and job displacement. This paper discusses the opportunities and challenges associated with AI adoption in online business and provides insights into future research directions.

The findings of this study suggest that AI has the potential to be a game-changer for online businesses enabling them to gain a competitive edge improve efficiency and drive growth. However, it is crucial for businesses to address the associated challenges and ensure responsible AI adoption.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Online Business Machine Learning Customer Experience Decision-Making Growth.

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OP 12

Micro Mastery Iterative Learning Model (MMILM) for Effective Online Education**Mr. Bharat Suryawanshi¹ and Dr. Sachin Ayarekar²**¹Assistant Registrar, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University),
Center for Distance and Online Education, Pune-411030²Assistant Professor, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University),
Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Pune-411038

Abstract: Online education is growing day by day and creating a tremendous impact on education ecosystem. Rapid evolution of digital infrastructure, increased access and emerging technologies has expanded the scope for innovative strategies to enhance online learning outcomes. Despite the availability of advanced technologies, supporting skill-based learning in online environments remains challenging. Ensuring smooth execution and effective learning outcomes through self-paced online education is difficult to measure and analyse for the teaching fraternity. Moreover, despite numerous digital initiatives, student assessment, quality assurance, and student engagement continue to be critical challenges that require focused attention. To address these issues, assessment can be implemented through iterative mastery learning techniques using innovative, engaging, and exploratory strategies. The research work proposes Micro Mastery Iterative Learning Model (MMILM) to provide engaging assessment practices that lead to improved online learning outcomes. The transition of micro learning mechanisms towards mastery-based learning is presented as an innovative strategy to enhance depth of understanding and fine-tune learners' conceptual clarity, thereby ensuring the achievement of learning outcomes. Comprehensive strategies such as MMILM are essential for addressing existing challenges and for creating a more inclusive, effective and outcome-oriented online educational environment.

Keywords: Mastery Learning, Online Education, Student Engagement, Student Assessment.

OP 13

Importance of Taxonomy in the Management of Invasive Plant Species**Dr. Sonia Saini****Department of Botany****Isabella Thoburn College, Lucknow**

Abstract: The International union of conservation of nature and natural Resources (IUCN) defines “alien invasive species” as an alien species which become established in natural or semi natural ecosystem or habitat as agent of change and threats’ us native biological. diversity. Invasive plant species are one of the major drivers of biodiversity loss, ecosystem degradation, and economic damage across the globe. Effective management of invasive plants depends largely on accurate identification, classification, and understanding of their biological and ecological characteristics. Plant taxonomy provides the scientific framework for identifying invasive species, distinguishing them from native flora, and understanding their evolutionary relationships. This paper highlights the importance of taxonomy in the management of invasive plant species, emphasizing its role in early detection, risk assessment, biological control, policy formulation, and long-term ecosystem. The integration of classical morphological taxonomy with modern molecular tools is discussed as a comprehensive approach to improving invasive species management and biodiversity conservation.

Keywords: Plant taxonomy, invasive species, biodiversity, biological control, ecosystem management.

OP 14

Adolescents' Preferences and Perceptions towards Ayurvedic Medicines: A Mixed-Methods Study from Pimpri-Chinchwad, Pune, India**Kiran Rao¹ and Dr. Pratap Desai²**¹**Research Scholar, IMRDA Sangli, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune, India**²**Associate Professor and Vice Principal, Department: Management Studies, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) IMRDA Sangli, India**

Abstract: Ayurvedic medicine continues to be an integral part of India's traditional healthcare system; however, limited empirical evidence exists regarding adolescents' perceptions and preferences toward Ayurveda. Adolescence is a critical developmental phase during which health beliefs and treatment decisions are influenced by family practices, cultural values, education, and exposure to modern healthcare systems (WHO, 2022). This study examines adolescents' awareness, perceptions, utilization patterns, and factors influencing their preference for Ayurvedic medicines.

A mixed-method, cross-sectional approach was implemented among 300 adolescents aged 13–19 years from selected schools and community settings in Pimpri-Chinchwad, Pune. Structured questionnaires generated quantitative data, complemented by semi-structured interviews providing contextual insights. Descriptive statistics and chi-square analyses were employed for quantitative evaluation.

Most respondents demonstrated familiarity with Ayurveda and reported previous use, particularly for self-limiting ailments. Perceptions were moderated by beliefs about natural composition, safety, accessibility, and affordability, with household practices exerting prominent influence. A statistically significant association was identified between family use and adolescent preference for Ayurvedic treatment ($p < .001$), underscoring the intergenerational continuity of traditional health practices.

Keywords: Ayurveda; adolescent health; traditional medicine; awareness; family influence; complementary medicine

OP 15

An Ai-Based Framework for Defect Detection in PCB Substrate Using Numerically Simulated Contour Images**M. Rajalakshmi^{1*} and Kavitha R. J²**¹**Electronics and Communication Engineering, Trichy engineering college, Konalai, Tiruchirappalli, 621 132, Tamil Nadu, India**²**Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, University College of Engineering Panruti, 607106, Tamil Nadu, India**

Abstract: It is essential for ensuring the reliability of printed circuit boards (PCBs) using automated defect detection in electronic manufacturing. In modern manufacturing industries, the quality inspection is a critical step, where the surface defects directly affect the customer satisfaction, product reliability and safety. The limitations, such as human fatigue, low consistency, and sensitivity to illumination and noise variations, hinder the conventional manual inspection and traditional image processing techniques. The artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning-based image processing techniques have served as a significant solution for automated industries in the past few years. In this work, an AI-based image processing framework for the auto detection of PCB defects using ANSYS-generated images is presented. To represent the defect-prone zones, the stress and deformation image contours of a PCB are developed using ANSYS Workbench. These images are treated as the defect data, and they are analyzed using the transfer learning approach of the convolutional neural network (CNN). The proposed method combines simulation-based image generation and AI-based image processing effectively, and the results suggest the feasibility of the proposed framework for automated inspection of the PCB.

Keywords: PCB, Numerical analysis, Image processing, Defect detection, CNN.

OP 16

Substance use Pattern among Women in Rural North India: A Chart Review**Dr. Sunila Rathee¹ and Dr. Jagriti Yadav²**¹Professor, Institute of Mental Health, Pt. B.D. Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak;²Assistant Professor, Pandit Neki Ram Sharma Government Medical College, Bhiwani)

Introduction: Substance use among women in rural India remains an underexplored public health issue due to social stigma, underreporting, and limited research focus. Understanding patterns of substance use among women is essential for developing gender-sensitive prevention and intervention strategies.. This study aimed to assess the profile of rural women with substance use disorder attending a tertiary care centre over a ten-year period.

Methodology: The present retrospective chart review study was conducted at the State Drug Dependence Treatment Centre (SDDTC), Institute of Mental Health, Pt. B.D. Sharma University of Health Sciences, Rohtak, Haryana. Case records of female patients from January 2015 to December 2024 were reviewed. A total of 196 women sought consultation, with 107 were from rural area.

Results: The majority of women were aged between 26 and 35 years, with a mean age of 35. The commonest substance of abuse was tobacco 48(44.8%), followed by opioids 31(28.9 %), alcohol 12(11.2%), multiple substance 10(9.3%) and benzodiazepines 6(5.6%). With co-morbid psychiatric illness were (11.68%), family history of substance abuse (33%).

Conclusion: Smoking was common among female patients and surprising to note that other substance like alcohol, opioids and benzodiazepines were also started showing their presence in females in rural areas. It is, therefore important to evolve alternate strategies to identify women with problems related to drug abuse in order to understand its impact both from the individual as well as from the gender perspective.

Keywords: Opioid misuse; Women; Rural; Substance use disorder.

OP 17

Effect of growth regulators on callus induction and somatic embryogenesis in *Gloriosa superba* L.**Ritu Mahajan, Pallavi Billowria, Shajaat Hussain****School of Biotechnology, University of Jammu, Jammu (J&K), India**

Gloriosa superba L. is an important medicinal plant, listed in Red data book and has been affirmed as endangered plant. It is highly valued for an alkaloid colchicine which has important role in anti-inflammation and plant breeding. Poor seed germination and only two daughter tubers restricts its multiplication and hence the germplasm available is very less. So, there is need to standardize a protocol for its multiplication. MS medium containing 2.0 mg/l BAP, 0.5mg/l Kn and 1.0 mg/l GA₃ resulted in 88.67% of *in vitro* shoots, while 1.5 mg/l BAP resulted in 80.21% shoots. The highest number of average number of shoots per explant was 8.7±0.18. MS medium resulted in 84.50% of healthy roots with an average of 7.47±0.29 roots per explant when supplemented with 2.0 mg/l IBA while creamish white and embryogenic callus was observed with MS medium containing 3.0 mg/l 2,4-D. Sub-culturing of callus on MS medium supplemented with BAP, Kn and IBA resulted in *in vitro* shoot and root formation while on MS medium containing 2,4-D, BAP and Kn resulted in globular structures and heart shaped somatic embryos. The developed protocol is useful for mass multiplication of *Gloriosa* and *in vitro* secondary metabolite production.

Keywords: *Gloriosa superba*, callus, colchicine, somatic embryos

OP 18

Patterns and Determinants of Out-of-Pocket Health Care Payments and Financing Strategies among Urban Households in West Bengal**Sujoy Kumar Majumdar****Assistant Professor****Department of Economics****Raiganj University, P.O.Raiganj, Uttar Dinajpur, West Bengal. PIN-733134**

Abstract: This paper analyses the pattern of household level health expenditure for the treatment of acute morbidity and hospitalisation during the reference period especially among the urban poor in West Bengal state of India. The analysis is based on primary household survey data collected from 282 slum households during the period from May to July 2010, covering approximately 1,600 individuals from slum settlements in three urban centres of West Bengal. Summary statistics, cross tabulation and regressions techniques are used for data analysis. It is found that due to the lack of government primary health care facilities, slums dwellers especially those are BPL families have to incur higher medical expenditure ratio for accessing outdoor and inpatient hospital care. Consequently, the slums dwellers often depend on illegal medical practitioners for treatment of acute and chronic morbidity. An econometric analysis also indicate that the households having good drainage facility, good environment is less likely to bear health care burden compared to those who are living in unhygienic environment. Similarly poor are paying higher health expenditure compared to rich in term of ratio of health expenditure in total household monthly consumption expenditure. The findings also reveal that limited access to affordable primary care increases the risk of catastrophic health expenditure among the urban poor, compelling them to adopt coping strategies such as borrowing from banks, friends, and relatives. As a result, many households are pushed into a cycle of indebtedness and often have to compromise on children's education and essential household goods in select urban slum settlements of West Bengal.

Keywords: Health care payment, Economic burden, coping strategies, Slums, Urban poor, Morbidity.

OP 19**The Fragility of endodontically treated tooth: Between strength and survival****Dr. Pooja Kabra (Professor)****Department of Conservative dentistry and endodontics,
S.D.S, Sharda University, Greater Noida**

Abstract: Endodontically treated teeth presents a unique challenge due to significant loss of natural tooth structure, altered biomechanics thereby increased susceptibility to fracture of the tooth. Endodontic treatment addresses to infection of pulp tissue of the tooth but does not aim to restore the tooth function, strength and esthetics. Therefore success relies on quality and design of post endodontic treatment. In the recent times, the advances in adhesive materials ,posts material and restorative techniques have definitely brought a difference in rendering the desired treatment but still high failures occur due to compromised restorative planning, material selection, occlusal forces and periodontal conditions for proper rehabilitation of endodontically treated tooth. This explores the multifactorial challenges involved in post endodontic restoration providing deeper understanding of the subject. This paper would highlight on the reasons of failure and evidenced based strategies to enhance the treatment success of post endodontic restorations.

Keywords: post endodontic treatment, challenges, strategies.

OP 20

Synthesis of polyhydroxypyrrolidines and formal synthesis of ent-pyloricidin D

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Abstract: Polyhydroxy pyrrolidines form the core structural framework of numerous natural products, including DMDP, ADMDP, hyacinthacines, bulgecinine, and swainsonine (Figure 1). These compounds, along with hydroxy indolizidines, exhibit significant biological properties, such as glycosidase inhibition, anticancer, and antibacterial activities. In this study, we present the synthesis of diverse polyhydroxy pyrrolidines and the formal synthesis of pyloricidins. The methodology involves a proline-catalyzed α -aminooxylation reaction on higher homologues of Graner's aldehyde, offering a straightforward and efficient synthetic route to these biologically active molecules.

Figure 1: Polyhydroxy pyrrolidines and Pyloricidin D

OP 21

Enantiospecific Synthesis of (–)-Cuspareine and (–)-Galipinine

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Abstract: An enantiospecific route to the synthesis of tetrahydroquinoline alkaloids (–)-cuspareine and (–)-galipinine is reported. Coupling of an iodide derivative of D-serine with aromatic dithianes and Pd-catalyzed intramolecular C–N coupling are the key steps in the synthesis

Figure 1: (–)-Cuspareine and (–)-Galipinine

OP 22

Artificial Intelligence: A Computational Catalyst optimizing the frameworks of Sustainable Development**Mr. Ayushman Panda¹, Dr. Dhyanadipta Panda² and Mrs. Chandralekha Rath³**¹Student, Christ Deemed to be University, B.Tech- CSE (AI &ML)²Associate Professor, KIIT Deemed to be University, School of Liberal Studies³Faculty, KIIT International School, IBDP Comp. Science

Abstract: Since the oncoming of digitalization, advanced technologies like Artificial Intelligence took over the pinnacle of development and globalization into a completely new aspect. Advanced machineries, AI-powered tools and digital systems became some of the vital connoisseurs of organizational and developmental frameworks. At the current pace, technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) play a pivotal role in our every-day life (both professional and personal) and have put light on quite new evolutionary ideas and directions.

With enhanced developmental pace came the surging need for sustainability. Deteriorating and limited resources, degrading environmental conditions and climate changes gave rise to ideas of sustainable development. Although Artificial Intelligence and Sustainability contract each other in many theoretical aspects, but over the recent years have shown immense compatibility. In this paper, we would emphasize on how the integration of AI and sustainability did not only fasten up the measures to satisfy the sustainable development goals (SDG's), but also put light on advanced and suitable methods to keep check on regulatory policies and strategies. Apart from detailed analysis and data filtering, Artificial intelligence has the potential to predict economic trends, assist world-wide healthcare systems with significant contribution in diagnosis and even assist with financial analysis and developmental initiatives. In educational field, digital teaching methods, personalized training and learning experiences have already marked the integration of Artificial Intelligence-infused sustainable development.

In a nutshell, Artificial Intelligence-empowered sustainable development has the potential to revamp the developmental frameworks with the risk of fewer setbacks. AI is essentially not only a technological innovation, but a revolutionary power globally. This paper would also discuss about the challenges and future aspects AI and sustainable ideas, for long-term development that also aligns with the idea of sustainability.

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Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Sustainable Development; Digitalization; Sustainability; Globalization.

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OP 23
Holistic Sustainable Development through Multi-Disciplinary Strategies
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Abstract: Holistic sustainable development focuses on combining economic growth, social fairness, and environmental protection to ensure long-term well-being for both current and future generations. This approach recognizes that sustainability challenges are complex and connected. They require strategies that go beyond traditional sector boundaries. By bringing together insights from economics, environmental science, social sciences, technology, governance, and cultural studies, holistic development frameworks create more inclusive, resilient, and flexible solutions. Multi-disciplinary strategies encourage innovation through collaboration, allowing policymakers, researchers, industry leaders, and communities to work together on specific interventions. These strategies help manage resources efficiently, build climate resilience, reduce poverty, improve public health, and ensure fair access to opportunities. Additionally, including indigenous knowledge, local practices, and modern technologies increases social participation and accountability in development processes. Holistic sustainable development also encourages a systems approach, prompting stakeholders to focus on long-term outcomes instead of short-term benefits. In a time defined by climate change, rapid urbanization, and socio-economic disparities, multi-disciplinary approaches are crucial for balancing competing priorities and managing trade-offs effectively. This overview highlights the need for coordinated action, partnerships across sectors, and evidence-based policymaking to achieve sustainable development goals. Ultimately, holistic and multi-disciplinary strategies offer a clear path to sustainable progress, ensuring that development is environmentally responsible, socially fair, and economically sound.

Keywords: Holistic development, Sustainable development, Multi-disciplinary strategies, Systems thinking, Environmental sustainability, Social equity, Economic growth, Cross-sectoral collaboration, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

OP 24

Environmental Literacy and Sustainable Living Practices among Adolescents in Bihar's High Schools: A Review Study**Kritika*, Dr. Rajni Pandey¹*****Ph.D. Scholar, Patna University, Patna-800001****¹Senior Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Home Science
Patna University, Patna-800001**

Abstract: Environmental literacy plays a vital role in shaping sustainable behaviours among adolescents, who represent a critical group for long-term environmental stewardship. This review study synthesises existing research on environmental awareness, attitudes, and sustainable living practices among high school students in Bihar, India. The analysis focuses on educational influences, school-based initiatives, and socio-economic factors that affect students' engagement with environmental issues. Findings from reviewed studies indicate that while students possess basic knowledge of environmental concepts, the consistent adoption of sustainable practices remains limited. Experiential learning, teacher involvement, and community-oriented programs were found to significantly enhance both awareness and responsible behaviour. However, disparities related to school resources and socio-economic conditions continue to influence outcomes. The review highlights the need for curriculum integration, practical learning approaches, and collaborative community efforts to strengthen environmental education at the secondary school level. These insights offer valuable implications for educators, policymakers, and institutions seeking to promote sustainable development through education.

Keywords: Environmental literacy, Sustainable practices, Adolescents, Secondary education, Environmental education, Sustainable development, Bihar

OP 25

Investigating the Impact of Perception on Job Satisfaction among Dental Care Providers in Delhi NCR**Amit Prakash Sharma¹ and Dr. Rohini Ruhil (Guide)²****Amity Institute of Public Health & Hospital Administration, J-1 Block, Amity University, Noida, Uttar Pradesh 201313****Abstract**

Aim: This research paper seeks to review the major organizational and professional factors that determine job satisfaction among dental professionals within the Delhi-NCR area. It concentrates on measures like the organizational setting, work burden and job definition, doctor/patient relationship and communication and access to facilities and staffing.

Methodology: Structured questionnaire was used as a quantitative design of the research. The information was gathered among 390 dental practitioners in Delhi, Noida, Gurugram, Ghaziabad, and Faridabad. Purposive sample methods were used to identify the respondents and the reliability and normality of the instrument was established.

Statistical Methods: The correlational analysis, descriptive statistics, Cronbach Alpha reliability analysis, Shapiro Wilk test of Normality, and linear regression analysis of multiple linear regressions were used in analyzing how independent variables impacted on the job satisfaction.

Results: The results elucidated that organizational environment, workload and role clarity, and resources and infrastructure play a major positive role in providing job satisfaction. But the interaction and communication with patients were lower predictive efficacy. The reg model accounted about 59 percent variance of job satisfaction.

Originality/Value: The research will address a very big gap on the Indian setting since the study targets the dental professionals themselves and includes the organizational and infrastructural variables to a model that will be used to predict this. It also gives comparative information in various urban areas in Delhi-NCR.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, dental professionals, organizational environment, workload, infrastructure, Delhi-NCR, regression analysis.

OP 26

Implementing Outcome-Based Education (OBE) in Management Curricula: A Strategic Framework for Competency-Based Assessment**Ms. Beki Sunil¹ and Dr. Sucheta Kanchi²**¹**Research Scholar, Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune**²**Assistant Professor, Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune**

Abstract: India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 establishes a critical imperative for higher education to transition from traditional rote learning to a competency-driven model. In the context of business schools, this reform demands a strategic pivot from merely tracking "outputs," such as syllabus completion, to validating "outcomes," defined as demonstrable managerial proficiency. This research articulates a comprehensive framework for operationalizing Outcome-Based Education (OBE) within management curricula. Drawing on an exploratory analysis of assessment protocols at premier institutions including IIMs and AACSB-accredited schools the study proposes a structured "Assurance of Learning" (AoL) model. Furthermore, it introduces practical assessment rubrics tailored for abstract competencies like critical thinking and leadership, offering institutions a blueprint to verify skill acquisition beyond standard course grades.

Keywords: Outcome-Based Education (OBE), NEP 2020, Assurance of Learning (AoL), Competency-Based Assessment, Management Education.

OP 27

Preparation of compost from Lignocellulosic waste and its effect on soil properties compared with urea and compost prepared from domestic waste**Laxmi, Brijesh Shivhare****Research scholar Botany, Baba Mastnath University, Rohtak, 124021****Assistant professor Botany, Baba Mastnath University, Rohtak, 124021**

Abstract: The reliance on chemical fertilizers and amount of agricultural waste produced worldwide has been rapidly rising in recent years. The production of large amounts of lignocellulose-containing wastes, such as crop residue, garbage, bagasse, dried leaves, etc., poses a serious environmental contamination risk and soil health challenges because people usually burn this residue. In future negative impacts may cause global climate changes due to high air pollution, depletion of soil nutrients, low agriculture productivity, increment in respiratory problems and many more. Composting provide a very useful and cost effective alternative to manage this waste. Compost is a decayed organic matter that can be utilized to assist in development of plants and maintain soil healthy. The main objectives of this research are to prepare compost of different composition i.e. one from lignocellulosic waste like crop residue and another from dung and domestic waste and evaluate its effect on soil properties in comparison with urea. A soil application experiment was conducted using different treatments, including lignocellulosic waste compost, domestic waste compost, urea, and an untreated control. In our study we compared the carbon content, pH, electrical conductivity and nutrient profile of soil pre and post application of both composts and urea.

The results indicated that application of lignocellulosic waste compost significantly enhanced soil organic carbon content and nutrient availability compared to urea-treated soils. When compared with domestic waste compost, lignocellulosic waste compost showed superior performance in improving soil fertility, with the added advantage of lower contamination risk and greater stability. The study also highlighted reduced nutrient losses in soils amended with lignocellulosic waste compost.

Keywords: soil properties, composting, Lignocellulosic waste, sustainable agriculture, soil fertility management.

OP 28

A Study to review an interdisciplinary research approach of Ayurvedic Rasayana therapy & genomic insights for health care interventions**Dr. Ashvini Kamble¹ and Dr. Madhuri Pachghare²**¹Associate professor

Department of Samhita Siddhanta Evam Sanskritam,

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R.A Podar Ayurved Medical College, Waroli, Mumbai

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Abstract

Introduction: Ayurvedic Rasayana therapies aim to promote longevity and vitality. This paper explores their intersection with genomic science, focusing on how Rasayanas modulate gene expression, stress responses, and cellular repair. We review literature, highlight potential synergies, and suggest future directions for integrative health approaches.

Keywords: Rasayana, genomics, Ayurveda, rejuvenation, gene expression

Introduction: Rasayana therapies in Ayurveda target rejuvenation at cellular and systemic levels. Genomic tools can decode their mechanisms, revealing pathways like antioxidant defense, DNA repair, and longevity genes.

Aim: To Study of interdisciplinary approach of Ayurvedic Rasayana therapy & Genomic insights for health care interventions.

Objective

1. Study genomic targets of key Rasayanas
2. Explore applications in longevity and disease prevention.

Materials and Methods-

- Literature review of Rasayana herbs and genomic studies.

Abstract Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approaches for Sustainable Development (ICMASD-26)

- Analysis of gene modulation pathways.

Observation: Rasayanas align with genomic pathways tied to aging, stress resilience, and cellular health.

Discussion: Integrating Rasayana with genomics could personalize rejuvenation therapies, pending further mechanistic studies.

Conclusion: This multidisciplinary approach holds promise for optimizing health span.

OP 29

**Drug Repurposing and co-adjuvant therapy for cancer care
Deepmala Kumari* and Brahm Kumar Tiwari****Department of MLT & Biochemistry, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, SGT University,
Gurugram 122505 (Haryana)**

Abstract: β -AR antagonists, non-selective β -Blockers are having substantial evidence for use against various cancers. Inhibition of β adrenergic signaling can result in inhibition of tumor growth. β -AR antagonists are an economical drug repurposing candidate for cancer beyond its traditional use in cardiovascular conditions. Whereas increased oxidative stress is the main feature of cancer cells and under the study of antioxidant therapeutic strategy in cancer, naturally safe; Ascorbic acid is widely studied against variety of cancers. Current study aims to investigate the effect of combination drug formulation- β -AR antagonist and Ascorbic acid tablet on Human lung carcinoma NCI-H1299 cell lines to provide evidence for further studies and clinical trials. MTT assay was performed to assess cell viability of H1299 cell lines at different concentrations of combination drug formulation, β -AR antagonist (alone) and ascorbic acid (alone). Absorbance and cell viability measured at 24hr, 48hr and 72hrs. Cell viability of H1299 decreased noticeably for combination drug formulation of β -AR antagonist and Ascorbic Acid tablets as compared to β -AR antagonist (alone) and Ascorbic acid (alone). At 1000 μ g/ml combination drug formulation concentration, cell viability was observed 6.67 % against the initial concentration of 62.50 μ g/ml cell viability 8.33 % in 72 hrs time point of study. Cell viability at 1000.00 μ g/ml concentration of β -AR antagonist (alone) was observed 15% and Ascorbic acid (alone) was observed 19% respectively. Calculated IC50 for β -AR antagonist and Ascorbic Acid tablets is significantly observed lower as compared to β -AR antagonist (alone) IC50: 213.56 μ g/ml and Ascorbic acid (alone) IC50: 230.05 μ g/ml. The combination drug formulation of β -AR antagonist and Ascorbic acid tablets considerably reduced cell viability. The present study and observation has revealed future confidence for study of "Repurposing of β AR antagonist + Ascorbic Acid Tablets as anti-cancer agents and co-adjuvant therapy for Cancer treatment" and potentially offer a viable, affordable, and useful cancer treatment option with lower side effects and a lower toxicity profile than conventional chemotherapy.

Key words: Drug Repurposing, Anti-cancer, β -AR antagonist, cell

OP 30

Evaluation of Diagnostic Performance of Amylase and Lipase in Pre-Operative Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma**Bhagwat Kale¹, Sunita Girish², Anjali Waghmode³, Somnath Salgar⁴, Sanjay Gaikwad⁵, Bhagyashree Yadav⁶**¹Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College and Cancer Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra.²D.Y.Patil Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Pune, Maharashtra.^{3,4}Department of Biochemistry, B.J. Government Medical College and Sassoon General Hospital, Pune, Maharashtra.⁵Department of Biochemistry, Smt. Sakhubai Narayanrao Katkade Medical College and Research Center, Kopergaon, Ahilyanagar, Maharashtra.⁶Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College and Hospital, Alibag, Maharashtra.**Abstract:**

Background: CEA and CA 19.9 are most common markers used in clinical practice in management of PDAC. Preoperative serum CA19-9 and CEA level are closely related with survival time in PDAC patients and therefore may be used for evaluating the prognosis of PDAC. Now, the question posed in this study was, “Whether the pancreatic enzymes lipase and amylase add significance towards increasing diagnostic and prognostic efficacy of PDAC furthermore ? ”. Thus, this study is planned to explore whether measured amylase and lipase can lead to statistically significant improvement in the diagnostic and prognostic efficacy of PDAC.

Methods: The study includes 50 clinically diagnosed and confirmed cases of PDAC. 50 age and sex matched healthy volunteers were selected and used for comparison of result. ROC analysis of CA-19.9 and CEA was the major statistical analysis to find cut-off. Sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, PPV and NPV of CEA, CA19.9, amylase and lipase were calculated in PDAC to know their diagnostic and prognostic efficacy.

Results: Increased serum lipase and amylase with increased LAR indicates pancreatic duct blockage while decreased serum lipase and serum amylase with increased or decreased LAR may hint for pancreatic insufficiency.

Conclusions: Preoperative amylase and lipase levels and the calculation of the LAR at the time of localized pancreatic cancer diagnosis might be helpful in the risk assessment in surgically resectable pancreatic cancer.

References:

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OP 31

Comparative Study of Performance of Plagiarism Detection Tools**Janhavi Pednekar¹ and Dr. H. M. Padalikar²****¹Research Scholar, Bharati Vidyapeeth, Pune-411030****²Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Pune-411038**

Abstract: With the advancements in Information Technology sector, there is rise in the availability of digital contents from various domains. This leads to increase in easily available resources that have resulted in plagiarism cases. With increase in plagiarism cases, it becomes necessary to pay attention towards prevention of plagiarism. To prevent plagiarism cases if possible or minimize plagiarism cases, the task of plagiarism detection plays important role. There is large number of plagiarism detection tools available, used in plagiarism detection process that in turn, helps in identifying plagiarism cases. In the current scenario, the performance of plagiarism detection tools has become a major concern. This paper proposes to study eight open-source plagiarism detection tools and compare their performance. A single paragraph was passed through these plagiarism detection tools and results obtained, in terms of similarity percentage, were compared. The performance of each of these tools, was measured based on two parameters, namely accuracy in plagiarism detection and execution time. Experiment shows variation in the plagiarism percentage as mentioned in the reports generated by these plagiarism detection tools. Apart from this, it was observed that there is variation in execution time for each of these tools as noted down by the researcher. The variation indicates inability of these tools to identify higher level of modifications. In future, performance of existing open-source as well as paid plagiarism detection tools, not covered under study, can be measured.

Keywords: Plagiarism, Plagiarism Detection, Plagiarism detection tools

OP 32

Bibliometric Mapping of Machine Learning for Cybersecurity**Mr. Amrut Mohan Jadhav^{1*} and Dr. Ramchadra Mahadik²**¹**Department of Computer Applications, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Pune**²**Department of Computer Applications, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Pune****Abstract**

Background and Rationale: AI provides modern solutions to address problems quickly without continuous human intervention. With the increasing use of the Internet and network-based solutions, cybersecurity persists as a major challenge in the current era. Machine learning techniques have been increasingly applied and have made significant scientific contributions to the field of cybersecurity.

Objective of the Study: This systematic review paper presents a bibliometric analysis to map relationships, trends, clusters, network structures and author collaborations in machine learning for cybersecurity using Scopus literature published between January 2015 and 19 January 2026.

Methodology: A structured review was conducted using the Scopus database with the keywords ‘Machine Learning’ and ‘Cybersecurity’ to retrieve Scopus-indexed research papers published between January 2015 and 19 January 2026. The annual publication trends, author productivity, top citations, leading sources, and collaboration patterns in ML-based cybersecurity research, along with keyword co-occurrence networks were analysed using the Bibliometric Analysis dashboard.

Key Findings/Results: A tremendous growth rate of nearly four times was observed from 2021 (136) to 2025 (445) in the field. Pawlicki M., Kozik R., Choras M. and Dang Q.V. emerged as the most productive authors. ‘Machine Learning and Deep Learning Methods for Cybersecurity’ was identified as one of the most cited manuscripts. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems and IEEE Access were the most influential sources up to 19 January 2026. The keyword co-occurrence network discovered dominant research patterns and emerging research trends in this field. Central keywords depicted well-established research areas, while peripheral nodes

indicated emerging topics. The central keywords co-occurrence of machine learning within the network confirms the important role of machine learning in the field of cybersecurity research.

Conclusion/Implications: This review explores associations among authors, collaborative networks, research trends using a high-quality Scopus bibliographic dataset. Future studies may extend this research work by incorporating datasets such as Web of Science and by investigating the integration of AI and IoT technologies for enhancing intelligent cybersecurity solutions.

Keywords: Bibliometric analysis, Cybersecurity, Machine Learning, Scientific Collaboration.

OP 33

Pattern of Utilization of Healthcare in Type 2 Diabetes in Gurugram District of Haryana**Dr. Vandana**

Department of Community Medicine, FMHS, SGT University

Abstract: Diabetes Complications and Healthcare Utilization Patterns in Gurugram District, Haryana: A Cross-Sectional Study

Background: Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) represents a significant public health burden in India, with high prevalence of complications and fragmented healthcare delivery. Understanding local complication patterns and facility utilization is essential for targeted intervention.

Objectives: To assess the prevalence and severity of diabetes-related complications and characterize healthcare facility utilization patterns among T2DM patients in Gurugram district, Haryana.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among T2DM patients in Gurugram district. Data were collected on diabetes complications (mild, moderate, severe), healthcare facility utilization, and service engagement. Association between disease duration and complication burden was analyzed.

Results: Of the study participants, 52.09% reported at least one diabetes-related complication, with 26.28% experiencing mild, 17.33% moderate, and 8.49% severe complications. Notably, 47.91% had no complications. Patients with diabetes duration >10 years showed significantly higher complication prevalence compared to those with shorter disease duration ($p < 0.05$).

Regarding healthcare facility utilization, private clinics dominated (46.74%), followed by government PHCs (26.74%), private hospitals (10.81%), and government hospitals (9.30%). AYUSH facilities were utilized by only 6.40% of patients. All participants (100%) accessed OPD services; 84.19% underwent laboratory investigations, 59.53% consulted specialists, but only 33.02% practiced self-monitoring of blood glucose (SMBG).

Conclusions: The study reveals a substantial complication burden in Gurugram's diabetic population, correlating with disease chronicity. Healthcare utilization is predominantly private-

sector dependent with limited self-management practices. These findings underscore the need for strengthening government primary health systems, promoting SMBG literacy, and integrated diabetes care models to reduce complications and improve outcomes.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Complications, Healthcare Utilization, Gurugram, Haryana, India.

OP 34

Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs), Associated Factors, Preventive Practices and Barriers among Information Technology (IT) Professionals in Gurugram: A Cross-Sectional Study**Shivam Sakshi**

Department of Community Medicine, FMHS, SGT University, Gurugram, Haryana 122505

Abstract

Background: Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) have become an important occupational health concern among Information Technology (IT) professionals. Long hours of computer use, repetitive movements, limited mobility, and psychosocial stress can gradually lead to discomfort, chronic pain, and reduced quality of life. These issues also affect work performance through absenteeism and presenteeism. In Gurugram, one of India's major IT hubs, limited local evidence exists on the burden of MSDs and the workplace conditions that shape it. This gap restricts the development of effective ergonomic strategies and health promotion programs, making the issue relevant to both public health and workplace policy.

Objective: The objective of the study is to determine the magnitude of MSDs and identify associated risk factors, preventive practices, and barriers among IT professionals in Gurugram.

Methods: A cross-sectional study is being conducted across major IT hubs in Gurugram using stratified random sampling to select IT companies and simple random sampling to identify employees. A structured questionnaire and the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ) are being used for data collection. Quantitative analysis will include descriptive and multivariate approaches to explore determinants of MSDs and patterns of preventive practices.

Results (Preliminary): Early trends from ongoing data collection suggest that IT professionals frequently report discomfort affecting the lower back, neck, and shoulders. Prolonged sitting, limited breaks, and suboptimal workstation ergonomics appear to be contributing factors. Although awareness regarding ergonomic measures is common, consistent implementation is hindered by workload pressures, insufficient ergonomic support at the organizational level, and a perception that symptoms do not require immediate correction.

Conclusion: Preliminary findings indicate that MSDs may represent a modifiable public health issue among IT professionals in Gurugram. Final results are expected to provide actionable insights for employers, policymakers, and occupational health practitioners to develop healthier and more supportive workplaces.

Keywords: Public health, Musculoskeletal disorders, Ergonomics, IT professionals, Occupational health, Workplace wellness, Gurugram.

OP 35

Animating Sustainability: Narrative Strategies of Sustainability in Hayao Miyazaki's Animated Cinema

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Department of English, LPU

Abstract

This study focuses on how Hayao Miyazaki's anime movies even without preaching conveys themes linked with sustainability goal. There are numerous research articles on Hayao Miyazaki's environmental intentions but very limited research integrates qualitative thematic and semiotic analysis with explicitly mapping cinematic representations onto formal sustainability frameworks. Addressing this gap, we conduct scene-based thematic coding and SDG mapping across six films ($n = 210$ scenes), employing both qualitative intensity scoring and quantitative frequency analysis. Findings demonstrate that SDG 15 (Life on Land) dominates representation (41.0%, $n = 86$), with secondary emphasis on SDG 12 (27.6%, $n = 58$) and SDG 13 (21.0%, $n = 44$). Qualitative analysis identifies coexistence as the most ethically emphasized theme ($M = 4.9/5.0$), despite moderate quantitative frequency. Temporal analysis reveals a clear creative trajectory: early films prioritize ecological preservation (58.0% SDG 15), middle films balance ecological and consumption concerns (37.5% SDG 15; 29.8% SDG 12), and the late film emphasizes technological ethics (45.5% SDG 9). Integrating strong sustainability theory and posthumanism we argue that Miyazaki's cinema functions as a sophisticated medium for sustainability communication, visualizing non-human agency and relational ethics in ways that live-action cinema cannot achieve. Miyazaki's environmental ethics is something which is coexisting within the narratives and backgrounds. The co-dependence of human and natural world is his main theme. The narratives and the greenery effortlessly reconnect us with the idea of Anthropocene which contradicts and co-exists both with human progress. Sustainability is the only way to solve this contradiction in a uniquely Miyazakian way.

Keywords: Miyazaki Movies, Animation studies, Sustainability, SDG goals, Environmental Ethics, Posthumanism, Ecology

OP 36

The Role of Citation Analysis in Measuring Research Impact and Scholarly Influence**Mrs. Usha Pawar¹ and Dr. Mohan Jamdade²**¹Research Scholar, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University Pune Yashwantrao Mohite College of Arts, Commerce and Science²Librarian, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University Pune New Law College, Pune

Abstract: This paper discusses citation analysis as a basic bibliometric method of assessing the impact of research and scholarly influence on the academic community. Citation analysis is a systematic analysis of the number and occurrence of scholarly works being referenced and to what extent reflecting their visibility, relevance, and intellectual contribution to various disciplines. The process aids in determining the impact articles, authors, journals, and institutions by examining the number of citations and citation patterns, networks, and can be utilized in making evidence-based judgments about the research process, granting of funds, promotions, and institutional ranking. The h-index, impact factor, Eigenfactor and SCImago Journal Rank together with methods like co-citation analysis and citation networks, are advanced indicators that allow one to have a subtle insight into the development and spread of knowledge over time. The research emphasizes the value of citation analysis as a tool of research trend tracking, seminal work identification, and emission of the efficient literature identification by forward and backward citation tracking. Simultaneously, it also does not overlook several important limitations, such as the disciplinary differences in citation behavior, the impact of self-citations, language bias, and the propensity of metrics towards other well-established or popular research areas.

Keywords: Citation Analysis, Bibliometrics, Research Impact, Scholarly Influence, h-index, Impact Factor, Research Evaluation.

OP 37

Revisiting Organizational Socialization and Onboarding through Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

Purpose- Two key concept in Organizational behaviour research, Organizational socialization and Onboarding are examined in this bibliometric analysis.

Design/methodology/approach- Preferred Reporting Item for systematic review and Meta-Analyses framework is used for the compilation of the paper and the RStudio and VOS Viewer application with Scopus database is used for bibliometric analysis.

Finding- Overall, the bibliometric findings indicate that organizational socialization and onboarding research has evolved from a nascent field into a rapidly expanding and mature domain, with a sharp growth in publications over the past decade. The literature is intellectually anchored in a small set of highly influential journals and scholars, primarily within vocational and organizational psychology, while also drawing from HRM, communication, and career studies. Geographically, knowledge production remains concentrated in North America and Europe, with growing contributions from Asia, highlighting both increasing internationalization and the need for broader global representation.

Originality/Value – the study is the original piece of work by the author with no conflict of interest with any party, person or organization.

Keyword- Organizational socialization, Newcomer socialization, Employee socialization, Entry socialization, Employee adaptation, Newcomer Adjustment, Onboarding, Induction, Orientation training & orientation assimilation, Organizational entry

OP 38

Instant Delivery Services: A Bibliometric Analysis**Areeba Khan****Research Scholar, Faculty of Management Studies, University of Lucknow**

Abstract: The instant delivery sector represents a rapidly evolving segment of the Indian retail market. Its primary value proposition lies in the capability to deliver a broad assortment of goods to consumers within extremely short timeframes, often as little as 10 minutes. In India, key instant delivery platforms include Dunzo Daily, Swiggy Instamart, Big Basket Daily, and Blinkit. These firms employ a decentralized fulfillment model by establishing strategically located micro-warehouses, commonly known as “dark stores,” in densely populated urban areas. Orders are processed and dispatched from these facilities by delivery personnel, enabling near-immediate fulfillment. The instant delivery model can be viewed as an advanced extension of the traditional e-commerce framework, emphasizing speed and proximity to consumers. An initial dataset of 303 scholarly publications, covering the period from 2015 to 2026, was obtained from the Scopus database. After a rigorous selection and screening procedure, the final set of articles was examined using bibliometric methods supported by the *bibliometrix* package in RStudio, along with visualization software including VOSviewer. The data were examined using the Bibliometrix package in RStudio to evaluate trends in annual scientific output, identify leading authors and core publication sources, and analyze keyword structures. VOSviewer was employed to conduct network analysis and generate visual representations of relationships among keywords. These visualizations enabled the identification of distinct keyword clusters, offering insights into the key research areas within the instant delivery domain.

OP 39

ECONOMIC GROWTH AND CARBON EMISSIONS: WHY QUAD NATIONS FOLLOW DIVERGENT DECARBONIZATION PATHS

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ABSTRACT

This study takes the first close look at how the four QUAD countries, the United States, Japan, Australia, and India, have moved toward cleaner energy from 2000 to 2021. By tracking how their use of renewables, carbon emissions, and economic growth are connected, we see that each nation has followed a distinctly different path, even though they are strong geopolitical partners.

The United States achieved the largest decline in per-person CO₂ emissions, cutting them by nearly one-third, while still growing its renewable energy share. Japan followed a path of steady decarbonization with more moderate renewable growth. Australia also reduced its emissions by a fifth while increasing its use of renewables.

India's trajectory stands in clear contrast. Although it maintained the highest share of renewable energy among the QUAD countries throughout the entire period, averaging close to 40%, its rapid economic growth was accompanied by a near-doubling of per-capita emissions.

The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted these diverging roads. The developed members managed to keep emissions below pre-pandemic levels during recovery, while India experienced a strong, V-shaped rebound in both economic activity and emissions.

These findings challenge the expectation that strategic allies will naturally converge in their climate efforts. Instead, they show that a country's stage of development fundamentally shapes how effectively renewable energy deployment translates into lower emissions. For policymakers, this underscores that uniform climate strategies are unlikely to succeed within diverse alliances like the QUAD. The study concludes by calling for more flexible forms of cooperation frameworks that acknowledge structural differences while identifying concrete areas where shared interests can drive practical joint action.

Keywords- Economic Growth, QUAD Alliance, Renewable Energy Transition, Carbon Emissions, Comparative Analysis, Sustainable Development, Climate Policy, Energy Economics.

OP 40**Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using Citrus Orange peels and evaluation of their anticancer Property****Chhavi Acharya¹, Priyanka Singh² *****Nims institute of Allied Medical Science and Technology****NIMS University Rajasthan, Jaipur, India**

Abstract: This work aimed to synthesis silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using biological waste products Citrus orange peels, its characterization, and their cytotoxic effect. SEM and TEM analysis confirmed the formation of spherical and uninformed nanoparticle. The average size of the synthesized nanoparticle was 10-11 nm as measured by DLS technique. FTIR analysis of the green synthesized AgNPs showed the presence of alcohols, phenolics, alkynes, aliphatic primary amines, and amino acid groups. Finally, the evaluation of the cytotoxic effect of the green synthesized AgNPs were done using human colon carcinoma cell line (HCT-116). The results revealed the concentration has a direct correlation with cell viability. The 50% inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of the HCT-116 cell line was expected as 8-10 µg/ml.

Keyword: Citrus orange peel, silver nanoparticle, characterisation, anticancer agent

OP 41**Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) of Artificial Intelligence in Nutrition among Physiotherapy (BPT) Students in Bangalore using Bayesian Regression Modelling****Lavanya R¹, Dr Manzoor Ahmad Khanday²****¹Phd Scholar at School of Chemistry, Engineering and Physical Sciences Lovely Professional University, Punjab****²Assistant Professor at School of Chemistry, Engineering and Physical Sciences Lovely Professional University, Punjab**

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a new and growing technology that is slowly changing healthcare, including the field of nutrition. AI can help in tracking food intake, identifying foods from images, estimating calories, planning personalized diets, and supporting clinical decisions. Nutrition is very important in physiotherapy practice because proper diet helps in muscle recovery, strength, healing, and overall rehabilitation. Physiotherapy students are future healthcare professionals who will guide patients during recovery, so it is important to understand how much they know about AI in nutrition, how they feel about it, and whether they use it in practice.

This study aims to assess the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) of Artificial Intelligence in Nutrition among Physiotherapy (BPT) students. Data will be collected using a structured questionnaire shared through Google Forms. The questionnaire will include sections on demographic details, knowledge about AI in nutrition, attitude towards the use of AI, and practice or usage of AI-based nutrition tools.

Bayesian regression modelling will be used to analyze the data. Bayesian linear regression will be applied to identify factors influencing knowledge and attitude scores, while Bayesian logistic regression will be used to examine factors affecting the practice of AI-based nutrition tools. Variables such as age, gender, year of study, knowledge score, and attitude score will be included in the models. Results will be presented using probabilities, odds ratios, and credible intervals.

The results of this study will help to provide the level of awareness and acceptance of AI in nutrition among physiotherapy students. The findings will help identify gaps in knowledge and

practice and highlight the need for training and education related to AI in nutrition and may support the inclusion of AI-based nutrition concepts in physiotherapy education and help prepare students for future clinical practice.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Nutrition, Knowledge Attitude and Practice (KAP), Physiotherapy students, Bayesian regression modelling, Dietary assessment

OP 42

A Systematic Review on Magnetic Properties of Mn-Ni Based Full-Heusler Alloys

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Abstract: Magnetic materials are becoming high demanding due to their suitable application in spintronic devices. Among the several magnetic materials, Heusler alloys have exhibited a great interest mainly due to their half metallic behavior along with high magnetic moments. Here, we report the rigorous analysis of Mn based full-Heusler magnetic materials as magnetic moment in these materials are found to be highly around the Mn elements. Magnetic moment of Mn in different Mn-based alloys has been listed in the table for the comparison. Therefore, experimental findings specifically on Mn₂NiSb have been critically reviewed in the subsequent section of this manuscript. However, several compensated ferrimagnetic and antiferromagnetic Heusler alloys have also been studied and few examples have also been given in order to show the multifunctionality of these alloys. Composites of half and full-Heusler have also been experimentally established with reducing their magnetic behavior. Effect of structure on the magnetic has also been revealed from the available literature. Specifically, structure of Mn₂NiSb full-Heusler alloy in their cubic, tetragonal and hexagonal form has been simulated and X-Ray diffraction data are plotted for each. Since, the magnetic behavior of these materials is intrinsically linked to their crystal structure and their respective sites. Any small change in their structure has significantly changed their magnetic behavior. Therefore, transition from low temperature austenite to high temperature martensite phase have been exhibited which has revealed in the magnetization versus temperature data in zero field cooled and field cooled measurements.

Keywords: Full-Heusler Alloys, Spintronic Application, Magnetic Moment, X-Ray Diffraction Data etc.

OP 43

From stress and strength: The role of psychological hardiness in advancing sustainable future**Shivi Agarwal¹ and Dr. PratibhaSagar²**¹Research scholar, Dept. of B.Ed./M.Ed., M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly²Assitant Professor, Dept. of B.Ed./M.Ed., M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly

Abstract: In the present era, people are facing many challenges like stress, climate change, work pressure and economic problems. Citizens are the assets of any nation, so development of any nation depends on the growth and development of their countryman. To build sustainable future, it is need to learn handle stress in positive way. To transform stress into strength, psychological hardiness is helpful for individual. It is a personality trait that improves emotional balance, problem solving ability, confidence and resilience. Psychological hardiness is defined interrelated dimensions of control (ability to overcome challenges of life), challenge (ability to see problems and stressful situations as opportunity) and commitment (ability to stay involved in life and take responsibility their works).When individual are mentally strong they can contribute more effectively in social, economic and environment development. Psychological hardiness refers to a positive mental health and enables them to stay strong and stable during stressful situations. Psychologically resilient people are not easily overtaken by issues. Rather, they think they can manage difficulties and come up with solutions. This way of thinking lessens stress and keeps unpleasant feelings like fear, anxiety, and frustration from taking over. This paper explores the role of psychological hardiness in moving stress into strength and promotes sustainable development. People with high hardiness are better able to handle stress as manageable and opportunity for personal growth. This paper also suggested how psychological hardiness can be developed by educational program, awareness program and supportive social environment.

Keywords: Psychological hardiness, stress, strength, sustainable development, oppoutunity.

OP 44**Isolation, identification & optimization of new microbial strain from soil sample for the production of cellulase.****Karan Singh and Priyanka Singh*****Nims institute of Allied Medical Science and Technology,
NIMS University Rajasthan, Jaipur, India**

Abstract: Cellulose which is present in abundance in our environment can be utilized as a renewable energy source. Hence, cellulase being the only enzyme that can help us breakdown this lignocellulosic biomass has gained a large interest of scientists and industrialists. Cellulase hydrolyses the β -1,4 bonds of cellulose and breaks it down into smaller glucose molecules. Cellulase enzyme is now used in most of the food businesses, silk industries for the softening of the fabrics and Biofuel production. Isolating the microbes from soil sample and allowing them to grow in CMC agar plate for 24hrs at 7.0 pH and temperature maintained at 37°C. The strains were selected with Congo red staining and further grown in optimised condition for the maximum production of cellulase.

Keywords: Cellulase, Lignocellulosic, Biofuel.

OP 45

Efficient Removal of Safranin Dye from Aqueous Solutions using *Thuidium cymbifolium* (Dozy & Molk.) Dozy & Molk.: A Green Approach**Meenu Elizabeth Benny¹, Tess Babu¹, Meenu Mathew¹, Deepak R¹, Abraham Mathew^{1*}****¹Bryology Division, P.G. and Research Department of Botany****St. Peter's College, Kolenchery, Kerala**

Abstract: Safranin is a persistent and poisonous dye that lingers in the environment, causing impairment to humans and wildlife. Its effects can range from acute irritation to potential long-term damage to organs, making it a significant biohazard. This study explores *Thuidium cymbifolium* (Dozy & Molk.) Dozy & Molk. potential as a biodegradable biosorbent for removing safranin dye from water considering factors like sorbent dose, dye concentration, temperature, and pH. The thallus dose was varied from 0.5 g to 3 g at a fixed 12.5 mg/L dye concentration. Results exhibited increased dye removal with longer contact time, higher concentrations, and larger surface areas. The experimental data was fitted to different kinetic models such as first order, pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order, intra particle diffusion model and Elovich kinetic model. Equilibrium isotherms were analysed using Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, and Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm models. Thermodynamic analysis revealed better biosorption at high temperatures. Overall, *Thuidium cymbifolium* (Dozy & Molk.) Dozy & Molk. arises as an eco-friendly, cost-effective solution for wastewater treatment, supporting a cleaner environment.

Keywords: Safranin, adsorption, isotherms, kinetics

OP 46

Performance Management Systems in Manufacturing Industries: Foundations for Productivity, Engagement, Strategic Alignment and Resilience: A Literature Review**Soumen Sarkar****Research Scholar, Faculty of Management Studies
The ICFAI University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India**

Abstract: Performance Management Systems (PMS) are essential for enhancing productivity, employee engagement, commitment, motivation and the overall success of organizations. An effective PMS aligns employee performance with organizational objectives, such as skill enhancement, teamwork and adaptability. A robust performance management system plays a critical role in enhancing a company's adaptability and long-term success and organizational resilience. In dynamic and uncertain business environments, performance management should go beyond traditional metrics and control mechanisms to become a strategic enabler of resilience. By setting clear goals, aligning individual and organizational priorities, providing timely feedback and recognizing performance, organizations foster agility, accountability and capability. This study examines the significance of role clarity, leadership, organizational culture and employee motivation in refining performance management practices. Furthermore, technology and data analytics have emerged as critical components in modern PMS, offering real-time insights and facilitating informed decision-making. Despite widespread recognition of the value of performance evaluations, discrepancies persist between intended goals and actual implementation. Research highlights those inconsistencies in appraisal practices. A successful PMS is one that is adaptable, inclusive and transparent. Openness, diversity and inclusion are the culture of values. Organization should have transparent culture where employee feels involved, motivated and committed. Involvement is directly proportional to commitment and as such a committed employee is the real resource of an Organization and can overcome any challenges in the interest of the Organization. The integration of SMART goals strengthens the ability to adapt and thrive amid turbulence. To maintain competitive advantage, organizations must evolve their performance management frameworks to dynamically connect business strategy with individual contributions, supporting real-time responsiveness and strategic decision-making in uncertain environments. There are indications that some organizations have implemented an ERP system

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in order to keep it up with competitors. Effectiveness of a Firm is affected by various dimensions of PMS such as performancebased appraisal system, organization vision & mission. In that way, the entire organization will move in a single direction. When the goals are clear, the targets are clear, the employee will perform better & the Management also get better output from the employee in terms of better quality, better productivity. When the Company will grow, the employees will also grow. All Organizations should Manage performance & maximize results in this way and should have the urge to take the organization to its next level. Future research could explore the long-term impact of PMS on employee behavior and organizational sustainability

OP 47

Micro Mastery Iterative Learning Model (MMILM) for Effective Online Education**Mr. Bharat Suryawanshi¹ and Dr. Sachin Ayarekar²**¹Assistant Registrar, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University),
Center for Distance and Online Education, Pune-411030²Assistant Professor, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University),
Institute of Management and Entrepreneurship Development, Pune-411038

Abstract: Online education is growing day by day and creating a tremendous impact on education ecosystem. Rapid evolution of digital infrastructure, increased access and emerging technologies has expanded the scope for innovative strategies to enhance online learning outcomes. Despite the availability of advanced technologies, supporting skill-based learning in online environments remains challenging. Ensuring smooth execution and effective learning outcomes through self-paced online education is difficult to measure and analyse for the teaching fraternity. Moreover, despite numerous digital initiatives, student assessment, quality assurance, and student engagement continue to be critical challenges that require focused attention. To address these issues, assessment can be implemented through iterative mastery learning techniques using innovative, engaging, and exploratory strategies. The research work proposes Micro Mastery Iterative Learning Model (MMILM) to provide engaging assessment practices that lead to improved online learning outcomes. The transition of micro learning mechanisms towards mastery-based learning is presented as an innovative strategy to enhance depth of understanding and fine-tune learners' conceptual clarity, thereby ensuring the achievement of learning outcomes. Comprehensive strategies such as MMILM are essential for addressing existing challenges and for creating a more inclusive, effective and outcome-oriented online educational environment.

Keywords: Mastery Learning, Online Education, Student Engagement, Student Assessment.

OP 48

2D Animated Storytelling as a Medium for Enhanced Emotional and Cognitive Engagement**Nitin Bihari Jaswal¹, Ganesh Gule², Dipankar Gitesh Goswami³, Swapnil Suresh Bhamare⁴, Kamal Srivastava⁵**¹Research Scholar, Lovely Professional University & Assistant Professor, MIT-ADT University, School of Fine Arts & Applied Arts, Pune, India, 412201²Assistant Professor, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India, 144411,³Assistant Professor, MIT-ADT University, School of Fine Arts & Applied Arts, Pune, India, 412201,⁴Assistant Professor, MIT-ADT University, School of Fine Arts & Applied Arts, Pune, India, 412201,⁵Assistant Professor, MIT-ADT University, School of Fine Arts & Applied Arts, Pune, India, 412201

Abstract: 2D animated storytelling has emerged as a powerful communication medium integrating narrative structure, visual symbolism, motion, and sound to influence human cognition and emotional response. Video production offers a way for students to learn content-area knowledge while simultaneously developing technology skills deemed important in contemporary society. [1] Despite rapid advancements in immersive media technologies, 2D animation continues to play a vital role in education, communication design, entertainment, and therapeutic practices due to its simplicity, accessibility, and expressive potential. This paper examines how 2D animated storytelling enhances emotional engagement and cognitive processing among audiences. Drawing on theories of narrative cognition, emotional design, visual perception, and multimedia learning, the study adopts a mixed-method research approach involving literature review, audience response analysis, and comparative observation. The findings suggest that 2D animated narratives significantly improve attention span, emotional resonance, comprehension, and memory retention compared to static and text-based media. The study establishes a conceptual framework positioning 2D animation as an effective tool for emotional communication and knowledge transfer. This article discusses how an APE course used a video-editing SL project to document student learning and performance in the Adapted Physical Education National Standards and prepare future general PETE students to teach students with disabilities. [2] The paper concludes by highlighting the relevance of animated

storytelling in contemporary digital education and visual communication, offering directions for future interdisciplinary research.

Keywords: 2D Animation, Storytelling, Emotional Engagement, Cognitive Engagement, Visual Communication, Multimedia Learning

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OP 49

**Environmental Literacy and Sustainable Living Practices among Adolescents in Bihar's
High Schools: A Review Study**

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Patna University, Patna-800001**

Abstract: Environmental literacy plays a vital role in shaping sustainable behaviours among adolescents, who represent a critical group for long-term environmental stewardship. This review study synthesises existing research on environmental awareness, attitudes, and sustainable living practices among high school students in Bihar, India. The analysis focuses on educational influences, school-based initiatives, and socio-economic factors that affect students' engagement with environmental issues. Findings from reviewed studies indicate that while students possess basic knowledge of environmental concepts, the consistent adoption of sustainable practices remains limited. Experiential learning, teacher involvement, and community-oriented programs were found to significantly enhance both awareness and responsible behaviour. However, disparities related to school resources and socio-economic conditions continue to influence outcomes. The review highlights the need for curriculum integration, practical learning approaches, and collaborative community efforts to strengthen environmental education at the secondary school level. These insights offer valuable implications for educators, policymakers, and institutions seeking to promote sustainable development through education.

Keywords: Environmental literacy, Sustainable practices, Adolescents, Secondary education, Environmental education, Sustainable development, Bihar.

OP 50

Hexanediamine assisted surface modification of ZnO nanoparticles for dielectric property tailoring and enhanced asymmetric supercapacitor device performance**Kaneez Fatima****Research scholar, Department of Chemistry****Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh**

Abstract: The development of multifunctional nanomaterials with both superior dielectric and electrochemical properties is crucial for advancing modern electronic and energy storage technologies. In this study, hexanediamine-functionalized zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) were synthesized and systematically investigated. ZnO nanoparticles were successfully functionalized with 1,6-hexanediamine, and comprehensive analysis confirmed modifications in structural, optical, chemical, and morphological properties, validating the effectiveness of the functionalization process. PXRD confirmed enhanced crystallinity and increased crystallite size upon capping, while FTIR verified successful amine functionalization through characteristic NH and CH₂ vibrations. Optical studies revealed a blue shift in absorption and reduced trap emissions in capped ZnO NPs due to quantum confinement, with band gaps of 3.02 eV (pure) and 2.87 eV (capped). TEM analysis confirmed improved morphology and dispersion in capped ZnO NPs with hexagonal shape and reduced agglomeration. The dielectric behavior of the functionalized ZnO NPs showed real and imaginary dielectric permittivity of 115 and 99 at 1 MHz, respectively. Additionally, the material exhibited an AC conductivity of 0.0056 $\Omega^{-1}\text{mm}^{-1}$, highlighting its potential for advanced electronic application. Furthermore, an asymmetric device was fabricated to investigate the electrochemical properties, which displayed cyclic stability. After 15,000 cycles at a current density of 15 mAcm⁻², the device retained 81% of its capacitance and achieved nearly 100% Coulombic efficiency. The device also exhibited notable energy and power densities of 10.94 mWh cm⁻² at 1 mA cm⁻² and 5000 mW cm⁻² at 10 mA cm⁻², respectively. These findings underscore the device's superior performance and long-term durability, positioning it as a desirable candidate for advanced energy storage applications. Finally, a real-time supercapacitor was demonstrated, showcasing the practical application of the functionalized ZnO NPs in energy storage technologies.

Keywords: Nanomaterials, PXRD, FTIR, TEM

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OP 51

Immediate Effects of a Structured 4-Week Yoga Program on Heart Rate Variability and Autonomic Regulation in Healthcare Workers: A Randomized Controlled TrialAnita Verma^{1*}, Vartika Saxena¹, Bela Goyal², Apar Avinash Saoji³, Yogesh Saxena⁴¹Department of Community and Family Medicine, AIIMS Rishikesh, Uttarakhand²Department of Biochemistry, AIIMS Rishikesh, Uttarakhand³School of Yoga and Naturopathic Medicine, SVYASA, Bengaluru, Karnataka⁴Department of Physiology, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, SRHU, Uttarakhand**Abstract**

Background: Chronic occupational stress among healthcare workers (HCWs) can adversely influence autonomic nervous system functioning and cardiovascular health. Heart rate variability (HRV) provides a non-invasive assessment of sympatho-vagal balance. Emerging evidence suggests that yoga may play a role in improving autonomic regulation. This study evaluated the immediate effects of a structured 4-week yoga module on HRV parameters among HCWs. The yoga module was developed by the Defence Institute of Physiology and Allied Sciences (DIPAS), Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO).

Methods: A randomized controlled trial was carried out in a tertiary care hospital enrolling 108 healthcare workers aged 19–60 years. Participants were randomly allocated to either a yoga intervention group (n = 54) or a medium-paced walking control group (n = 54). The yoga group participated in supervised sessions lasting 30 minutes per day, 5 days per week for 4 weeks, while the control group undertook medium-paced walking for an equivalent duration. Time- and frequency-domain HRV parameters, including RR interval, RMSSD, 30:15 ratio, LF, HF, and LF/HF ratio, were recorded using a portable BIOPAC MP46 system pre- and post-intervention on Days 1, 14, and 28 to evaluate acute changes in autonomic regulation.

Results: The yoga group showed significant immediate autonomic modulation, with increased ln HF and reduced ln LF/HF on Day 1 (p = 0.027 and p = 0.019, respectively) and Day 14 (p = 0.049 and p = 0.023), whereas no significant within-group changes were observed in controls. Between-group comparisons demonstrated significantly greater reductions in ln LF and ln LF/HF in the yoga group on Day 1 (p = 0.022 and p = 0.009) and Day 14 (p = 0.044 and p = 0.019). No significant between-group differences were noted on Day 28.

Conclusion: This structured 4-week yoga intervention produced significant immediate improvements in autonomic balance among HCWs, reflected by enhanced parasympathetic

activity and reduced sympathetic dominance. These findings suggest that yoga may serve as an effective short-term strategy for autonomic regulation in high-stress occupational settings.

Keywords: Yoga, Heart Rate Variability, Sympatho-Vagal Balance, Healthcare Workers, Autonomic Regulation.

OP 52

Computational Design and Optimization of an Ideal FrGeCl₃ Lead-Free Perovskite Solar Cell for Theoretical Benchmark Analysis**Priyanka Singh¹ and Brijesh Kumar Pandey^{1*}****¹Department of Physics and Material Science, Madan Mohan Malaviya University of Technology, Gorakhpur, U.P, India, 273010**

Abstract: Despite significant advancements in inorganic metal-halide PSCs, the use of lead (Pb)-based perovskite solar cell presents environmental issues, underscoring the necessity for more sustainable and stable materials. This study analyses FrGeCl₃ as a theoretical benchmark for assessing the potential performance of lead-free germanium halide perovskites under optimal conditions. Although Fr is not appropriate for practical applications, its electronic structure contributes to the prediction of the behaviour of future non-toxic materials exhibiting analogous properties. SCAPS-1D simulations are employed to examine the effects of various transport materials and device parameters on charge extraction, recombination, and efficiency. The analysis thoroughly investigates critical photovoltaic factors such as layer thickness, J-V characteristics, temperature response, quantum efficiency, defect density, band alignment, and doping concentration. Optimizing the FTO/WO₃/FrGeCl₃/CBTS/back-contact structure results in an open-circuit voltage Voc of 0.9286 V, a short-circuit current density Jsc of 40.989 mA/cm², a fill factor of 82.30%, and a theoretical efficiency of 28.17%. The results presented here are intended to set a theoretical performance ceiling with an enhancement of the basic understanding needed to guide the design and synthesis of future stable, non-radioactive perovskites with analogous electronic characteristics.

Keywords: HTM, FrGeCl₃, ETM, Copper, SCAPS-1 D.

OP 53

In-silico Design and Validation of PCR Primers for AT1R Gene Polymorphism in Hypertensive Patients**Archana Adhikari¹, Dr. Chandrakala Sharma², Dr. Mingma Lhamu Sherpa³, Dr. Mona Dhakal⁴**^{1,2}**Department of Pharmacology, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences, 5th Mile Tadong, Sikkim**³**Department of Biochemistry, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences, 5th Mile Tadong, Sikkim**⁴**Department of Medicine, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences, 5th Mile Tadong, Sikkim****Abstract**

Background: Genetic variations in the angiotensin II type 1 receptor (AT1R) gene are associated with the pathogenesis of essential hypertension and variability in response to angiotensin receptor blockers. Accurate identification of AT1R gene polymorphisms depends on the availability of well designed and validated polymerase chain reaction primers to ensure specificity reliability and reproducibility of molecular analyses.

Objective: The present study aimed to design and validate PCR primers for the amplification of a clinically relevant polymorphic region of the AT1R gene using in silico tools followed by laboratory validation in hypertensive patients.

Methods: Primer sequences were designed using NCBI Primer BLAST targeting the selected polymorphic site of the AT1R gene. In silico validation included evaluation of primer length GC content melting temperature secondary structure formation and potential primer dimer interactions using OligoAnalyzer tools. Primer specificity was further assessed through in silico PCR against the human genome database. Experimental validation was carried out using genomic DNA extracted from hypertensive patients. Conventional PCR amplification was performed and the products were analyzed by agarose gel electrophoresis to confirm amplification efficiency and expected product size.

Results: The selected primer pair demonstrated optimal thermodynamic properties including appropriate GC content and melting temperature with minimal tendency to form hairpins or

primer dimers. In silico PCR analysis confirmed specific amplification of the targeted AT1R gene region without off target products. Laboratory validation consistently produced a single distinct amplicon of the expected size across multiple samples indicating specificity sensitivity and reproducibility of the designed primers.

Conclusion: This study successfully developed and validated a reliable PCR primer set for the amplification of the AT1R gene polymorphic region. These primers represent a molecular tool for pharmacogenetic and association studies in hypertensive populations and support future research aimed at understanding genetic influences on antihypertensive drug response and advancing personalized medicine.

OP 54

From Tradition to Technology: A Bibliometric Exploration of Digital Tools in Traditional Medicine (1995–2025)**Dr.Amit Gajarmal¹****¹Ph.D. (Ayu.), Research Officer (Ayu.), Central Council For Research In Ayurvedic Sciences (CCRAS) - Central Ayurveda Research Institute (CARI), Moti Bagh Road, Patiala, Punjab - 147001, Under Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India, New Delhi, India.**

Abstract: This thirty-year bibliometric analysis (1995–2025) presents the first comprehensive, data-driven visual mapping of global research on the integration of Digital Tools in Traditional Medicine (TM), examining 3,068 unique publications from Scopus and PubMed. This work uniquely quantifies the field's evolution, revealing a critical shift: following two decades of gradual activity, the domain entered an exponential acceleration phase after 2014, demonstrating its status as a high-growth research area. Thematic mapping based on keywords and MeSH terms highlights central research areas of telemedicine, mobile applications, and the impact of COVID-19. Research is led by institutions in the United States and the United Kingdom, with the Journal of Medical Internet Research (JMIR) as the most influential platform. However, network analysis reveals profound fragmentation across author and institutional clusters. Persistent structural deficiencies include the lack of universally accepted digital ontologies for traditional medicine systems and an insufficient number of large-scale randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to rigorously evaluate digital interventions. These findings expose urgent needs for coordinated international collaboration to harmonize data standards and conduct rigorous validation studies, offering a crucial roadmap for future research to realize the full potential of digital health in Traditional Medicine.

Keywords: Digital Health Technologies, Traditional Medicine, Bibliometric Analysis, Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare, Global Research Trends

OP 55

Laboratory Markers for Early Detection of Severe Dengue by the Implications for Length of Hospital Stay**Kumar S¹, R. Raj Bharath²****¹Department of Microbiology, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu - 603203, India****²Department of Transfusion Medicine & Blood Centre, SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Center, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu Tamil Nadu, India**

Abstract: Severe dengue, defined by hemorrhagic fever and dengue shock syndrome, can develop quickly in people who have warning indications such as abdominal pain, mucosal bleeding, and a significant decrease in platelet count. Laboratory markers such as haematocrit, platelet count, liver enzymes, and coagulation tests are critical for early diagnosis and prognosis. This retrospective study was carried out from January 2023 to December 2024 at a super-specialty tertiary care hospital. In adult dengue patients with warning signs, there were 283 patients, which were categorized into 82 patients with >6 days and 201 patients with <6 das. Patient data includes clinical history, radiological findings, demographics and laboratory values were systematically obtained from hospital records during the admission in the hospital. The following laboratory parameters such as increased prothrombin time, Presence of dengue IgM antibody positive and reduction of platelet count contributed to prolonged hospital stay. Simple and routinely available laboratory markers can effectively predict prolonged hospital stay and risk of severe dengue, aiding early clinical decisionmaking.

Keywords: Severe dengue, Platelet count, activated partial thromboplastin time, IgM, Hospital stay.

OP 56

Pomiferin as a Dual-Action Bioactive for Therapeutic Use: In Vitro Antioxidant and AntiInflammatory Insights**Arockya Stafi Arockyasamy¹, Sridevi Gopathy¹, Durga Lakshmanan¹****¹Department of Physiology, SRM Dental College, Ramapuram, Bharathi Salai, Chennai, TN, India**

Abstract: Pomiferin, a prenylated isoflavone derived from *Maclura pomifera*, has gained attention for its potential therapeutic value in conditions involving oxidative stress and inflammation. This study explored its dual bioactivity through in vitro biochemical and molecular assays. Antioxidant capacity was assessed using free-radical scavenging and enzyme inhibition methods, alongside evaluation of intracellular oxidative stress markers in hepatic and muscle cell models. Endogenous antioxidant defences were examined by measuring the activities of key enzymes associated with redox balance. Anti-inflammatory activity was examined by quantifying inflammatory mediators and signaling factors at the molecular level. Cellular assays revealed that pomiferin effectively neutralizes reactive species and inhibits pro-oxidant enzyme activity. These effects corresponded with reduced oxidative damage and enhanced antioxidant enzyme responses, indicating improved cellular resilience. At the inflammatory level, pomiferin downregulated central pro-inflammatory pathways, reflected by decreased cytokine activity and suppressed expression of key regulatory genes involved in inflammatory signaling. These findings indicate that pomiferin limits inflammatory cascades by preventing degradation of cellular components and modulating transcriptional responses. Overall, the study highlights pomiferin as a bifunctional natural compound exhibiting both strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. Its combined molecular effects suggest therapeutic promise against conditions driven by oxidative imbalance and chronic inflammation, supporting further investigation into its potential translational applications.

Keywords: Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory, Gene expression, Invitro, Pomiferin.

OP 57

Investigating the Molecular Mechanisms Underlying the Therapeutic Effects of the Natural Alkaloid Cephalotaxine in Human Osteosarcoma Cells (MG-63 Cells)**Durga Lakshmanan¹, Sridevi Gopathy¹, Arockya Stafi Arockyasamy¹****¹Department of Physiology, SRM Dental College, Ramapuram, Bharathi Salai, Chennai, TN, India**

Abstract: Osteosarcoma is a malignant neoplasm of bone characterised by disrupted osteogenic signalling and increased cellular proliferation. This work assessed the therapeutic efficacy of the natural alkaloid Cephalotaxine in human osteosarcoma (MG-63) cells and investigated the associated molecular pathways. MG-63 cells were subjected to escalating doses of Cephalotaxine and evaluated for cytotoxicity, morphological changes, mineralisation, and protein expression. A significant dosedependent decrease in cell viability was detected, along with morphological characteristics indicative of apoptosis. Mineralisation tests revealed decreased calcium deposition and nodule development, indicating an inhibition of pathological osteogenic activity. Western blot analysis revealed the suppression of growth factor-mediated proliferative signalling. Molecular docking studies demonstrated a robust binding affinity of Cephalotaxine to osteogenic and metastatic regulatory targets, therefore offering mechanistic justification for its noted biological effects. Cephalotaxine demonstrates anti-osteosarcoma efficacy by inhibiting cell survival, inducing apoptosis, suppressing mineralisation, and modulating critical signalling pathways. These results underscore Cephalotaxine as a potential natural therapeutic agent for osteosarcoma and advocate for more exploration in advanced preclinical models.

Keywords: Apoptosis, Bone Remodelling, Cephalotaxine, MG-63 cells, Mineralization, Molecular Docking, Natural Alkaloid, Osteosarcoma.

OP 58

Phytosynthesized Iron Nanoparticles Enhance Seed Germination in Pea (*Pisum sativum* L. var. GS-10): Concentration-Dependent Effects**Priya Kushwaha¹, Rahul Verma², Amit Kumar Singh³, Pallavi Dixit⁴**¹**Research Scholar, Plant Nutrition and Stress Physiology Laboratory, Department of Botany, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007, Uttar Pradesh, India**²**Corresponding Author, Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007, Uttar Pradesh, India**³**Research Associate, Plant Nutrition and Stress Physiology Laboratory, Department of Botany, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007, Uttar Pradesh, India**⁴**Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Mahila Vidyalaya Degree College, Lucknow-226018, Uttar Pradesh, India**

Abstract: Iron (Fe) is an essential micronutrient critical for plant metabolism, yet its immobility in soil often leads to deficiency symptoms, particularly in legumes like pea (*Pisum sativum* L.). Conventional Fe fertilizers face limitations in bioavailability and environmental impact. In recent years, phylogenically synthesized iron nanoparticles (FeNPs) have emerged as a sustainable, eco-friendly alternative due to their high surface area, enhanced reactivity, and biocompatibility. This study investigated the effect of green-synthesized FeNPs, prepared using plant-mediated methods, on seed germination of *Pisum sativum* L. var. GS-10 through seed priming at concentrations of 25, 50, 100, and 200 ppm. Germination parameters were evaluated under controlled conditions. Results demonstrated that all tested concentrations improved germination compared to untreated controls, with the most pronounced enhancement observed at 50 ppm, achieving **100% germination within 24 hours**. A higher concentration (200 ppm) also achieved **100% germination**, albeit within 48 hours. These findings indicate a concentration-dependent promotive effect of phytogetic FeNPs on germination speed and uniformity, likely attributable to improved Fe bioavailability, reduced oxidative stress, and enhanced metabolic activation during imbibition. The study highlights the potential of phytogetic FeNPs as an effective, environmentally benign priming agent to overcome micronutrient constraints and promote rapid, synchronous germination in pea, offering promising applications in sustainable agriculture and precision nano-fertilization strategies for legume crops.

Keywords: Iron nanoparticles, phytochemical synthesis, seed priming, germination enhancement, *Pisum sativum*, micronutrient deficiency, sustainable agriculture, legumes.

OP 59**Variations in the Branching Pattern of Axillary artery- Cadaveric Study****Aswathy M****Research Scholar, Department of Anatomy****Sri Siddhartha Institute Of Medical Sciences and Research Center**

Introduction: Variations in the origin, course, branching and termination of axillary artery have received much importance of anatomists, surgeons, and particularly vascular surgeons. The axillary artery is continuation of subclavian artery, extending from outer border of first rib to the lower border of teres major muscle and it is divided by Pectoralis minor muscle into 3 parts. The axillary artery normally gives off one branch from its first part, i.e. superior thoracic, two branches from second part, i.e., lateral thoracic and thoracoacromial arteries, and three branches from third part, i.e., subscapular, anterior and posterior circumflex humeral arteries.[1]

Objective: To study the variations in the branching pattern of axillary artery

Materials & Methods: This cadaveric study involved the dissection of 30 upper limb specimens from 15 embalmed cadavers during routine dissection classes conducted for 1st MBBS students in the Department of Anatomy of Sathagiri Institute of Medical sciences and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. The axillary arteries were meticulously dissected and the branching pattern including the side was recorded. We encountered multiple variations in many specimens.

Results: In one case, an anomalous common trunk arises bilaterally from the second part of the axillary artery which branches into superior thoracic, lateral thoracic & thoracoacromial trunk which is uncommon. In another a bilateral variant of lateral thoracic artery was noted.

Conclusion: Knowledge of variations in the origin of axillary artery branches is of immense significance to anatomists, anaesthetists, cardiovascular and orthopaedic surgeons during surgical exploration of axilla, during flap or reconstructive surgeries, shoulder dislocation and for radiologists during angiography.

Keywords: Axillary artery, Variation, Cadaveric study, Pectoralis minor

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OP 60**Multiple variations in the tendon of Abductor pollicis longus- A cadaveric study****Raina V Joseph****Research Scholar, Department of Anatomy****Sri Siddhartha Institute Of Medical Sciences and Research Center****Abstract**

Background: Abductor pollicis longus (APL) tendon exhibits significant anatomical variability in the dissections of the wrist near extensor retinaculum of hand which can result in de Quervain's syndrome which is caused by stenosing tenosynovitis, which is crucial for understanding its clinical implications in surgeries involving the thumb. So a cadaveric study was conducted to study the variations and to aid in clinical investigation and management of cases of de Quervain's disease.

Methods: This cadaveric study involved the dissection of 50 upper limb specimens from 15 embalmed cadavers during routine dissection classes conducted for 1st MBBS students in the Department of Anatomy of Sathagiri Institute of Medical sciences and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. We encountered multiple variations in many specimens.

The APL tendons were meticulously dissected, and the number of tendons slips and their insertion sites with other abnormalities in the region of extensor retinaculum including the side were recorded.

Results: The number of APL tendon slips distal to the first extensor compartment ranged from 1 to 8, with double slips being the most common configuration. The primary insertion site was consistently the base of the first metacarpal bone, observed in all specimens. Secondary insertion sites included the abductor pollicis brevis muscle (67.82 %), trapezium (17.24 %), opponens pollicis muscle (5.75 %), and proximal phalanx (2.30 %). Statistical analysis showed no significant differences in the insertion sites between sides and sexes, with subtype IIb being the most common pattern.

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Conclusion: This study highlights significant multiple anatomical variations of the APL tendon in the vicinity of Extensor retinaculum with important clinical implications for Interventional radiology and surgical treatment of thumb-related conditions.

Keywords: Abductor pollicis longus (APL), variation, Cadaveric study, Tendon slips, Extensor retinaculum

OP 61

Phytochemistry and Pharmacological Potential of Saussurea Costus**Sajad Ahmad Sofi****Research Scholar, Department of Botany****NIMS University Rajasthan Jaipur**

Abstract: Saussurea costus is a highly valued medicinal plant that is used in many traditional medical systems, like ayurveda, unani and traditional Chinese medicine. With an emphasis on Saussurea costus's potential for pharmaceutical and therapeutic uses, this article attempts to present a thorough summary of the plant's phytochemical components and pharmacological activity. The plant is abundant in secondary metabolites, including as flavonoids, phenolic acids, and sesquiterpene lactones mainly costunolide and dehydrocostus lactone, which are linked to a variety of bioactivities. Saussurea costus has strong antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticancer, hepatoprotective, and antidiabetic qualities, according to pharmacological studies. The full realisation of its therapeutic potential is hampered by obstacles like a lack of standardised extraction techniques, a dearth of clinical studies, and conservation concerns brought on by habitat loss and overharvesting. Critical research gaps are likewise recognized in this education, for example the condition aimed at strong clinical validations, sophisticated mechanistic studies, and sustainable cultivation methods. Through the integration of current information and the resolution of these gaps, this learning leaves the basis for additional investigation and advancement of treatments based on Saussurea costus.

Keywords: Saussurea costus, medicinal plant, antibacterial, pharmacological studies.

OP 62

Exploring the anticancer potential of selected plant extracts: cytotoxic evaluation and partial purificationSona Ghosh¹, Kannan Vadakkadath Meethal²¹Department of Zoology, University of Calicut, Kerala, 673635²Department of Zoology, University of Calicut, Kerala, 673635

Abstract: Cancer remains one of the significant burdens on global health, with cancer incidence and mortality rates steadily increasing worldwide. Globally, Lung cancers cause most cancer deaths, exceeding the combined deaths from second and third ranking colorectal and pancreatic cancer. Several plant-derived molecules have successfully transitioned into clinical use, reinforcing the significance of natural products in the search for safer and effective anti-cancer drugs. The present study was conducted to evaluate the cytotoxic potential of five selected plant extracts against the human cancer cell lines HT-29, PANC-1 and MCF-7. Plant extracts were prepared by sequential extraction with organic solvents of increasing polarity (Petroleum ether, Chloroform, Ethyl acetate, Acetone and Methanol). Cytotoxicity was assessed by MTT assay after 24 and 48 hours of treatment and the IC₅₀ values were determined. Among the extracts tested, remove this plant as it is not used further) petroleum ether extract of *Lophopetalum wightianum* showed promising cytotoxicity with an IC₅₀ values of 9.45 µg/ml in PANC-1 cell line and 59.40 µg/ml in HT-29 cell line. Based on the promising activity, partial purification of the extract has been carried out using column chromatography. The resulting semi purified fraction also showed appreciable cytotoxicity with an IC₅₀ of 2.17 µg/ml in PANC-1 cell line and 23.28 µg/ml in HT-29 cell line. From this study, it can be concluded that the petroleum ether extract of *L.wightianum* has potential cytotoxic activity to PANC-1 cell line and HT-29. The results suggest that *L.wightianum* can be used as promising source for developing new anticancer drugs.

Keywords: Cancer, Medicinal plants, Cytotoxicity, Anticancer compounds.

OP 63

Time Series Analysis of Chronic Kidney Disease Prevalence and Dialysis Demand for Sustainable Healthcare Planning**Maria Samreen¹, Kumar Satyendra Yadav²**¹**Research Scholar, Department of Statistics Patna University, Patna – 800005**²**Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics Patna University, Patna – 800005**

Abstract: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) prevalence and dialysis demand in India have surged steadily over the past decade, propelled by rapid aging populations, escalating hypertension (HTN), diabetes mellitus (DM), and broader non-communicable disease (NCD) epidemics. These converging factors overwhelm India's strained healthcare infrastructure, which struggles with limited dialysis centers, workforce shortages, and uneven rural access. High-burden states like Bihar face acute challenges, where rural populations endure delayed diagnoses and 2.8-fold higher demand relative to urban Delhi, exacerbating mortality and economic burdens. This comprehensive time-series analysis synthesizes secondary data from National Family Health Surveys (NFHS-4/5, 2015-21), ICMR-INDIAB longitudinal studies (2014-22), and National Cancer Registry Programme (NCRP) dialysis registries (2012-24). Focusing on interstate variations in Delhi, Maharashtra, and Bihar, it employs Seasonal Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models incorporating HTN/DM covariates (correlation $r=0.87$). Complementary Granger causality tests assess DM/HTN drivers, while age-period-cohort decomposition disentangles temporal effects. Projections extend to 2035 using ARIMA forecasts validated against GBD trends. CKD prevalence climbed from 9.2% in 2015 to 14.8% in 2024 across analyzed regions, with projections reaching 18-22% by 2035. Bihar's rural dialysis demand exceeds Delhi's by 2.8-fold, driven by underserved populations and delayed diagnoses. Models yield Average Annual Percent Change (AAPC) of 3.2% for prevalence and 4.1% for dialysis initiations; DM incidence explains 68% of prevalence variance. Elderly (≥ 60 years) face 28% prevalence due to cohort NCD exposures. By 2030, India requires 1.2 million additional dialysis slots amid population growth. Policymakers should prioritize integrated NCD platforms merging NFHS with real-time hospital data, alongside mobile screening units and subsidized dialysis targeting high-burden areas like Bihar for equitable, sustainable healthcare.

Keywords: CKD time-series, ARIMA forecasting, dialysis demand, NFHS-INDIAB, healthcare planning.

OP 64

Analytical Modelling of Nonreciprocal Surface Magneto-Plasmons in Carbon Nanomaterials Embedded in a Non-Dispersive Dielectric Environment**Daya Shanker, Rashimi Yadav*****Department of Physics, University of Lucknow
Lucknow (UP), India, 226007**

Abstract: This paper investigates the propagation characteristics of surface magneto-plasmon polaritons (SMPPs) on the surface of carbon nanomaterials. Graphene/CNTs] interfaced with a non-dispersive dielectric medium. By applying an external static magnetic field B , we break the time-reversal symmetry, leading to nonreciprocal wave propagation. We derive the dispersion relation for the SMPPs using the semi-classical Drude-Lorentz model for the conductivity tensor. Our results demonstrate that the non-dispersive nature of the surrounding medium allows for a more stable confinement of the plasmonic mode compared to dispersive environments. Furthermore, we analyze the shift in the resonance frequency as a function of the cyclotron frequency ω_c . These findings provide a theoretical foundation for developing tunable, nonreciprocal THz devices and magneto-optical sensors. Surface magneto-plasmons (SMPs) in carbon nanomaterials offer a transformative approach to breaking time-reversal symmetry at the nanoscale. Here, we report an analytical model that elucidates the role of the dielectric environment in shaping nonreciprocal THz propagation. By embedding graphene in non-dispersive claddings, we demonstrate a tunable "one-way" electromagnetic window. Our findings provide a scalable platform for future topological photonic circuits and 6G communication modules.

Keywords: Graphene, Nonreciprocity, Surface Magneto-Plasmons, Terahertz, Dielectric Environment.

OP 65

Socio-Economic Vulnerabilities and Social Security Gaps Among Unorganized Sector Workers of Chikmagaluru, Rural Karnataka**Mandara SM****Research Scholar, Department of Management Studies
Shri Venkateshwara University**

Abstract: The unorganized (informal) sector dominates employment in rural Karnataka, encompassing agricultural laborers, construction workers, artisans, domestic helpers, and small-scale service providers. These workers, who constitute a major share of the rural workforce, face chronic challenges including low and irregular wages, lack of job security, long working hours, absence of formal contracts, limited access to healthcare, pensions, and other social protections. Gender disparities are pronounced, with women often engaged in low-paid, physically demanding roles such as farm labor and household work, compounded by lower literacy and skill levels. Despite national and state initiatives like the e-Shram portal registration, MGNREGA, and various welfare schemes, coverage remains uneven in rural areas, leaving many households vulnerable to economic shocks, health crises, and poverty traps. This study highlights key issues drawn from household-level realities, including income instability, migration for work, and inadequate enforcement of labor protections. It argues for strengthened policy interventions such as expanded social security nets, skill training programs, and better implementation of existing schemes to promote formalization, enhance livelihoods, and foster inclusive growth in rural Karnataka.

Keywords: Unorganized sectors, Rural Karnataka, Informal sectors, Gender disparities.

OP 66**Development of a Cooling Bag Using Garment Industrial Waste****M. A. Shelar¹, R.L. Gotipamul²****D.K.T. E's Textile and Engineering Institute, Ichalkaranji**

Abstract: The increasing accumulation of textile industrial waste poses serious environmental concerns due to landfill disposal, incineration, and the excessive use of non-biodegradable materials. At the same time, the growing demand for cooling bags for food, beverages, and temperature-sensitive products highlights the need for sustainable thermal insulation solutions. This study focuses on the development of a cooling bag using textile industrial waste as an alternative to conventional synthetic insulation materials. Waste denim fabric, discarded nonwoven carry bags, pulp sheets, and aluminum foil were selected based on their availability, fibrous structure, and thermal insulation potential. These materials were arranged into a multilayer composite structure designed to reduce heat transfer by conduction, convection, and radiation. The developed cooling bag was evaluated for temperature retention performance, structural stability, and functional usability under controlled conditions. The results demonstrate that textile-waste-based insulation can effectively slow heat gain and maintain internal cooling for a significant period. This research highlights the feasibility of upcycling textile waste into a functional, low-cost, and eco-friendly cooling bag, contributing to waste reduction, resource efficiency, and sustainable product development within a circular textile economy framework.

Keywords: Textile industrial waste, Cooling bag, Thermal insulation, Sustainable materials, Upcycling, Denim waste, Nonwoven fabrics, Eco-friendly product design

OP 67

Reconstructing misconceptions of parents about Intellectual Disability in community**Suaad Aziz¹ and Dr. Sanjay Kumar²**¹M.Ed. S.E (ID) Final Year, Department of Intellectual Disability, DSMNR University, Lucknow²Assistant Professor, Department of Intellectual Disability, DSMNR University, Lucknow**Abstract**

Background: Misconceptions deeply rooted lead to shaping individual beliefs and attitudes. The misconceptions about persons with intellectual disability are largely accepted by people without any scientific logic or knowledge. Misconceptions have to be reconstructed so as to avoid negative thinking and stigmatization.

Aims: The purpose of the present study was designed to know the misconception of parents about intellectual disability in one of the suburban areas in Lucknow and evaluate the impact of the awareness program on community attitudes.

Method: Using the NIMH–GEMS Questionnaire, data were collected from families having intellectual disabilities.

Results: The findings reveal a high prevalence of misconceptions related to karma, fate, black magic, and the curability of intellectual disability. All participants (100%) believed intellectual disability is caused by karma, black magic, or eclipse, and 90% of them believed it is a punishment for parents. The awareness program demonstrated positive improvement in community understanding, highlighting the need for sustained interventions, parental training, and policy-level support.

Keywords: Misconception, intellectual disability, parents, community.

OP 68**Solid Lipid Nanoparticles and Nanostructured Lipid Carriers as Advanced Nanoplatfoms for Breast Cancer Treatment****Kuhu****Department of Pharmacy****DIPSAR, Delhi Pharmaceutical Science and Research University, Delhi 110017**

Abstract: With its molecular subgroups displaying unique therapy responses and illness outcomes, breast cancer continues to be one of the most diverse and clinically difficult cancers. Conventional chemotherapy is frequently linked to poor selectivity and systemic side effects, despite notable advancements in treatment approaches. Lipid-based nanocarriers have drawn a lot of interest in this regard as cutting-edge medication delivery systems. An overview of lipid-based nanocarriers in oncology follows a discussion of breast cancer categorization with a focus on molecular subgroups. With an emphasis on their capacity to improve drug delivery and therapeutic efficacy, the potential of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) as promising nanoplatfoms for the treatment of breast cancer is critically investigated. Additionally, recent therapeutic uses of SLNs and NLCs in the treatment of breast cancer are emphasized. Additionally, recent therapeutic uses of SLNs and NLCs in the treatment of breast cancer are discussed. Lastly, the present difficulties and prospects for the advancement of lipid-based nanocarriers for the treatment of breast cancer are examined.

Keywords: Nanocarriers, oncology, Solid lipid Nanoparticles, Nanostructured lipid carriers, Nanoplatfoms, Breast cancer.

OP 69**Statistical Analysis of Spending on Food Delivery Apps****Ms. Manasi Sameer Sawant¹ and Mr .Sanjay Karande²**¹**TYBSc Student, Department of Statistics, Sathaye College (Autonomous)**²**Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Sathaye College (Autonomous)**

Abstract: The high growth rate of food delivery apps related to smartphone usage has created a significant impact in terms of the level at which expenditure takes place related to food expenditure in urban areas. The current study will be focused primarily on the analysis in terms of importance, related to usage, based on the information derived, with respect to the essential elements which define the level of expenditure based on the usage of food delivery apps related to certain specified factors. Primarily, the information has been derived based on a sample of 101, taken in accordance with a survey conducted online. The bivariate model has been derived based primarily on descriptive statistics, in accordance with information derived from the analysis, in order to assess the level at which food expenditure takes place in accordance with a specified frequency related to usage levels of a specified implicational platform. Further, a Chi-square test has been conducted in order to assess the relationship related to expenditure levels, incorporating different factors such as frequency, expenditure, etc.

These results show that the behavioural intensity variables, namely frequency of use of the app and spending per order, are highly significantly and positively related to average monthly spending, with $p < 0.001$. This gives an indication that repeated usage and increased orderlevel spending have strong impacts on higher cumulative monthly spending. However, delivery fee range and perceived influencing factors were not significantly related to monthly spending. In addition, the demographic variables had a limited effect on expenditure behaviour. The findings indicate that the factors pertaining to behavioural engagement result in more decisive judgements with regard to spending patterns compared to cost-related or demographic characteristics. The research offers empirical perceptions into spending behaviour of consumers within digital food-delivery ecosystems and develops an understanding of expenditure dynamics in app-based consumption environments.

Keywords: Food Delivery Apps, Spending Behaviour, Monthly Expenditure, Usage Patterns, Chi-square Analysis

OP 70

A Statistical Study on Consumer Behaviour towards Discounts and Coupons**Ms. Vaishnavi Nalawade¹ and Mr. Sanjay Karande²**¹**TYBSC Student, Department of Statistics, Sathaye College (Autonomous)**²**Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Sathaye College (Autonomous)**

Abstract: In today's competitive market, discounts and coupons have become a common part of everyday shopping. Consumers are surrounded by numerous brands, stores, and online platforms offering similar products which often vary in different prices. As a result, price-based promotions such as discounts and coupons play a significant role in influencing what people buy and how satisfied they feel after making a purchase. This study aims to understand how consumers feel about discounts and coupons and how these offers influence their buying decisions and satisfaction levels. A descriptive research approach was used for the study. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire from 100 respondents. The survey focused on understanding how often consumers use discounts, how these offers influence their spending behaviour, and how satisfied they are with such promotions. The data were analysed using descriptive analysis and the chi-square test to study the relationship between key variables. The findings show that many consumers have a positive attitude toward discounts and coupons, indicating that these offers encourage purchases. The results also reveal a significant relationship between how frequently consumers use discounts and their level of satisfaction. Overall, the study shows that discounts and coupons are effective marketing tools. However, they should be used carefully and ethically to maintain consumer trust and long-term satisfaction.

Keywords: Consumer Behaviour, Discounts and Coupons, Purchase Intention, Promotional Offers, Consumer Satisfaction.

OP 71

Blood sugar-controlled insulin delivery: Mechanisms, Technologies, and Future Direction**Shailya Preeti¹, Rahul Nishad², Dr. Pranab Kumar Mahata³ and
Rahul Kumar⁴**¹Department of microbiology, Radha Govind University Ramgarh, Jharkhand, India²Department of microbiology, Radha Govind University Ramgarh, Jharkhand, India³Department of microbiology, Radha Govind University Ramgarh, Jharkhand, India⁴Department of paramedical Sciences, Usha martin university, Ranchi, India

Abstract: Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease caused by regular making of hyperglycemia resulting from improper insulin secretion, insulin improper action. Traditional insulin therapy remains the primary treatment strategy for type 1 diabetes and type 2 diabetes and suffering from such as hypoglycemia, frequently using injections, and can't able to control the blood glucose (sugar) level. To control the difficulties in these challenges, blood sugar-controlled insulin delivery systems, also known as glucose-responsive system, have been developed. The system is designed to autonomously regulate insulin release in response to blood glucose levels, imitating pancreatic β -cell function. Different types of delivery platforms including enzyme-based systems, polymeric smart hydrogels, nanotechnology-driven carriers, and micro needle patches have shown promising results in preclinical and clinical studies. This review discusses the mechanisms, technologies, advantages, challenges, and future directions of glucose-responsive insulin delivery systems.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Glucose, Drug Delivery Systems, Insulin. Nanotechnology.

OP 72

Traditional Medicinal Plant Resources of North East India: A Sustainable Development and Utility of Healthcare Needs**Gargi Sharma****The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat, India**

Abstract: The North East India constitutes an important segment of the Indo-Burma biodiversity hotspot and is characterized by exceptional biological asset and deep-rooted ethno medicinal traditions. Indigenous and ethnic communities across the region have long relied on these medicinal plants as preventive and curative healthcare resources, particularly in the remote and rural landscapes where access to modern and formal medical infrastructure remains limited. However, rapid socio-cultural change, habitat loss and inadequate documentation threaten the continuity and effective utilization of these medicinal resources. Drawing upon the ethno botanical studies and global perspectives of sustainability, this study highlights the role of indigenous knowledge systems as affordable, culturally embedded and locally accessible healthcare alternatives. Medicinal plants not only support primary healthcare but also offer significant potential for livelihood generation and eco-friendly entrepreneurship when integrated with sustainable management practices. Despite their widespread use, limited scientific validation and integration into the modern practices have constrained the broader acceptance and systematic application of these traditional healthcare practices. Strategic integration of traditional knowledge with scientific research and policy frameworks can transform the traditional medicinal plant resources into a resilient and sustainable healthcare system.

Keywords: Traditional medicinal plants; Ethnobotany; Indigenous Knowledge Systems; Primary healthcare; North East India; Sustainable development.

OP 73

**Lessons from Multi-OMICS Approaches for Investigating Plant-Endophyte Interactions:
Is it time for revolution in Sustainable Agriculture?**Loveness¹, Sayanti Mandal^{1*}¹Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, School of Engineering & Sciences
Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India-201310

Abstract: Endophytes, encompassing bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, inhabit various plant tissues, establishing mutually beneficial associations and serving as a promising reservoir of natural compounds with medicinal potential. Despite progress, gaps persist in understanding endophytic biology and commercializing bioactive compounds. Endophytes also hold promise in bolstering plant resilience to environmental stresses, offering innovative solutions to mitigate climate change's agricultural impacts. Understanding plant-endophyte interactions is critical due to their dynamic nature across plant growth stages. Advancements in sequencing technologies enable comprehensive exploration of endophytic genomes, elucidating molecular mechanisms underlying these interactions. As worries about the negative effects of agrochemicals increase, there is a growing interest in utilizing endophytes as sustainable alternatives. Endophytic microorganisms are being used as bioinoculants to provide environmentally acceptable farming solutions. OMICS technologies are crucial in understanding plant-endophyte interactions. Multi-omics techniques combine genomic, transcriptomic, and metabolomic data to gain a more comprehensive understanding of biological systems and the regulatory networks that influence plant-microbe interactions. The utilization of this comprehensive method improves comprehension of how microbes mitigate stress and has potential applications in other fields of study. Ultimately, exploring and utilizing the relationships between plants and endophytes presents valuable opportunities for sustainable agriculture and medicinal research. The application of OMICS technology is crucial in understanding and unravelling the intricacies of these interactions.

Keywords: Endophytes, Genomics, Metabolomics, Next Generation Sequencing (NGS), Proteomics, Transcriptomics

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OP 74

A study of available family support for persons with intellectual disability in the community¹Anshika Tiwari, ²Dr Sanjay Kumar¹MED SE (ID) Final Year, Department of Intellectual Disability, DSMNRU, Lucknow³Assistant Professor, Department of Intellectual Disability, DSMNR University, Lucknow**Abstract**

Background: In India, informal support services are backbone of entire rehabilitation process of children with intellectual disability. Caregiving for persons with intellectual disability is predominantly family based, with parents, siblings, grand-parents and extended relatives forming the core support group. Despite policy advances and disability legislation, formal support services remain limited, unevenly distributed, and often inaccessible, especially in rural and semi-urban areas. It is important to understand that families having children with intellectual disability are often isolated, stigmatized and marginalized in community (Murthy, 2025). Consequently, informal support services play a critical role in caregiving and promoting wellbeing of persons with intellectual disability.

Aim & objective: The main objective of the study was to assess available support; quantum of support being utilized and their satisfaction level with support being received by the families having children with intellectual disability in chosen community.

Method: The methodology used in the present study was field survey to identify various sources and quantum of support available in the family having children with intellectual disability in the selected community.

Results: All families in the study were utilizing support of mother (100%), followed by fathers (40%), paternal grand-mother (30%), paternal grand- father (20%), siblings (20%), paternal aunt/uncle (20%) and maternal grand-mother (10). Six families having children with intellectual disability were satisfied with support and four families were not satisfied with support available in the family.

Key Words: Family support, Intellectual disability, informal support.

OP 75

In Vitro Anti-Cancer Activity of CS/PVA Hydrogel Incorporating *Zaleya pentandra* Extract against Lung Cancer Cell Line

Deepika A

Department of Biochemistry, Saveetha Medical College, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India**Abstract**

Background: Lung cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) accounting for nearly 85% of all cases. Conventional chemotherapy is often associated with systemic toxicity and drug resistance, highlighting the need for safer and more effective therapeutic strategies. Natural plant-derived bioactives, when combined with biocompatible delivery systems, offer a promising alternative. *Zaleya pentandra*, rich in flavonoids and phenolic compounds, possesses notable anticancer potential. Chitosan (CS) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogels provide an efficient platform for sustained drug delivery.

Materials and Methods: A CS/PVA hydrogel incorporated with *Zaleya pentandra* extract was developed using a freeze-thaw method. The hydrogel was characterized for homogeneity and functional group interactions using FTIR analysis. In vitro anticancer activity was evaluated against the human lung cancer cell line A549. Cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay following 24 h treatment with varying concentrations of the extract-loaded hydrogel. Morphological alterations and apoptosis induction were examined using bright-field microscopy and fluorescence staining (AO/EtBr and DAPI).

Results: FTIR analysis confirmed the successful incorporation of *Zaleya pentandra* phytoconstituents into the CS/PVA hydrogel matrix. The extract-loaded hydrogel exhibited a significant, dose-dependent reduction in A549 cell viability compared to the crude extract alone. The IC_{50} value was notably lower for the hydrogel formulation, indicating enhanced anticancer efficacy. Fluorescence microscopy

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revealed characteristic apoptotic features, including nuclear condensation and membrane integrity loss, confirming apoptosis induction in treated cells.

Conclusion: The findings demonstrate that a CS/PVA hydrogel incorporated with *Zaleya pentandra* extract exhibits significant *in vitro* anticancer activity against lung cancer cells. The hydrogel system enhances the bioavailability and sustained release of phytochemicals, leading to improved cytotoxic efficacy and apoptosis induction. This biopolymer-based herbal hydrogel shows strong potential as a safe and effective therapeutic approach for lung cancer management, warranting further *in vivo* and mechanistic investigations.

OP 76

Biogenic Silver Nanoparticles Synthesized from Sprouted *Trigonella* Seeds Exhibit Dual Antioxidant and Anti-Diabetic Activities

Dr. KALAIARASLS

II YR PG

MD (Biochemistry)

Abstract:

Introduction: Green synthesis of nanoparticles using plant-based resources has gained significant attention due to its eco-friendly, cost-effective, and sustainable nature. *Trigonella foenum-graecum* (fenugreek) is known for its rich phytochemical profile and anti-diabetic properties. This study aims to synthesize silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using sprouted fenugreek seed extract and to evaluate their antioxidant and anti-diabetic potential.

Materials and Methods: Sprouted *Trigonella foenum-graecum* seeds were used to prepare an aqueous extract, which served as a reducing and stabilizing agent for the biogenic synthesis of AgNPs. The formation of nanoparticles was confirmed by UV–Visible spectroscopy. Structural and functional characterization was performed using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscopy. Antioxidant activity was evaluated using DPPH, ABTS, and FRAP assays. The in vitro anti-diabetic potential was assessed through α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibition assays.

Results: UV–Visible analysis showed characteristic surface plasmon resonance peaks confirming AgNP formation. FTIR analysis indicated the presence of bioactive functional groups involved in nanoparticle stabilization, while XRD confirmed their crystalline nature. The synthesized AgNPs exhibited significant, concentration-dependent antioxidant activity across all assays. Furthermore, AgNPs demonstrated notable inhibitory effects against α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes, indicating strong anti-diabetic potential.

Discussion: The enhanced antioxidant and anti-diabetic activities of the biogenic AgNPs may be attributed to the synergistic interaction between silver nanoparticles and phytochemicals present in the sprouted fenugreek seed extract. These findings suggest that plant-mediated AgNPs could

serve as promising nano-therapeutic agents for managing oxidative stress and diabetes, supporting the potential application of green nanotechnology in biomedical research.

OP 77

Vision Meets Language: An Image Captioning Framework Using Deep Learning¹Ishu Pandey, ²Anuradha Misra¹Amity School of Engineering Technology, Amity University Lucknow, 226028²Amity School of Engineering Technology, Amity University Lucknow, 226028

Abstract: The project “Vision Meets Language: An Image Captioning Framework Using Deep Learning” explores the intersection of computer vision and natural language processing (NLP) to automatically generate descriptive captions for images. Image captioning is a complex task that requires understanding both the visual content of an image and the linguistic structure necessary to express that understanding in natural language. This project presents a deep learning–based framework that combines convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for image feature extraction and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), specifically Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, for generating coherent textual descriptions. Large volumes of visual data are produced every second in the current digital era by social media platforms, smartphones, and cameras. In the past, machines have had difficulty deciphering images in a meaningful, human-like manner, despite the fact that images can frequently convey rich information at a glance. One step in closing the gap between computer vision and natural language processing is the ability to both “see” and “describe” visual content. The intriguing field of image captioning, in which a system automatically creates textual descriptions for an image, was born out of this intersection. The way we engage with digital media could be completely changed by such technology, which could lead to new developments in search engines, accessibility, education, and even healthcare. The increasing significance of making visual information comprehensible to both people and robots is what inspired this effort. By describing what is happening in a picture, automated captioning can provide those with visual impairments with richer digital experiences. News organizations may automate the labeling and summarizing of visual material, while e-commerce platforms can gain from more detailed product descriptions.

Keywords: dataset, CNN, RNN, LSTM, BLEU, machine learning, deep learning, gate, transformer, caption, NLP, generator, preprocessing, tokenization.

OP 78

Body Fat Distribution Index (BFDI): A Novel Adiposity Marker for Identifying Metabolic Syndrome in Adults at a Tertiary Care Hospital

Anu Aksharaa JP

Department of Biochemistry, Saveetha medical college

Abstract

Background: Metabolic syndrome (MetS) is a constellation of interrelated cardiometabolic abnormalities including central obesity, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and insulin resistance, substantially increasing the risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus. Conventional anthropometric indices such as body mass index (BMI) and waist–hip ratio (WHR), though widely used, have limitations in accurately reflecting visceral fat distribution and its metabolic impact. The Body Fat Distribution Index (BFDI) has emerged as a novel, simple, and cost-effective anthropometric marker designed to better assess central adiposity.

Aim and Objectives: This study aimed to compare BFDI values between individuals with metabolic syndrome and healthy controls and to evaluate the association of BFDI with components of metabolic syndrome.

Materials and Methods: A hospital-based comparative study was conducted at Saveetha Medical College Hospital between January 2025 and March 2025 after obtaining institutional ethical clearance. A total of 128 adults aged 30–70 years were enrolled, comprising 64 metabolic syndrome cases and 64 controls, selected based on NCEP ATP III criteria. Individuals with chronic illnesses such as chronic kidney disease, cardiovascular disease, malignancy, and pregnant women were excluded. Anthropometric measurements including height, weight, waist circumference, hip circumference, BMI, and WHR were recorded. BFDI was calculated using the formula: $BFDI = ([\text{waist circumference}/\text{height in meters}] + [1/\text{height in meters}]) \times \text{WHR}$. Statistical analysis was performed to compare variables and assess diagnostic performance using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis.

Results: Weight, BMI, waist circumference, hip circumference, WHR, and BFDI were significantly higher in metabolic syndrome cases compared to controls ($p < 0.01$). The mean BFDI was 66.1 ± 16.6 in cases and 56.2 ± 5.4 in controls. ROC curve analysis demonstrated

strong discriminatory ability of BFDI with an area under the curve of 0.818 (95% CI: 0.756–0.879; $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: BFDI demonstrated strong diagnostic performance and a significant association with metabolic syndrome, highlighting its potential as a reliable and practical anthropometric marker for identifying individuals at risk. Its simplicity and effectiveness make BFDI a valuable tool for clinical and public health screening of metabolic syndrome.

OP 79

Effect of Rutin Trihydrate on metal induced stress

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Abstract: Heavy metal exposure remains an essential toxicological threat through their ability to perform redox reactions and interfere with the cellular function. In this study, we tested the potential of Rutin Trihydrate against copper-induced cellular toxicity using *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* as the model organism. It is a commonly used eukaryotic organism to study cellular phenomena and interactions. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was grown on media enriched with YPD supplemented either with copper sulfate or Rutin alone and together to study the growth kinetics and morphology in order to test its potential to counter cellular stress caused by copper. The study showed a significant decrease in cell viability with the increase in concentration to 600 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; Rutin supplementation showed better growth performance compared to cultures grown only on copper sulfate solutions. It was observed through microscopic study, there was less stress observed on the cell surface after treatment with Rutin solutions. The study on DPPH assay was not conclusive owing to difficulties observed in extracting a consistent quantity of cell derived proteins; it is concluded from the study conducted on Rutin Trihydrate that Rutin holds a potential to moderate cellular stress and resulting cellular toxicity if copper compounds were to act similarly on biological systems.

Keywords: Rutin trihydrate, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, copper toxicity, oxidative stress, flavonoids, antioxidant protection, metal-induced stress.

OP 80

Hydrothermal synthesis of WS₂ nanosheets on reduced graphene oxide for highly sensitive simultaneous detection of heavy metals**S. Arjun⁴, U. Suresh³, P. Margaret Sangeetha² and Dr. C. Balalakshmi^{1*}**^{1*}Assistant Professor, Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Alagappa University, Karaikudi²Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, The American College Madurai³AURF Project Fellows, Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Alagappa University, Karaikudi⁴Ind M.Sc, Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Alagappa University, Karaikudi

Abstract: The accumulation of heavy metals in foods and drinking water has presented a significant risk to human health, underscoring the importance of devising a portable and cost-effective method for detecting heavy metals. Thus, we have developed an ultrasensitive non-faradaic electrochemical sensor based on using engineered two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterial heterostructures integrated on interdigitated microelectrode arrays, enabling the simultaneous quantification of Cd²⁺ and Hg²⁺. The 2D-HRGO/WS₂ with doping Mn/Mg/Fe/C nano-particles material prepared in this study was characterized by characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Raman spectroscopy and field emission transmission electron microscopy (FETEM). In addition, the device was characterized by cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Compared between the bare and doing layer showed a significantly higher activity for anodic stripping analysis of the four considered heavy metal ions; in particular, the Fe peak current enhancement was about 1.5 times higher for Hg²⁺. Moreover, this study provides a potential material for electrochemical detection of heavy metal ions, individually or simultaneously.

Keywords:**Acknowledgment:**

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OP 81

Sodium tungstate–graphene nanocomposite for simultaneous and individual electrochemical detection of heavy metal ions**P. Viram⁴, U. Suresh³, P. Margaret Sangeetha² and Dr. C. Balalakshmi^{1*}**^{1*}Assistant Professor, Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Alagappa University, Karaikudi² Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, The American College Madurai³AURF Project Fellows, Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Alagappa University, Karaikudi⁴Ind M.Sc, Department of Nanoscience and Technology, Alagappa University, Karaikudi

Abstract: Aggravated by human and industrial activities, heavy metal pollution has become a severe problem, causing widespread concern in society, and cannot be ignored. Herein, a reduced graphene nanoparticle (WS₂NPs/rGO) was proposed and synthesized by electrochemical methods. Based on the WS₂NPs/rGO hybrid, a novel electrochemical sensing platform was established and successfully applied for the selective, quantitative detection of Hg²⁺ and Cd²⁺ taking advantage of the well-established anodic stripping voltammetry (ASV). This hybrid material not only increases the surface area and charge transfer rate but also provides more active sites for Hg deposition due to the formation of homogeneous, high density and monodispersed WS₂NPs on the rGO film. LOD for Hg²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions were found to be 4.7x10⁻¹⁰ M and 3.8x10⁻¹⁰ M for individual detection and 2.3x10⁻¹⁰ M and 2.8x10⁻¹⁰ M, for simultaneous detection, respectively. The selectivity and stability of the as-prepared electrode were investigated and showed promising results. In addition, a screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) was also employed to verify the practical application ability of our assay with an excellent performance, which presents a bright application prospect for *in situ* Hg²⁺ detection.

Keywords: Graphene oxide, Sodium tungstate, Hydrothermal synthesis, Heavy metal, Electrochemical

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been great support and help to me in writing this Work. So I have included AURF acknowledgment in this abstract.

OP 82

Comparative Study of Hypertensive Disorders of Pregnancy with Normotensive Pregnancies through Evaluation of Coagulation Profile and Platelet Count**¹Yusra Jamal, ²Sayeedul Hasan Arif *, ³Mahboob Hasan, ⁴Zehra Mohsin****1 Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, J N Medical College and Hospital, AMU, Aligarh****2 Professor, Department of Pathology, J N Medical College and Hospital, AMU, Aligarh****3 Professor, Department of Pathology, J N Medical College and Hospital, AMU, Aligarh****4 Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, J N Medical College and Hospital, AMU, Aligarh*****Corresponding author Email: arif.pa@amu.ac.in, sharifpatho@gmail.com****Abstract**

Pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) is the major cause of maternal and fetal mortality and morbidity and it contributes to 16% of mortality in pregnant mothers in developed and developing countries. Aim of this study was to estimate, evaluate and compare platelet count, prothrombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), D-Dimer and fibrinogen levels in patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy with normotensive pregnancies and further correlate the derangements in platelet count, PT, APTT, D-Dimer and fibrinogen levels with the clinical outcomes. For this a prospective case control study was conducted for two years in the Department of Pathology, JNMCH, AMU on total 128 pregnant females comprising of diagnosed cases of PIH and normal pregnant females were taken as controls. Platelet count, PT, APTT, D-Dimer and fibrinogen levels in 128 pregnant females (31 Severe Preeclampsia (BP above 160/110 mmHg), 37 Non-Severe Preeclampsia (BP ranges between 140/90 mmHg and 160/110 mmHg), and 60 Normal Pregnant Females) were evaluated and then correlated with the clinical outcomes. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by post hoc Scheffe test has been used for statistical analysis. In this study, the mean platelet count significantly decreases while mean D-Dimer significantly increases with increasing severity of PIH. The mean PT, mean APTT and mean fibrinogen levels for the severe PIH group were significantly higher as compared to non-severe PIH and normal pregnancy groups. Statistical difference was not significant between the normal pregnancy group and the non-severe PIH group. Maternal and

Fetal complications are more common with severe PIH, decreased platelet count and deranged coagulation profile. Therefore this study concludes that platelet count and D-dimer levels can be used to monitor the progression of pregnancy-induced hypertension and raised PT, APTT and fibrinogen levels are fairly good indicators of severe pregnancy-induced hypertension.

Keywords: PIH, Platelet count, PT, APTT, D-Dimer, Fibrinogen.

Declarations

Funding: No external funding was received for this study.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

OP 83

CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing in fruit crops: Steps towards improving fruit traits and ensuring food security**Ramsha Syed¹, Deepak Kumar Upadhyay¹, Ansu Chetri¹, Sayanti Mandal^{1*}**¹Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Sharda School of Basic Sciences & Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India**Abstract**

Fruits form a significant part of a regular healthy human diet, having significant role in maintaining a systematic immune system. Fruit crops provide a diverse array of nutrients and beneficial metabolites that are advantageous to human health. But Fruit quality and quantity are susceptible to numerous environmental stresses. Previously many approaches have been applied to enhance the traits in fruits and to stabilise the production, unfortunately leading to significant drawbacks and no evident result. As the global population is escalating aggressively, the demand for more food is expected and should remain a priority. Modern solutions are required to curb the growing tension concerning food and a stable supply of fruits as well. Due to advanced fruit genomics and readily available genome sequences, the progress of genome editing techniques like clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)/CRISPR-associated protein9 (Cas9) makes it easier to augment, enhance, and knockout key traits. In order to improve the quality and production of fruits, this review attempts to provide readers a thorough grasp of the possible uses of CRISPR technology. Moreover, CRISPR/Cas9 holds boundless potential as an advanced tool to handle many aspects of growing scientific problems.

Key words: CRISPR; precision editing; ribonucleoprotein; fruit quality; nutritional quality;

OP 84

Comparative Analysis of Vitamin D and Heart Rate Variability in Hypertensive Subjects and Normotensive Individuals with a Family History of Hypertension¹Shilpi Bhat, ²Shobitha Muthukrishnan¹PhD scholar, Department of Physiology, SMS&R, Sharda University, Greater Noida, U.P²Professor, Department of Physiology, SMS&R, Sharda University, Greater Noida, U.P

Essential hypertension is a multifactorial disorder with a strong genetic component. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) that represents the balance of the cardiovascular system via ANS control is an established tool in cardiology studies. Research documents the association of Vitamin D deficiency and HRV in hypertension. However, very few studies have explored the association between vitamin D and cardiac autonomic function in healthy people. This study aims to evaluate and compare serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] levels and cardiac autonomic function in hypertensive patients and normotensive offspring of hypertensive parents.

Methods: 120 participants aged 18-60 years participated in this cross-sectional analytical study. ELISA was used to measure serum 25(OH)D levels. RMS Polyrite software was used to measure short-term HRV. Frequency-domain (LF/HF ratio) and time-domain (SDNN, RMSSD, PNN50%) metrics were examined. 25(OH)D levels and HRV parameters among the three groups: A (hypertensives), Group B (normotensive with a family history of hypertension), and Group C (normotensive without a family history of hypertension) were compared.

Results: Mean serum 25(OH)D levels were higher in Group A (20.93 ± 6.14 ng/mL) compared to Group B (13.92 ± 6.87 ng/mL) and Group C (16.04 ± 9.00 , $p=0.00017$) However, after controlling for Age and Gender no difference in 25(OH)D levels between the groups was found ($p=0.698$). Even after adjusting for Age and Gender, Group C showed significantly higher SDNN, RMSSD, PNN50) compared to the Hypertensive and Family History groups at ($p=0.0001$). The LF/ HF ratio in Family History group was closer to the Hypertensives (2.58 ± 0.69 , 2.62 ± 0.70) displaying early signs of sympathovagal imbalance.

Conclusion: Autonomic dysfunction may be early markers of hypertensive risk in genetically predisposed individuals, warranting early screening and lifestyle intervention. Vitamin D deficiency is linked to overall HRV but its levels are more affected by gender and sex rather than the disease condition.

Keywords: Hypertension, Heart Rate Variability, Vitamin D Deficiency, Familial Predisposition, Autonomic Dysfunction.

OP 85

Citation Analysis of Ph.D. Theses: A Comprehensive Overview**¹Mr. Digvijaysinh Anil Pawar and ²Dr. Sachin Suryawanshi**Research Scholar, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), and Pune, Yashwantrao
Mohite College of Arts, Science and CommerceResearch Guide, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Pune Abhijit Kadam Institute of
Management and Social Sciences**Abstract**

Citation analysis of Ph.D. theses provides a unique lens to examine scholarly communication, research impact, and knowledge dissemination in academia. Unlike journal articles, theses are extensive, often unpublished works that serve as a foundation for early-career researchers. This paper offers an overview of citation analysis applied to doctoral dissertations, exploring its methodologies, purposes, key findings, and inherent challenges. It examines how thesis citations differ from other publications, their role in measuring research influence, and their utility for collection development, accreditation, and understanding disciplinary trends. The analysis reveals that while thesis citation data is valuable for assessing local and specialized impact, it is often underrepresented in traditional bibliometric databases. The paper concludes by discussing future directions, including the integration of institutional repositories and altmetrics.

Keywords: Citation Analysis, Ph.D. Theses, Doctoral Dissertations, Bibliometric, Research Impact, Scholarly Communication

OP 86

Clinical and laboratory profile of scrub typhus cases detected by RT PCR among adult febrile patients in a tertiary care hospital, Vellore, South India**C.Chandraleka^{1*}**, M.Bhaskar¹, V.Sathi², M.Lavanya³, S.Priyadarshini³¹Department of Microbiology, Government Vellore Medical College, Vellore -632011, Tamil Nadu, India.²Department of General Medicine, Government Vellore Medical College, Vellore -632011, Tamil Nadu, India.³Department of Microbiology, Chettinad Academy of Research and Education, Chennai-603103, Tamil Nadu, India.

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Background:

Scrub typhus is an emerging and tropically neglected Rickettsial disease caused by an intracellular gram negative bacterium, *Orientia tsutsugamushi* transmitted by accidental bite of chigger stage trombiculid mites. It generally manifests from mild acute febrile illness to severe complications like multi-organ failure.

Objective: To analyze the clinical, and laboratory features of scrub typhus cases detected by RT PCR in acute febrile illness patients.

Methods: This prospective study was conducted at Government Vellore Medical College, Vellore, and Tamilnadu. Duration of study period was three months. Totally 240 hospitalized adult patients with acute febrile illness were included. About 4 ml of blood samples were collected and transferred 2ml in plain tubes and 2 ml in EDTA coated tubes. Separated serum samples from plain tubes were tested for scrub typhus IgM antibodies using ELISA kit. DNA was extracted using Buffy coat from 45 ELISA positive EDTA blood samples and subjected to RT PCR.

Results: In this present study, 240 samples were tested for scrub typhus IgM antibodies. Out of which 92(38%) were IgM ELISA positive in which 47(51%) were females and 45(49%) males. 29(64%) cases were positive by RT PCR out of 45 ELISA positive samples. Most common clinical manifestations were fever, vomiting, abdominal pain, headache, cough, chills, rigor, myalgia, breathlessness and noted complications were ARDS, Transaminitis and Meningoencephalitis.

Conclusion: Early diagnosis of cases provide better treatment and reduce risk of complications and mortality rate.

OP 87

Quantum Computing Materials: Unlocking the Potential of Quantum Information Processing**Dr. Mukesh Kumar (Prof.&Head)****Dept.of Physics, Shivpati PG College Shoharatgarh Siddharthnagar (U.P.)****Abstract:**

Quantum computing materials are a class of novel materials that exhibit quantum mechanical properties, enabling the manipulation and control of quantum information. Recent breakthroughs in the discovery of materials like cobalt-based molecules with metal-metal bonds have shown promise as spin qubits, a fundamental unit for future quantum computers. This review highlights the current state of quantum computing materials, including superconductors, topological insulators, and quantum dots. We discuss the challenges and opportunities associated with the design, synthesis, and characterization of these materials, as well as their potential applications in quantum computing, quantum communication, and quantum simulation. The development of quantum computing materials is crucial for harnessing the power of quantum information processing and transforming the field of computing.

Keywords: Quantum computing, quantum materials, spin qubits, superconductors, topological insulators, quantum dots.

OP 88**An analytical study on effectiveness of training programme conducted at Kirloskar Ferrous Industries Limited, Solapur”**

¹ Dr. Ganraj S. Mane (Assistant Professor), ² Ms. Ms. Karuna K. Devar (MBA Student),
Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Abhijit Kadam institute of Management and Social Sciences,
Solapur

Kirloskar Ferrous Industries Limited (KFIL), Solapur, believes in continuous improvement and emphasizes employee's development as key factor in achieving productivity, quality, and innovation. The organization has implemented various training and development programs to enhance employee skills, knowledge, and performance. Training and development are essential component of organizational growth and employee performance improvement. Effective training not only equips employees with the required knowledge and skills but also ensures that these are applied productively in their day-to-day tasks. The effectiveness of training refers to the extent to which training objectives are met, employee's skills and competencies are enhanced, and organizational performance improves as a result. Measuring training effectiveness helps identify strengths, areas of improvement, and ensures that resources are being utilized efficiently. It should establish the importance of practical, hands-on training for skill development and career readiness, define training effectiveness as the successful application of learned skills in the workplace, and state the study's objective to evaluate the effectiveness of specific training program, potentially using frameworks like the Kirkpatrick Model to measure learning, behavior changes, and results. The researcher thus, aims to study the effectiveness of training programme conducted at Kirloskar Ferrous Industries Limited, Solapur.

Keywords: Training, Employee skills, Effectiveness, Behavior change, performance

OP 89**Artificial Intelligence (AI) Governance in India: A Global Perspective****K. Ravinder Reddy, PhD Scholar****The School of Law, Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar - Delhi G.T. Road,
Phagwara, Punjab (India) 144411****Abstract:**

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has taken over the world and influenced multiple disciplines, including healthcare, Education, public administration and agriculture, reshaping economies of every nation. This AI-driven innovation did have significant benefits, but it raises ethical, legal, moral, and human rights concerns, including algorithmic bias, transparency, data privacy, and accountability, sparking global debates over AI regulation and research examines India's AI governance landscape through a comparative analysis of the EU, the USA, and China, with the objective of developing a rights-based, context-specific, innovation-friendly regulatory framework for India.

The research was conducted using doctrinal, legal, and qualitative comparative methodologies, drawing on scholarly articles, legislative policy documents, regulatory institutions, and case studies. The EU's AI regulation is risk-based, grounded in the binding AI Act and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which emphasise human rights, transparency, and accountability. The US fragmented framework is dispersed, sector-specific, voluntary, and accountability-driven by competitiveness and Innovation and overseen by the Federal Trade Commission. On the other hand, China has a state-centric, security-oriented AI governance framework, with comprehensive regulatory oversight of generative AI, deepfakes, and algorithmic systems shaped by collective values, national security priorities, and strong state oversight.

As India lacks a binding AI regulatory framework, the rapid AI adoption based on economic growth is formally based on policy-driven initiatives and largely voluntary, incorporating existing policy wording from the National Strategy for AI and Responsible AI, which prompts regulatory gaps in areas such as legality, data protection, algorithmic fairness and institutional enforcement. The study underscores India's institutional, political, and socio-economic dichotomy, which further complicates the direct implementation of foreign AI regulatory

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models, requiring India to formulate a hybrid, adaptive AI governance framework that incorporates the EU's risk-based approach, the US's sectoral flexibility and China's regulatory clarity while remaining anchored in India's constitutional and democratic values. The paper adds to legal literature on technology governance by providing normative guidelines for developing a balanced, rights-oriented, innovation-compatible AI regulatory framework suited to the Indian context.

Keywords: India, Comparative AI regulation, AI regulation, Human Rights, Technology law.

OP 90

Computational Investigation of Self-Healing Concrete Structures: Finite Element Analysis and Artificial Neural Networks study**Kanagaraj. K¹, Suresh Kumar. P²****¹Research Scholar, Dept. Of Civil Engineering, University College of Engineering (A Constituent College of Anna University, Chennai), Panruti, 607106, Tamil Nadu, India.****²Professor, Dept. Of Civil Engineering, University College of Engineering (A Constituent College of Anna University, Chennai), Panruti, 607106, Tamil Nadu, India.**

Abstract: The durability and service life of concrete structures are significantly limited by the crack-induced deterioration. Without any external repair, the self-healing structures provide a promising solution by allowing partial or complete recovery of mechanical properties. In this work, the self-healing structures are numerically investigated using finite element analysis (FEA) and artificial neural networks (ANN). A concrete beam model is developed using ANSYS Workbench, and the damage is numerically simulated by considering stiffness degradation, and the healing is characterized by the recovery of elastic modulus governed by the efficiency of healing parameters. To evaluate the influence of crack width, healing efficiency, stiffness recovery, and loading conditions on structural response, a comprehensive parametric study is conducted using numerical analysis. The simulated numerical results are utilized to train a supervised ANN model to accurately predict the strength and stiffness recovery. The combined approach of FEA and ANN provides an effective self-healing mechanism for the enhancement of structural parameters for sustainable infrastructure application.

Keywords: Self-healing concrete, Damage recovery, Stiffness degradation, Finite element analysis, Artificial neural network.

OP 91**Sustainable Endodontics: Route to root for ecofriendly practice****Dr.Pooja Kabra****Department of Conservative dentistry and endodontics,****SDS, Sharda University, Greater Noida****Corrospounding Email: pooja.kabra@sharda.ac.in****Abstract:**

Where the world has made a shift towards sustainability, all branches in dental industry including endodontics adapts to environmentally conscious practice. The environmental impact in dentistry involves substantial waste generation and energy consumption which gives dental professionals an alarm to adapt sustainable practice in endodontics benefiting both the environment and patient's health. Endodontics is a branch in dentistry which demands both precision and sterility for a promising treatment prognosis. Opting sustainable practice can minimize environmental footprints without compromising patient care. Incorporation of digital technologies like CBCT, implementation of waste segregation and recycling protocols in clinic, choosing biocompatible and biodegradable materials as alternatives during treatment, optimizing energy consumption with LED lights and energy efficient equipment can maintain high standards of patient care by reducing their ecological impact. This paper presentation not just explores on implementing ecofriendly approach in endodontics focusing on reducing waste, conserving resources and promoting sustainable materials but also provides awareness to dental professionals for their crucial role in a sustainable endodontic practice

Keywords: environmental impact, endodoncs, digital technologies, sustainable materials

OP 92

A Comparative Study of Poisson and Negative Binomial Regression Models for Analyzing HIV/AIDS Transmission Risk Factors**¹SUJATHA INGINSHETTY, ²ANAND B S***¹Department of Statistics, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi-585106, India.²Faculty of Business Studies, Sharnbasva University, Kalaburagi-585102, India.**Abstract**

HIV/AIDS continues to pose a major public health challenge in India, with pronounced regional variation in transmission patterns and mortality. Robust statistical modelling of HIV/AIDS-related count data is essential for identifying key risk factors and informing targeted interventions. This study presents a comparative analysis of Poisson and Negative Binomial regression models to examine demographic and transmission-related determinants of HIV/AIDS mortality in the Kalyana Karnataka region of Karnataka, India. The analysis uses aggregated count data obtained from Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) centers across seven districts for the period 2005–2023, stratified by age group, gender, and mode of transmission.

Results from the Poisson regression model indicate that age, gender, and transmission route significantly influence HIV/AIDS mortality, with higher risk observed among individuals aged 30–36 years, males, and those infected through heterosexual contact, mother-to-child transmission, and female sex workers. However, diagnostic measures reveal substantial overdispersion in the data, violating the equidispersion assumption of the Poisson model. To address this limitation, a Negative Binomial regression model was fitted, which incorporates an additional dispersion parameter.

The Negative Binomial model demonstrates superior performance, evidenced by lower deviance and Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values, and provides more reliable standard errors and confidence intervals. Findings from this model confirm the dominance of heterosexual transmission and male vulnerability in HIV/AIDS mortality, while older age groups exhibit significantly lower mortality incidence. Overall, the study highlights the importance of appropriate model selection for overdispersed epidemiological data and supports the use of Negative Binomial regression for reliable inference and effective public health planning in regional HIV/AIDS control programs.

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Keywords: HIV/AIDS mortality, Poisson regression, Negative Binomial regression, overdispersion, transmission risk factors.

OP 93

Synthesis Of [^{68}Ga]Triazine Linked With Glu-Ureido Targeting PSMA as TheranosticsMohd. Faheem^{1,2}, Manish Dixit^{2*}, Manisha Prasad^{1*}

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2. Department of Nuclear Medicine, Sanjay Gandhi Postgraduate Institute of Medical Sciences, Lucknow, UP, India.

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The second leading cause of death for males is prostate cancer, which affects one in eight men. A protein that the prostate-specific antigen targets is the prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA). Prostate cancer can be identified using the PSA protein, which is encoded by the PSA gene and is present in the blood, semen, and urine. PSMA has been identified as a molecular target for prostate cancer by a number of types of theranostic ligands. These theranostics use radioisotope emission characteristics linked to the ligand to target PSMA. Lately, PSMA ligands have been utilised to treat/diagnose patients with prostate cancer as theranostics integrated with therapeutic treatment.

The present work aims to synthesize triazine-linked Glu-Ureido-based scaffolds by the reported method of Maresca et al., with slight modifications via the coupling of di-tert-butyl glutamic acid ester with Cbz-Lys-O(t-Bu). Followed by the removal of Cbz-group under reduction condition to yield triazine linked Glu-Ureido scaffolds in good yield. These intermediates were used to synthesize triazine-linked Glu-Ureido-based PSMA biomarkers, which are assessed for biological potential. The synthesized compounds were analyzed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectroscopy and other analytical tools. These scaffolds will be radiolabelled and their efficacy will be explored both via *in-vitro* and *in vivo* study.

Keywords: PSMA, Glu-urea, prostate cancer, prostate-specific antigen

OP 94

Microgreens and Phytoremediation Matrices for Atmospheric Particulate Matter**Dr.Soni Singh****Department of Botany, B.S.N.V.P.G College,Lucknow-226001,UP,India**

Abstract: Atmospheric particulate matter (PM) is a persistent environmental stressor. This is due to its chemically heterogeneous nature, extended atmospheric residence time, and significant ecological and health consequences. This work elucidates microgreens as dominant bioactive regulators at the plant–atmosphere interface. They govern the interception, transformation, and environmental fate of airborne particulate matter. Accordingly, phytoremediation is an efficient biological conduit. Phyllosphere microbial mediation is a primary regulator that accentuates microgreen functionality.

Microgreens have structural and physiological traits that aid PM interception. Their high surface-area-to-biomass ratios, permeable and chemically active cuticles, and rapid growth speed make interception swift and efficient. Following deposition, the microgreen phyllosphere supports specialised microbial consortia. These consortia mediate particulate transformation through adsorption, metal immobilisation, organic degradation, and redox-regulated detoxification. Microbial processes work with plant antioxidant defences and secondary metabolite biosynthesis. Together, they lower particulate bioaccessibility and stabilise leaf-surface chemistry.

Short cultivation cycles and frequent harvesting further boost remediation efficiency. This allows continuous removal of particulate loads and reduces secondary re-entrainment into the atmosphere. In this biological system, phytoremediation enables ecological control. Microbial mediation adds biochemical specificity. Microgreens direct both processes through their unique biology and structure.

These findings redefine microgreens as central agents in managing atmospheric particulates. They advance from passive interceptive surfaces to active, microbiome-assisted phytoremediation platforms. This work sets a mechanistic foundation for using microgreens as scalable, nature-based solutions to improve air quality in cities and controlled environments.

Keywords: Microgreens, Phytoremediation, particulate matter, Phyllosphere, Air Quality, Bioactive.

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OP 95

Instant Delivery Services: A Bibliometric Analysis

Areeba Khan

Research Scholar, Faculty of Management Studies, University of Lucknow

Abstract

The instant delivery sector represents a rapidly evolving segment of the Indian retail market. Its primary value proposition lies in the capability to deliver a broad assortment of goods to consumers within extremely short timeframes, often as little as 10 minutes. In India, key instant delivery platforms include Dunzo Daily, Swiggy Instamart, Big Basket Daily, and Blinkit. These firms employ a decentralized fulfillment model by establishing strategically located micro-warehouses, commonly known as “dark stores,” in densely populated urban areas. Orders are processed and dispatched from these facilities by delivery personnel, enabling near-immediate fulfillment. The instant delivery model can be viewed as an advanced extension of the traditional e-commerce framework, emphasizing speed and proximity to consumers. An initial dataset of 119 scholarly publications, covering the period from 2015 to 2026, was obtained from the Scopus database. After a rigorous selection and screening procedure, the final set of articles was examined using bibliometric methods supported by the *bibliometrix* package in RStudio, along with visualization software including VOSviewer. The data were examined using the Bibliometrix package in RStudio to evaluate trends in annual scientific output, identify leading authors, core publication sources, most cited countries, most relevant affiliations and analyze keyword structures using VOSviewer to conduct network analysis and generate visual representations of relationships among keywords. These visualizations enabled the identification of distinct keyword clusters, offering insights into the key research areas within the instant delivery domain.

OP 96

Nanostructured Transition Metal Oxides for Efficient Removal of Dyes from Wastewater**Subia Ambreen****Department of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Rajkiya Engineering College Bijnor, UP, India-246725****Abstract**

Organic dyes are amongst the rapidly increasing environmental contaminants across the globe. When these dyes are directly disposed into the aquatic bodies from various industries it causes serious threat to the environment. The complex molecular structures, high solubility, and chemical stability of these dyes make them resistant to the conventional treatment methods. Therefore, advance and efficient treatment methods are required. Nanomaterials have been vigorously investigated and efficaciously used in many areas including waste water treatment. Transition metals show extraordinary properties at nanoscale. Their physicochemical properties with high surface area and favourable electronic structure make them excellent semiconductor materials. The commonly employed methods for the synthesis of these nanomaterials are sol-gel, hydrothermal, CVD etc. TiO₂ nanomaterials are rigorously used for the degradation of dye under UV-VIS radiation. However, other transition metal oxides like ZnO, Fe₃O₄, CuO also serves as an efficient intriguing alternative to TiO₂. The advanced oxidation process occurring at the surface of the nanomaterials is responsible for the degradation of the dye. When these nanomaterials absorbs favourable radiation, electron hole pairs are generated. These electron hole pairs oxidize and break the dye molecules. This work demonstrate a detailed discussion on the synthesis and application of transition metal oxide nanomaterials for the effective removal of dyes from wastewater bodies. Various factors that have significant effect on the efficiency of the dye degradation are also discussed thoroughly like the amount of catalyst and dye, pH of the water system, temperature etc. Besides several suitable properties of transition metal oxides there are some challenges associated also like toxicity of materials, agglomeration and cost effectiveness.

Keywords: Nanomaterials, Water treatment, Photocatalyst, Advanced oxidation process.

OP 97**Sustainable development in commerce: an analytical study**

**Swapnil Gaur, Assistant Professor, School of Commerce,
Graphic Era Hill University**

Abstract

Sustainable development has emerged as a critical global objective, integrating economic growth with social equity and environmental protection. Commerce, as a central driver of economic activity, plays a pivotal role in shaping sustainable development outcomes. This paper examines the influence of commerce on sustainable development by analyzing how trade practices, business strategies, market mechanisms, and consumer behavior contribute to economic sustainability, social responsibility, and environmental conservation. The study highlights the evolving role of commercial organizations in adopting sustainable business models, ethical trade practices, green supply chains, and corporate social responsibility initiatives. Furthermore, it explores the challenges faced by the commercial sector in balancing profitability with sustainability goals, particularly in developing economies. The paper concludes that commerce, when aligned with sustainable principles, can act as a catalyst for inclusive growth, resource efficiency, and long-term socio-economic development. The findings underscore the need for policy support, stakeholder collaboration, and innovation-driven commercial practices to achieve sustainable development objectives effectively.

Keywords: Commerce, Sustainable Development, Economic Growth, Corporate Social Responsibility, Green Business Practices

OP 98**Cytological Studies in seventeen single tepalled cultivars of Tuberose (*Polianthes tuberosa* L.)****Dr. Loveneet Kaur,****P. G. Department of Botany & Environment Science, Mata Gujri College, Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab****Abstract:**

Cytological studies were carried out on 17 different single tepalled accessions viz., Prajwal, Shringar, GKTC-4, Phule Rajani, Arka Nirantar, Kalyani Single, Bidhan Ujjwal, Single, STR-505, Sikkim Selection, Hyderabad Single, Mexican Single, Bidhan Snigda, Sardar Local, Calcutta single, Pune Single and Arka Sugandhi of *P. tuberosa*. The present cytological studies provide the original gametic chromosome counts for 17 single cultivars of tuberose, along with comments on their male meiotic course, pollen viability/ sterility and pollen size studies. The perusal of the data for meiotic studies revealed that *P. tuberosa* had gametic chromosome number ($n=30$) with 30 (5 large and 25 small) bivalents, at Metaphase-I and 30:30 segregation at Anaphase-I (A-I). Chromosomes show irregular chromosome segregation. Laggards and bridges were the main abnormalities found in meiosis I. This was confirmed by the appearance of abnormal post-meiotic products, primarily monads and diads with irregularly shared cytoplasm and imperfect cytokinesis. In the present study, different-sized pollen grains ranging from normal pollens to Shrunken pollens have been observed in different accessions of *P. tuberosa*.

Keywords: Cytology, *Polianthes tuberosa* L., Tuberose, Meiosis and Pollen.

OP 99**The anti-colonization movement in Punjab 1901-1910**

Dr. Jagdeep Singh

,Assistant Proffesor In History, University College Miranpur,Patiala (Punjab)

The opening year of the twentieth century in India were marked by a revolutionary upsurge. The country was in the grip of an economic and political crisis. Frequent visitation of famine and appalling mortality from bubonic plague during the fast years of the nineteenth century had left their indelible marks. The antagonism between British bureaucracy and Western educated Indians had grown. particularly after the withdrawal of the Ilbert Bill in 1884 which had left them disgruntled and frustraed. At this juncture, however, certain develoments took place in Europe and Asia whic filled the Indian people with a new confidence and hope for the furture. The Goverment of India was increasingly using loyal Muslim elements against the nation movement, and the Punjab was equally covered by this all-India policy. Measures like the Land Alienation Act, of 1900, the Punjab Limitation Act, 1904, the Transfer of Property Act, 1904 and the Punjab Preemption Act, 1905, were considered as devere blows to nation unity and solidarity and an attempt to win the favour of the Muslim peasants at the cost of Hindus. Despite the undercurrent of dissatisfaction and frustration, there was hardly any sign of a political upsureg in the Punjab uptill now. It must be frankly admitted that so far the Punjabees have shown very little aptitude for political work to expose official injustice high handedness and oppression.

Keywords: Ilbert Bill, Punjab Limitation Act, 1904, Muslim peasants, British Bureaucracy and Western education.

OP 100

Impact of Early Childhood Care and Education on Holistic Development of Children Aged 3–6 Years: A Social Work Perspective**Dr. Lakhvir Singh,****Assistant Professor, Department of Social Work, Punjabi University, ,****²Snow Saadgi, Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, Punjabi University Patiala****Abstract:**

Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) is a crucial foundation for holistic child development and lifelong learning. This paper examines the impact of ECCE on children aged 3–6 years, focusing on cognitive, social, emotional, and physical domains of development. The study is based on a review of secondary sources, including national policies, educational frameworks, and empirical research studies. Findings indicate that participation in quality ECCE programs significantly enhances language development, early literacy and numeracy skills, social interaction, emotional regulation, and overall school readiness. The paper further emphasizes the role of trained educators, child-centered pedagogy, and developmentally appropriate learning environments as outlined in national education guidelines. In alignment with UGC regulations and the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, the study highlights ECCE as a key strategy for reducing educational inequities and promoting inclusive and sustainable development. The paper concludes that strengthening ECCE provisions is essential for achieving equitable educational outcomes and fostering human capital development.

Keywords: Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), Holistic Child Development, School Readiness, UGC Guidelines and National Education Policy 2020

OP 101
Improved Aniline Blue Photocatalytic Degradation with Ceramic Doped WO₃
Nanocomposites

Anjali Gupta¹ and R.K. Shukla^{2*}, Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh³

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³ **Department of Physics, DSMNRU, Lucknow, India**

Abstract

Due to the widespread manufacture and use of synthetic dyes worldwide, water contamination by these substances is a serious concern. Among the several approaches to tackle this problem, Advanced Oxidation Process, in which photocatalytic substances break down the dyes into non-toxic minerals by releasing Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) like superoxide and hydroxyl radicals in suspension. However, in order to activate this process, visible or UV light is needed. In this study, we synthesized the WO₃ doped sodium calcium based silicate ceramic by solid state reaction method and investigated their structural, optical and morphological properties. A small shift in peak locations was found by XRD analysis, suggesting lattice deformation brought on by WO₃ doping. While energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra verified elemental composition, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed homogeneous, evenly distributed nanoparticles. UV-visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis) indicated a redshift in absorption, lowering the bandgap and boosting visible-light absorption. Using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, distinctive functional groups were found. The catalytic performance of ceramic material was studied for the degradation of aniline blue dye using visible light source. It was observed that doped material enhance catalytic performance to completely degrade 10 ppm dye solution with 10 mg catalyst in 40 min under visible light source.

OP 102

Computational Toxicology of Environmental Microplastics: In-Silico Prediction of Emerging Hepatotoxic Risks through Molecular Docking and ADMET Profiling**B Gyani Priyanka Patnaik¹, Sanjeevi Ramakrishnan^{2*}, Dushyant Singh Chouhan³, and Anuradha Jayaraman⁴****¹Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Environmental Science, Nims Institute of Allied Medical Science and Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur–303121 (India).****²Associate Professor, Department of Environmental Science, Nims Institute of Allied Medical Science and Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur–303121 (India).****³Assistant Professor, Department of Environmental Science, Nims Institute of Allied Medical Science and Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur–303121 (India).****⁴Professor, Department of Biotechnology, Nims Institute of Allied Medical Science and Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur–303121 (India).****Abstract**

Environmental microplastics (MPs; <5 mm) are now ubiquitous across ecosystems, resulting in continuous human exposure via ingestion, inhalation, and trophic transfer. Increasing biomonitoring evidence reporting micro- and nanoplastics in human blood and hepatic tissues highlights the liver as a critical target organ for microplastic-induced toxicity. As the central site of xenobiotic metabolism, the liver is particularly vulnerable to physicochemical interactions between microplastics, their additives, and sorbed environmental contaminants; however, predictive human hepatotoxic risk assessment remains limited by experimental constraints.

This review critically synthesizes advances in computational toxicology approaches for predicting microplastic-associated hepatotoxicity, with a focus on molecular docking, quantitative structure–activity relationships (QSAR), and absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) profiling. We evaluate how polymer type, particle size (micro- to nanoscale), surface charge, and environmental aging influence hepatic bioavailability and molecular reactivity. Docking-based analyses targeting key hepatic proteins—including cytochrome P450 enzymes, bile acid transporters, nuclear receptors, and oxidative stress–inflammatory signaling regulators—are discussed to elucidate potential mechanisms underlying metabolic disruption, cholestasis, oxidative stress, and inflammatory liver injury. Complementary ADMET predictions are assessed to estimate bioaccumulation, metabolic interference, biliary clearance, and hepatotoxic endpoints.

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By integrating molecular interaction data with systems toxicology and adverse outcome pathway frameworks, this review demonstrates the utility of in-silico models for mechanistic risk ranking of microplastic polymers and associated chemicals. Finally, key methodological limitations and future directions, including artificial intelligence–assisted modeling and regulatory integration, are highlighted to advance predictive hepatotoxic risk assessment of environmental microplastics.

Keywords:

environmental microplastics; nanoplastics; hepatotoxicity; computational toxicology;

OP-103

The pursuit and challenges of Machine learning in clinical trials**Manisha Sharma¹, Saumya Goyal², Rubina Zaidi³****¹Assistant Professor, Department of Clinical Research, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, Swami Ram Himalayan University, Swami Ram Nagar, Dehradun****²Department of Clinical Pharmacy, SGRR University, Patel Nagar-248001, Dehradun Uttarakhand, India****³Department of Clinical Pharmacy, SGRR University, Patel Nagar-248001, Dehradun Uttarakhand, India****Abstract-**

There has been a significant upward push in artificial intelligence and system mastery. Drug, device, and treatment protocol testing has traditionally relied on trial data. Timelines, trial expenses, and compliance are common trial issues that have historically affected the volume of data gathered. The human workload has decreased, allowing people to live extraordinary lives. Researchers are now able to access, manage, and analyze data more quickly, affordably, and legally than ever before because of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI).

Clinical development is about to undergo a major transformation due to the rapid integration of massive novel digital data sources, the computing power to locate clinically relevant trends in the data using effective artificial intelligence and machine-learning algorithms, and the regulators' acceptance of this change through new partnerships. In order to speed up the research process and evaluate the risk and cost of clinical trials, machine, learning techniques and tools are utilized at every stage of development. This review offers relevant literature and drug discovery using these methods. The primary source of poor interpretability results that may limit potential uses and drug development is machine learning difficulties. Qualitative and methodological data needs to be collected in order to address a number of issues in clinical trials, such as confirming machine learning methods, improving decision-making, increasing awareness of strategies for machine learning, and detecting risk inadequacies in drug discovery. This article discusses the difficulties in clinical research as well as the use of AI and system learning to enhance drug development.

Keywords- Machine learning, Clinical trials, Artificial intelligence, AI, ML

OP 104

Green Synthesised Nanomaterials for Photocatalysis: Properties, Mechanisms, and Emerging Applications**Vishnu Kumar Dwivedi, R K Shukla and Anchal Srivastava**
Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India-226007**Abstract**

Green synthesis of nanomaterials has emerged as an environmentally benign and sustainable alternative to conventional physical and chemical fabrication methods, offering reduced toxicity, lower energy consumption, and improved biocompatibility. In recent years, green synthesized nanomaterials have attracted considerable attention for photocatalytic applications due to their unique structural, optical, and surface properties. This review provides a comprehensive overview of green synthesis approaches for photocatalytic nanomaterials, including plant extracts, microorganisms, biopolymers, and other renewable resources. The influence of green synthesis routes on particle size, morphology, crystallinity, surface chemistry, and defect formation and their consequent impact on photocatalytic performance is critically analyzed. Fundamental photocatalytic mechanisms, encompassing light absorption, charge carrier generation, separation, and reactive oxygen species formation, are discussed in detail. Recent advances in visible-light-driven photocatalysis and emerging applications in environmental remediation, water purification, hydrogen production, and antimicrobial activity are highlighted. Finally, the review addresses current challenges such as reproducibility, scalability, and stability, and outlines future perspectives for the rational design and practical implementation of green synthesized nanomaterials in sustainable photocatalytic systems.

Keywords: Photocatalysis, Nanomaterials, Plant extracts, Microorganisms

OP 105

To Find out the most preferred and popular social media platform for consumers

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Abstract

Social media has revolutionized communication patterns, consumer engagement, and digital marketing strategies, significantly shaping user preferences and brand interactions. This study aims to determine the most popular and preferred social media platform among consumers by systematically analyzing engagement patterns, demographic influences, and satisfaction levels. A structured survey was conducted among 450 respondents selected from a wider population of 510 individuals belonging to different age groups, professions, and digital usage categories.

The survey focused on essential parameters such as frequency of usage, type of content consumed, level of interaction with advertisements, and overall trust in platforms.

Keywords- Social media , Consumer behaviour, preferred media

OP 106**Impact of Financial Stress and Decision Fatigue on Personal Money Management among Salaried Employees****Ms. Jaya Pandey****Research Scholar, Department of Commerce (Finance), Amity University Lucknow****Abstract**

Salaried employees increasingly operate in financial environments characterized by rising living expenses, long-term credit commitments, income rigidity, and heightened expectations for financial security. These conditions often generate sustained financial stress, which can influence not only economic outcomes but also cognitive capacity and behavioral control. Simultaneously, salaried individuals are required to make repeated financial decisions related to spending prioritization, budgeting, saving, debt servicing, and investment planning. Continuous exposure to such decision demands may result in decision fatigue, a state of cognitive depletion that weakens self-regulation and judgment quality.

Although prior studies have examined financial stress and financial behavior separately, limited empirical research has investigated how cognitive fatigue interacts with financial stress to shape personal money management. Moreover, many existing financial behavior models rely on rational decision-making assumptions and inadequately account for psychological constraints, particularly in emerging economy contexts such as India.

The present study aims to examine the effect of financial stress and decision fatigue on personal money management behavior among salaried employees. Anchored in behavioral finance and cognitive resource theory, the study conceptualizes money management as a behavior influenced by both financial pressure and limited cognitive resources. It proposes that decision fatigue serves as a critical mechanism through which financial stress undermines effective money management practices.

A quantitative, cross-sectional research design is employed. Primary data will be collected from salaried employees working in public and private sector organizations using a structured questionnaire. Established and validated scales will be used to measure financial stress, decision fatigue, and personal money management behavior. The data will be analyzed using reliability

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and validity testing, correlation analysis, multiple regression, and structural equation modeling to examine the relationships among the variables.

The study is expected to demonstrate that higher levels of financial stress significantly increase decision fatigue, which in turn negatively affects personal money management outcomes such as savings discipline, expenditure control, and debt management. By integrating psychological fatigue into personal finance research, the study contributes to behavioral finance literature and offers practical implications for financial wellness initiatives, employer-supported interventions, and policy frameworks aimed at improving financial well-being among salaried employees.

Keywords: Financial Stress; Decision Fatigue; Personal Money Management; Behavioral Finance; Cognitive Depletion; Salaried Employees; Emerging Economy.

OP 107

Impact of Government Initiatives on Economic Condition of Sugarcane Farmers in Sitapur District Uttar Pradesh in Last Decade**Dr. Rahul Kumar Misra*****Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti Language University, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh (India).**

Abstract: Sugarcane cultivation constitutes a critical component of the agrarian economy of Uttar Pradesh, particularly in Sitapur district where a substantial proportion of rural households depend on it for livelihood. Over the last decade, the Government of India and the Government of Uttar Pradesh have implemented multiple policy initiatives aimed at improving the economic condition of sugarcane farmers. These include measures related to minimum support pricing (MSP) through Fair and Remunerative Price (FRP) and State Advised Price (SAP), expansion of institutional credit, crop insurance schemes, technological extension services, irrigation development, and reforms in sugar mill operations and cane payment mechanisms. The present study examines the impact of these government initiatives on the economic condition of sugarcane farmers in Sitapur district during the last ten years.

The study is based on a mixed-method research design, combining primary data collected from selected sugarcane-growing households with secondary data obtained from government reports, agricultural statistics, and policy documents. Economic indicators such as income levels, cost of cultivation, productivity, indebtedness, payment delays, and access to government schemes have been analysed to assess changes in farmers' economic status. The research also evaluates farmers' awareness and utilization of policy measures and identifies regional and structural constraints affecting policy outcomes.

The findings indicate that government initiatives have contributed to improvements in sugarcane productivity, expansion of irrigation facilities, and greater access to credit and input subsidies. Timely dissemination of improved seed varieties and mechanization support has positively influenced yield levels in several blocks of the district. However, the study also reveals persistent challenges that limit the overall economic gains of farmers. Delayed cane payments by sugar mills, rising input costs, fluctuating profitability, and uneven implementation of schemes have

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continued to affect income stability. Small and marginal farmers, in particular, remain vulnerable to debt and market uncertainties despite policy support.

The study concludes that while government interventions have had a moderately positive impact on the economic condition of sugarcane farmers in Sitapur district, their effectiveness has been constrained by institutional inefficiencies and implementation gaps. Strengthening payment enforcement mechanisms, improving extension outreach, and ensuring region-specific policy execution are essential for achieving sustainable economic improvement. The research offers policy-relevant insights that can aid in refining agricultural development strategies for sugarcane-dependent regions.

Keywords: Sugarcane farmers, Government initiatives, Economic condition, Sitapur district, Agricultural policy, minimum support pricing (MSP), Uttar Pradesh.

OP 108

निःशुल्क एवं अनिवार्य शिक्षा : अधिकार अधिनियम 2009

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सार

निःशुल्क एवं अनिवार्य शिक्षा अधिकार अधिनियम 2009 भारत में शिक्षा के क्षेत्र में एक महत्वपूर्ण पहल है। यह अधिनियम भारतीय संविधान के अनुच्छेद 21A के अंतर्गत शिक्षा को एक मौलिक अधिकार के रूप में स्थापित करता है। इस अधिनियम का मुख्य उद्देश्य 6 से 14 वर्ष की आयु के सभी बच्चों के लिए निःशुल्क और अनिवार्य प्राथमिक शिक्षा प्रदान करना है ताकि कोई भी बच्चा सामाजिक, आर्थिक तथा भौगोलिक कारणों से शिक्षा से वंचित न हो

इस अधिनियम ने बच्चों को औपचारिक शिक्षा व्यवस्था से जोड़ना तथा शिक्षा में समानता और समावेशन को सुनिश्चित किया।

यह अधिनियम शिक्षा को एक कानूनी अधिकार के रूप में स्थापित करता है और राज्य को बच्चों की शिक्षा के प्रति उत्तरदायी बनता है।

आरटीई अधिनियम न केवल बच्चों के शैक्षिक अधिकारों को स्पष्ट करता है, बल्कि राज्य सरकार, स्थानीय निकायों, विद्यालय प्रबंधन तथा अभिभावकों की जिम्मेदारियों को भी निर्धारित करता है। इसमें विद्यालयों के मानक, शिक्षक-छात्र अनुपात, भौतिक संसाधन, प्रवेश प्रक्रिया, निरंतर एवं व्यापक मूल्यांकन, बाल अनुकूल वातावरण और बालक के मानसिक उत्पीड़न पर प्रतिबंध जैसे महत्वपूर्ण प्रावधान शामिल किए गए हैं। साथ ही, अधिनियम के अंतर्गत कमजोर एवं वंचित वर्गों के बच्चों के लिए निजी विद्यालयों में आरक्षण जैसी व्यवस्था भी की गई है, जो सामाजिक न्याय की दिशा में एक महत्वपूर्ण कदम है।

इस अधिनियम के लागू होने के बाद प्राथमिक शिक्षा के क्षेत्र में नामांकन में वृद्धि, ड्रॉप-आउट दर में कमी तथा विद्यालय से बाहर रहने वाले बच्चों की संख्या में उल्लेखनीय सुधार देखे गए हैं।

OP 109

रामचरित मानस की वन्य सम्पदा और संरक्षण

PROF. RICHA PANDEY

Professor, Botany, Rajkiya Mahila Mahavidyalaya Mishrikh Sitapur

शोध सार

भारतीय ज्ञान परम्परा प्राकृतिक तत्वों में जीवन ही नहीं अपितु देवत्व की प्रतिष्ठा से अनुप्राणित है। धार्मिक अनुष्ठानों एवं दैनिक क्रियाकलापों में नवग्रह मण्डलद सूर्य, चन्द्रमा, मंगल, बुध, वृहस्पति, शुक्र, शनि, राहु, केतु के पूजन का विधान है। पृथ्वी, जल, आकाश, वायु और अग्नि में पंच महाभूत की देवता हैं। स्वस्त्ययन में इन सबके शान्ति की प्रार्थना एवं कामना की जाती है। देवी देवताओं के वाहन के रूप में पशु पक्षियों और पदार्थों या चढ़ावे के रूप में पत्रों, पुष्पों, फलों एवं पौधों के साथ ही साथ पकवानों की विहित एवं निषिद्ध परम्परा है। यहीं नहीं पूजन हेतु भी आवश्यक प्राकृतिक सामग्री के चयन एवं प्राप्ति की प्रक्रिया तथा अवसरानुकूलता व प्रतिकूलता का विधिवत उल्लेख है। अतः इनके संरक्षण की भावना स्वतः स्फूर्त है।

रामचरित मानस व्यक्तिगत चरित्र, परिवार, समाज की मर्यादा के पोषण

एवं संरक्षण के साथ-साथ प्राकृतिक तत्वों के पोषण एवं संरक्षण का मानक ग्रन्थ है। इस शोध पत्र में गोस्वामी तुलसीदास द्वारा उल्लिखित प्राकृतिक तत्वों में से वन्य सम्पदा को चुना गया है। पर्वतीय, स्थलीय एवं जलीय पौधों के वर्णन एवं उनके संरक्षण के स्थलों को इंगित किया गया है। मानस में वन्य और उपवन्य के साथ साथ 'रेलू बगीचे में पादप रोपण एवं संरक्षण की परम्परा का दिग्दर्शन होता है आज की अनियमित दोहन शैली के जीवन में रामचरित मानस का मार्गदर्शन अनुकरणीय है।

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OP 110

The Right to Food as a Human Right in India: A Gender Justice Perspective under the National Food Security Act, 2013**Dr. Kaneez Fatima****Assistant Professor, Faculty of Juridical Sciences, Rama University, Kanpur Nagar****Abstract**

The right to food has a long history as a recognized human right under international law and has increasingly gained legal recognition in domestic legal systems. In India, this right was legally recognized through the National Food Security Act, 2013 (NFSA), one of the world's largest food security programs, providing subsidized food grains to nearly two-thirds of the population. While the NFSA is a major step toward eliminating hunger and malnutrition, legal discourse on the right to food has largely ignored the gendered aspects of food provision, particularly the unpaid work of women in households. This article argues that the NFSA views women's work as a free resource for implementing the state's welfare agenda. Women's work is crucial in converting subsidized food grains into edible food, yet this contribution remains unreflected in the legal framework. The article argues that socializing women's domestic cooking requires reimagining the right to food as a "right to cooked food." Such a reframing would shift cooking from a private household responsibility to a form of public care provision, thereby making visible the traditionally undervalued function of social reproduction.

This study situates the right to food within international human rights law, which emphasizes access to adequate, safe, and nutritious food for physical and mental health. It further examines the constitutional and human rights foundations of the right to food in India and analyzes the impact of international legal norms on the Indian legal system. Adopting a constitutional, human rights, and gender justice perspective, this article offers a critical re-examination of the right to food in India, emphasizing the need to integrate women's labor and social reproduction into food security law and policy.

Keywords- National Food Security, NFSA, Constitution, Social responsibility, Population, International human rights

OP-111

**TAPINAROF LOADED CHITOSAN NANOPARTICLES: PREPARATION
EVALUATION AND *IN VITRO* RELEASE STUDIES****Suvarna G. Bhokare****Department of Pharmaceutics, Srinath College of Pharmacy, Bajaj Nagar,
Chh.Sambhajinagar India - 431136.****Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of the present study was to develop sustained release biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles of Tapinarof. **Methods:** Nanoparticles were prepared by modified ionotropic gelation method using 3² full factorial designs. From the preliminary trials, the constraints for independent variables X1 (concentration of chitosan) and X2 (concentration of sodium tripolyphosphate) have been fixed. Factors included concentration of chitosan and sodium tripolyphosphate, have been examined to investigate effect on particle size, encapsulation efficiency, zeta potential, % release, scanning electron microscopy, Fourier transfer infrared study and X-ray diffraction and release study of Tapinarof nanoparticles.

Results: The prepared nanoparticles were white, free-flowing and spherical in shape. The infrared spectra showed stable character of Tapinarof in the drug-loaded nanoparticles and revealed the absence of drug polymer interactions. The chitosan nanoparticles have a particle diameter ranging approximately 114.5±3.61 to 724±2.51 nm and a zeta potential -13.12 to -52.63 mV. The *in vitro* release behavior from all the drug loaded batches were found to follow first order and provided sustained release over a period of 10 h. The Zeta potential of all the batches were in the range of -13.12 to -52.63 mv. The release profiles of all batches were very well fitted by Korsmeyer Peppas model.

Conclusion: The best-fit release kinetics was achieved with Korsmeyer peppas model. The release of Tapinarof was influenced by the drug to polymer ratio and particle size. These results indicate that Tapinarof nanoparticles could be effective in sustaining drug release for a prolonged period.

Keywords: Tapinarof, Biodegradable, Particle size analysis, Ionotropic gelation

OP-112

Serum Interleukin 26 as a biomarker for disease activity assessment and association of single nucleotide polymorphism in interleukin 26 gene in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus

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ABSTRACT**Background:**

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic multisystem autoimmune disease characterized by immune dysregulation and fluctuating disease activity. Conventional biomarkers such as complement levels and anti-dsDNA antibodies have limitations in reliably reflecting disease activity. Interleukin-26 (IL-26), a pro-inflammatory cytokine of the IL-10 family with unique DNA-binding properties, has emerged as a potential mediator of autoimmune inflammation; however, data on its role in SLE, particularly in the Indian population, remain limited.

Methods:

This prospective observational study included 180 participants comprising 140 clinically confirmed SLE patients and 40 age- and sex-matched healthy controls. Disease activity was assessed using the SLE Disease Activity Index-2000 (SLEDAI-2K). Serum IL-26 levels were quantified using sandwich ELISA. Additional parameters including complement components (C3, C4), anti-dsDNA antibodies, urinary protein-creatinine ratio (uPCR), and liver enzymes were analyzed. Genotyping for IL-26 single nucleotide polymorphism rs2870946 was performed using conventional PCR followed by Sanger sequencing in a subset of 30 individuals (25 cases and 5 controls).

Results:

Serum IL-26 levels were significantly elevated in SLE patients compared to controls (404 ± 116.6 pg/mL vs. 123 ± 20.2 pg/mL; $p < 0.0001$). Patients with active disease (SLEDAI > 4) demonstrated significantly higher IL-26 levels than those with inactive disease. IL-26 showed a positive correlation with SLEDAI scores, anti-dsDNA antibody levels, and uPCR, and an inverse correlation with complement C3 and C4 levels. Receiver operating characteristic analysis

demonstrated good diagnostic performance for IL-26 in distinguishing cases from controls (AUC = 0.87), with 100% specificity at a cut-off value >219 pg/mL. The rs2870946 polymorphism was detected exclusively in SLE cases, with heterozygous variants observed in 6.6% of patients, while all controls exhibited the wild-type genotype.

Conclusion:

Elevated serum IL-26 levels are strongly associated with disease activity in SLE, highlighting its potential utility as a sensitive biomarker for disease monitoring. The exclusive presence of rs2870946 polymorphism in SLE patients suggests a possible genetic association warranting further investigation in larger cohorts.

Keywords: Systemic lupus erythematosus, Interleukin-26, Disease activity, rs2870946, Biomarker.

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